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Oybek Raximberdiyev

Gollandiyada «Lolalar» inqirozi: Sharhlar, qarashlar va ilmiy-tarixiy yechimlar

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Kalit so'zlar

Lolalar inqirozi, varrantdan foydalanish, devalvatsiya, inflyatsiya, Haarlem mediatorlari, chayqovchilik, forvard shartnomalari.

Annotatsiya

Insonlar o'z xatti-harakatlari bilan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni boshqaradi, dunyoni o'zgartiradi. Taassufki, shaxslar o'zaro mulkiy munosabatlarni o'rnatish, boyliklarga ega bo'lish, ularni taqsimlash da'vosida global va mintaqaviy inqirozlarning yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo'ladi. Mazkur ilmiy-tarixiy maqolada insoniyat tarixida sodir bo'lgan global iqtisodiy inqirozlarning dastlabki ikkitasining mazmun-mohiyati, kelib chiqish sabablari va ularni barataraf etish yo'lida hukumatlar tomonidan olib borilgan iqtisodiy siyosatlar tarixiy faktlarga tayanib, tahlil etilgan.

Kirish

Olamda odamzod yuksak ma'naviy sifatlari bois jamiki mavjudotlarning gultoji hisoblanadi. Insoniyat eng katta bunyodkor, obod qiluvchi va yaratuvchi kuchga ega bo'lish bilan birga afsuski, ba'zan nafs ko'yida buzg'unchilikka ham qodir...

Insonlar o'z xatti-harakatlari bilan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni boshqaradi, dunyoni o'zgartiradi. Taassufki, shaxslar o'zaro mulkiy munosabatlarni o'rnatish, boyliklarga ega bo'lish, ularni taqsimlash da'vosida global va mintaqaviy inqirozlarning yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo'ladi. Dunyoda sodir bo'lgan inqirozlarni o'ylab topgan ham, ularni bartaraf etish choralarini ko'rgan ham, ilm-fanni rivojlantirib, koinotni kashf qilayotgan ham, o'zi to'qib chiqargan turli aqida va g'oyalarga mahkum bo'lib, butun xalqlar, mavjudotlarning boshiga turli balolarni yog'dirayotgan ham inson hisoblanadi.

Ayrim davlat arboblari, siyosatchilarning olamni o'zgartirish da'vosi, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy qonun-qoidalarni inobatga olmay qabul qilgan qarorlari tufayli global inqirozlar, urushlar va ocharchiliklar vujudga kelgani ham sir emas. Dunyo olimlarining qaydlariga ko'ra, sayyoramizda global tus olgan inqirozlar jami 27 tani tashkil qilgan ekan.

Ushbu ilmiy-tarixiy maqolada inqirozlarning kelib chiqish sabablari, davlatlar tomonidan ularni bartaraf etish maqsadida ko'rilgan chora-tadbirlar tafsilotlariga oid tarixiy faktlar o'rganib chiqildi. Dastlab xronologik nuqtai nazardan 1634-1637 yillarda Gollandiyada sodir bo'lgan iqtisodiy-moliyaviy inqirozlarning kelib chiqish sabablari, olib borilgan iqtisodiy siyosat va uning oqibatlariga to'xtalangan. Davlat rahbarlari, jamoat va siyosat arboblari tomonidan qabul qilingan qarorlar, ko'rilgan chora-tadbirlar o'rganib chiqilgan va mualliflik qarashlari bayon etilgan.

Adabiyotlar tahlili

Ushbu mavzu bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar, ilmiy qarashlar va tavsilotlar olimlar tomonidan kam o'rganilgan bo'lsada, tarixiy manbalar, o'sha davr voqealari ayrim olimlarning monografiyalari, jurnallarda qayd etilgan. Ular sirasiga L.Ye.Grinin, A.V.Korotayevlarni keltirish mumkin. Global inqiroz va retrospektiva, deb nomlangan ilmiy risolada ushbu olimlar Gollandiyada 1634-1637-yillarda sodir bo'lgan iqtisodiy inqirozning kelib chiqish sabablari, uning oqibatlari va hukumat rahbarlari, mutasaddi

Jan-Leon Jerom, 1882-yil.

tashkilotlar tomonidan amalga oshirilgan chora-tadbirlarning samarasi, ularning ta'siri bo'yicha aniq dalillar o'rin olgan.

S.Frink tomonidan ham dunyo inqirozlari, ularning turlari va bo'lib o'tgan iqtisodiy-moliyaviy buxronlarning ta'siriga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlarida (Frink S. Crises Management: Planning for the Inevitable. Backinprint.com, 2000) ham biz tomonimizdan tayyorlangan mavzu doirasida tahlillar amalga oshirilgan. Ko'xna adabiyo tlarni varaqlaganimizda Nobel mukofoti laureati R. Samuelson (Interaktions between the Multiplier Analysis and the Principle of Acceleration// Review Economics Statistik. 1939. Vol. 21) va V.Rostov (The World Economy. History and Prospect. L., 1978) tomonidan o'sha paytdagi iqtisodiy vaziyatlarning holati, davlatning bir-biri bilan mehnat, tovar ayirboshlashi, savdo-sotiq va soliq tizimlarining ko'rinishi, natural xo'jalikdan pul ko'rinishiga o'tish jarayonlari, Gollandiyada sodir bo'lgan "lolalar jazavasi"ning tub mohiyati boshqa davlatlarga yetkazilgan zararlar va jahon iqtisodiyotiga mavjud holatlar aniq misollar va faktlar bilan ochib berilgan.

Shuningdek, V.Svetkov muallifligida nashr qilingan «Davrlar va inqirozlar» deb nomlangan nazariy-uslubiy qo'llanmaning "Jahon inqirozlari tarixi" bo'limida barcha bo'lib

o'tgan inqirozlarning ta'siri ikki va undan ortiq davlatlar iqtisodiyotiga ko'rsatgan zarari bilan bog'liq tanqidiy tahlillar aniq sanalar, statistik ko'rsatkichlar asosida sharhlangan. Tadqiqot ob'yekti sifatida iqtisodiy inqirozlarning kelib chiqish sabablari, tashqi va ichki ta'sirlar, inqirozning yashirin fazalari va inqirozga qarshi kurashishda qabul qilingan qarorlar jamlanmasi namoyon bo'ladi. V.Svetkov dunyo inqirozlarining xronologiyasini tuzib chiqqan bo'lib, ularning sabab va oqibatlarini tahlil qilmagan. Yaqin tarixda bo'lib o'tgan jahon moliyaviy-iqtisodiy inqirozlari, davlatlar hukumatlari tomonidan tijorat banklari, moliya tashkilotlarini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha amalga oshirgan siyosatlarining ijobiy va salbiy jihatlari ochib bergan.

Yuqorida zikr etilgan barcha olimlarning tadqiqotlarida asosan, 20-asrdan keyin vujudga kelgan global tus olgan inqirozlarning sabablarini ochib berishga ko'proq urg'u qaratilgan. Biz tomonimizdan olib borilgan mazkur maqolada esa, usha davrdagi iqtisodiy-siyosiy vaziyat, Gollandiya sindromi deb atalib kelinayotgan iqtisodiy tarixning daqiq joylari tahlil etilgan va sabablari, oqibatlari statistik dalillar orqali ochib berilgan. Shu jihati bilan mazkur tadqiqot ushbu mavzu bo'yicha qilingan izlanishlardan farq qiladi.

1637-yilda bosilgan, Gollandiya lolamaniyasidan olingan risola

Metodlar

Maqola tarixiy faktlar asosida tayyorlangan bo'lib, unda asosan taqqoslama tahlillar, o'sha paytda chiqarilgan qarorlarning nechog'lik ahamiyatli ekanligi, bozorlarning holati, iqtisodiy tuzumlarining ta'siri baholangan. Dunyo inqirozlarining kelib chiqish sabablari, oqibatlar va yechimlari nimalardan iborat ekanligi metod sifatida belgilangan. Ushbu uchlikka qurilgan maqolada qiyosiy dalillar, tarixiy qarorlar, statistik ko'rsatkichlar tahlili kabi metodlardan foydalanilgan bo'lib, olimlarning bergan baho va qarashlariga munosabat ham keltirib o'tilgan.

Natijalar

Kelib chiqish sabablari.

Ko'pchilik insonlar lola ilk marta Gollandiyada yetishtirilgan, deb noto'g'ri o'ylashadi. Ushbu gulning vatani – G'arbiy O'rta Yer dengizi va Markaziy Osiyoning bir qismi (Pokiston, Afg'oniston va Turkiya) hisoblanadi. Lolaning ayrim turlari yovvoyi holda Shimoliy Afrika, Janubiy Yevropa va Yaponiyada o'sadi. Ushbu gul Yevropaga 1554-yilda kirib kelgan. Turkiya elchisi Busbek mamlakat bo'ylab sayohatlaridan birida chiroyli gulni ko'radi va Augsburgga (Germaniyadagi shahar) birinchi lola piyozlarini yuboradi.

Lola Sharqdan olib kelinganda o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega edi, ya'ni bir necha yil o'tgach, gullarning rangi o'zgarar edi. Bu degani, bir dona lola piyozining egasi vaqt o'tib mutlaqo yangi va noyob navning egasi bo'lishi mumkin. Bu bozorda oddiy lola piyozlariga qaraganda bir necha barobar yuqori narxli

mahsulot, degani edi. 1612-yilda Amsterdamda yangi katalog nashr etildi, unda yuzdan ortiq lola navlari mavjudligini ko'rish mumkin.

XVII asrning dastlabki yigirmanchi yillarida lola bozorining talab va taklif doirasi kengaydi. Professional mirishkorlar osonlikcha bozorga kirishlari mumkin edi, chunki lolalar sotuvi boshqa savdolar singari qat'iy tartibga solinmagandi. Dastlab lolalar o'ta noyob hisoblanganligi tufayli faqat yuqori tabaqa vakillarining saroylarida uchratish mumkin edi. Shuning uchun avval lolalar zodagonlar jamiyatining hashamatli boyligi bo'lib kelgan bo'lsa, keyinchalik bozorga o'rta sinf vakillarining kirib kelishi natijasida bog'lar barpo etish tobora ommalashib ketadi. Hatto xalqaro savdo ham juda tez rivojlanadi.

Yetkazib beruvchilarning xilma-xilligi tufayli narxlarga cheklov qo'yiladi. Bu mirishkorlar boshqa biron bir kultivatordan nusxa ko'chirish, yuqori foyda olish uchun yangi navlarni yaratishga majbur bo'ldi, degani edi. Shunday qilib, yangi yaratilgan navlarga talab odatiy lolalarga qaraganda yuqoriroq bo'lgan.

1630-yillarda yangi navlarga bo'lgan talab taklifdan oshib ketadi. 16-asrning 20-yillarida Ispaniya bilan qayta urush boshlangani sababli, Gollandiya iqtisodiyoti inqirozga yuz tutgan bo'lsa, 1630-yillarda tez tiklanish ushbu tendensiyani yanada kuchaytirdi.

Lolalarga talab tobora ortib borar, ammo ta'minot yetarli emas edi. Gollandiyaliklarning asosiy qishloq xo'jaligi va iqtisodiyoti lola biznesiga bog'lanib qoladi. Gollandiyanning katta shaharlari hisoblangan Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Xarlem va Leydenda lolalar savdosi bo'yicha asosiy oldi-sotdi ishlarini olib boruvchi birjalar tashkil qilindi.

Bu birjalarda nafaqat «jonli» lolalar balki hali yetishtirilib ulgurmagan lola piyozlarini ham sotib olish mumkin edi. Bundan tashqari, bu yerda faqat oldi-sotdi ishlari emas, balki kelajak uchun ham shartnomalar tuzilgan. Bu shartnomalarning mazmuni kelajakda belgilangan vaqtda va kelishilgan miqdorda lola piyozlarini sotish va sotib olishdan iborat edi (hozirgi tilda aytganda varrantdan foydalanishgan).

Aynan mana shu varrantlardan foydalanish «sovun pufagi»ning shakllanishiga olib keldi. Ko'plab gollandiyaliklarning bu bozorga kirib kelishi uchun imkoniyat yaratib berdi.

Bu birjada nafaqat o'stirilgan lolalar, balki

kelgusi yil kuzda ekilishi kerak bo'lgan lola piyozlari ham oldi-sotdi qilingan. Ushbu bitimlar «shamol ko'llari», deb ham atalgan. Bir so'z bilan aytganda, birja faoliyatida «hayot avjida» edi, faqat bu yerda aksiyalar emas, balki lola piyozlari taxminiy narxlarda sotilar edi. Birja hayotidagi o'sish ko'plab gollandiyaliklarni mana shu bozorga kirishga undaydi. Lola maniyasida qatnashishni xohlagan gollandiyaliklar o'zlarining yagona mulklarini ham sotish hisobiga bir juft lola olish va keyinchalik uni qimmat narxga sotishga oshiqar edilar.

1630-yildan keyin piyozlarning narxlari muttasil o'sib borishi sababli, bozorda yangi turdagi o'yin kelib chiqdi: floristlar piyozlarni chayqovchilik uchun aktiv sifatida ishlatishdi. Bundan tashqari, keng jamiyat orasida «lola piyozlari bilan chayqovchilik qilish tez va yuqori foyda keltiradi», degan vasvasalar kelib chiqdi. Odamlar o'zlarining piyozlarini sotish, tezroq foyda olishga kirishib ketishdi. Bu esa, bozorni harakatga soluvchi mexanizmni buzdi, ya'ni bozorda hamma o'z mahsulotini sotar, bu esa, talab yo'q ammo taklif ko'p, degani edi.

Mana shu vaziyatdan keyin birjada lolalar narxi keskin tushishni boshlaydi, talab juda kam lekin taklif haddan tashqari ko'payib ketadi.

Qanday oqibatlarga olib keldi?

Inqiroz 1637-yil boshida, narxlar o'sishda davom etadimi yoki yo'qmi, degan shubha paydo bo'lganida yuz bergan. Bir kecha-

kunduzda lolalarning narxlari keskin tushib ketib, boylarlarni yo'q qildi va ko'plab oddiy golland oilalari uchun moliyaviy halokatni yuzaga keltirdi.

Narxlar «qulagani»dan so'ng xaridorlar lolalar piyozlari uchun forvard shartnomalari bo'yicha to'lovdan bosh tortdilar. Dehqonlar to'lashni talab qilish foyda bermasligini bilishgan va shu sababli 1637-yil 23-fevralda Amsterdamda umumiy jarayonni hal qilish uchun uchrashishdi. Ularning aksariyati 1636-yil 30-noyabrdan keyin imzolangan barcha shartnomalar asl narxining 10 foizini to'lash bo'yicha kelishishga urindilar. Ushbu qonuniy, majburiy bo'lmagan taklif esa xaridorlarni ishontira olmadi, ular hali ham shartnomalarni hech qanday to'lovlarsiz to'liq bekor qilishni talab qilishar edi.

O'sha paytdagi ko'plab golland yozuvchilarining fikriga qaraganda, piyozlar davlatning zarar ko'rish yoki rivojlanishi uchun unchalik ham ta'sir ko'rsatmagan. Bunga ikkita sababni asos qilib olishadi: **birinchidan**, piyozlarning butun savdosi davlat iqtisodiyotining unchalik katta qismi hisoblanmagan. Lola piyozlari bilan shug'ullanuvchi ko'plab floristlarning aksariyati uchun esa, bu qo'shimcha ish hisoblangan.

Garchi chayqovchilarning kutilgan daromadlari ko'kka sovurilib ketgan bo'lsa ham, ko'rilgan zarar asosan shaxsiy daromad hisobiga to'g'ri kelgan va ular o'zlarini o'zlar qoplar edi. Lekin shunga qaramay inqirozdan katta zarar ko'rganlar yetarlicha topilardi. Ular o'zlarining ko'chmas mulklarini sotgan yoki garovga qo'ygan, narxlar tushgandan keyin

Reynsburgdagi lola dalalari va shamol tegirmoni. Klod Monening rasmlari, 1886-yil. Vinsent Van Gog muzeyi, Amsterdam.

esa hech vaqosiz qolgan oddiy aholi, o'z yerlarini foydalanish uchun florist va chayqovchilarga bergan dehqonlar edi. Biroq, bu tarqoq muammo butun iqtisodiyotga ta'sir qilmadi va butun epizod qisqa lokalizatsiya qilindi.

Yuqorida aytib o'tilgan **ikkinchi** jihat shundan iboratki, lola piyozlari bozorida ishlatiladigan kreditning aksariyati piyoz savdosi bilan shug'ullanuvchi tomonlar va moliya institutlari tomonidan berilgan edi. Shunday qilib, kredit yo'qotishlari piyoz bozorida ajralib turdi va umuman banklarga ta'sir ko'rsatmadi. Bu Gollandiyaning to'lov va kredit tizimida barqarorlikni keltirib chiqardi. Iqtisodiy o'sish uchun katta tahdid bo'lgan kreditlarning muzlashi Lolamaniya halokatining natijasi emas edi. Bu holatdan asosiy zarar ko'rganlar oddiy aholi va dehqonlar bo'lib qoldi. Ushbu mojarolarni xususiy ravishda hal qilishning muvaffaqiyatsizligini tushunib yetgan hukumat xolis bo'lish maqsadida munozarali shartnomalarni saralash majburiyatini mahalliy hokimiyat idoralari zimmasiga yuklab qo'yadi.

Munozara

1637-yil aprelda Gollandiya oliy sudi barcha kelishuvlarni to'xtatib turishga qaror qildi va shahar sudlariga nizolarni mahalliy darajada hal qilish uchun yetarli ma'lumotlar yig'ishni buyurdi. Garchi markaziy parlament ushbu qarorni qonuniy kuchga kiritib qo'ygan bo'lsa ham shaharlar uni amalga oshirishga

urinishmadi. Sud qarori va uning ijrosi ta'minlanmagani dehqonlar va oddiy «jabrlanuvchi» aholi uchun juda katta zararni keltirib chiqardi.

Qaror ijrosini amalga oshirmayotganlarni shahar sudlari shunday izohlashadi: **«Yaqinda gullash mavsumi, ya'ni dehqonlar uchun lola hosillarini yig'ish va sotish davri hisoblanadi».**

Inqirozgacha hech narsa to'lamagan barcha shartnoma egalari bundan foyda olishdi. Keyinchalik barcha shartnomalarning 3,5 foizini bekor qilish bo'yicha qaror qabul qilingan. Avval bu qarorni Haarlem shahar kengashi joriy qiladi. Bir yil o'tgandan keyin esa boshqa shaharlar ham bu qarorni qabul qilishadi.

Odatda do'konlarning tavsiyalariga amal qilgan shahar sudyalari qaror qabul qilishga shoshilmadilar. Chayqovchilik bilan shug'ullanadigan rasmiylar mojaroni o'z manfaatlarini uchun hal qilishga umid qilishdi va mojaro misli ko'rilmagan darajada murakkab, keng miqyosli bo'lib chiqdi. Haarlemda ehtiroslar keskin avj oldi. Shahar kengashi mart oyida shartnomalarni xaridorlar foydasiga, aprel oyida esa aksincha sotuvchilar foydasiga qaror chiqardi va Bosh shtatlardan yordam so'radi.

Kreditorlar va qarzdorlarni bir-birlari bilan shaxsiy muomalada bo'lishga majbur qilgan oddiy yechim ishonch inqirozini yanada kuchaytirdi va Gollandiya jamoatchiligining ishonchli muhitini abadiy yo'qqa chiqardi.

Qarama-qarshiliklar huquqiy sohadan chiqib ketib, yana bir necha yil davomida oilaviy nizolar darajasiga ko'tarildi: kreditorlar qarzdorlarni ta'qib qildilar, qarzdorlar to'lashdan bosh tortdilar. Birinchi marta «nol warrant»ga toqat qilmaslik Haarlemda tan olingan: 1638-yil yanvarda Gollandiyadagi gul turlari bo'yicha birinchi hakamlik sudi ishini boshladi.

To'rtta CBS vositachilarining asosiy vazifasi haqiqatni aniqlash emas, balki shahar aholisini muzokaralarga majburlash orqali yarashtirish edi. 1638-yil may oyida Haarlem nizoni hal qilishning standart tartibini ishlab chiqdi: agar sotuvchi qarzni qaytarishni talab qilsa, qarzdor-xaridor sotuvchiga shartnoma narxining 3,5 foizini to'laganidan keyin har qanday majburiyatdan ozod qilingan. Ushbu shartlar na gul ishlab chiqaruvchilar, na lolalarni sevadigan qarzdorlarga foydali bo'lmadi; munozarachilarga tinchlik bilan tarqalish Gollandiya oliy sudining odil hukmini topishdan ko'ra osonroq edi. Ushbu yo'nalish bo'yicha harakat qilgan Haarlem mediatorlari o'z shaharlaridagi barcha nizolarni 1639-yil yanvargacha hal qildilar.

Noaniqlik holati lola shinavandalari o'rtasida vahima qo'zg'atdi. Bukletlar, proklamatsiyalar va multfilmlar tayyorlanib, mamlakat bo'ylab «aqldan ozgan» chayqovchilarni qoralovchi lavhalar tarqatildi. Tabiiy ofat uchun javobgarlarni qidirish boshlandi. Bu masala bo'yicha parlamentlar 1637-yil 27-aprelda qaror qabul qildilar. Barcha lola shartnomalari, imzolangan sanasidan

qat'i nazar, vaqtincha to'xtatildi.

Xulosa

Amsterdam Regenslari shartnomalarni o'z kuchida qoldirishga qaror qildilar, mirishkorlar va lolani xush ko'ruvchilar esa sudga berish huquqini saqlab qolishdi; Haarlem, Alkmaar va Gollandiyaning boshqa barcha shaharlari lola shartnomalarini bekor qildi. Noyob lola bozori ikki yil ichida falokatdan qutuldi. 1637-yil yozida haqiqiy bitimlar narxi bir piyoz uchun ming gilderga (gektar) yaqinlashdi. 1640-yillarning boshlaridagi ma'lumotlardan ko'rinib turibdiki, bu vaqtga kelib noyob lolalarning narxi 1636-1637-yillardagiga qaraganda qariyb olti baravar past bo'lgan.

Narxlar va foydaning pasayishi ortidan lolalar yetishtiradigan fermer xo'jaliklari soni asta-sekin kamayib bordi. XVII asrning o'rtalariga kelib, Gollandiyada barcha lola ishlab chiqarish Haarlem shahar chegaralarida to'planib, omon qolgan o'nga yaqin fermer xo'jaligi milliy bozorni taqsimlab olgan edi.

Gullar «maniyalari» vaqti-vaqti bilan XVII asrda, hatto XX asrda ham uchrab turardi. 1703-yilda Usmon imperiyasida Ahmed III hokimiyat tepasiga kelishi bilan «lolalar asri» – yigirma yetti yillik «ma'rifatparvar», niqobsiz hedonizm davri boshlandi. O'zini o'ylovchi va lolalarni yaxshi ko'radigan yangi sulton Istanbul jamiyatida ham lola maniyasining yangi to'lqinini yaratgan edi.

Transitioning to a green economy and implementing sustainable technological changes in Uzbekistan

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Kalit so'zlar

Green Economy, sustainable development, renewable energy, carbon emissions, climate change, Central Asia, technological innovation, environmental policy, clean energy, energy efficiency, green jobs sustainability.

Abstract

Although it has one of the fastest-growing economies in the region, Uzbekistan nonetheless has a lot of environmental problems. Adopting sustainable technical advancements and transitioning to a green economy are essential to addressing these issues. This paper discusses the significance of Uzbekistan's transition to a green economy and the actual application of sustainable technical developments. It looks at the issues preventing the use of sustainable technologies and provides recommendations to address them.

Introduction

Numerous environmental issues, including air pollution, deforestation, water scarcity, and climate change, are currently affecting the planet. These difficulties have an impact on the economy and society in addition to the environment.

To solve these issues, nations worldwide are switching to a green economy, which encourages inclusive and sustainable economic growth, lowers environmental hazards, and boosts social fairness. Despite being one of the fastest-growing economies in the region, Uzbekistan nevertheless has serious environmental problems that need to be addressed immediately. Transitioning to a green economy and implementing sustainable technical advancements is crucial to secure sustainable economic growth.

Literature Review

Many studies have shown that transitioning to a green economy can have significant economic, social, and environmental benefits. For example, a study by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) found

that transitioning to a green economy could result in higher GDP growth, job creation, and poverty reduction in Asia and the Pacific.

The literature also highlights the importance of overcoming the challenges that hinder the adoption of sustainable technologies. Lack of awareness and understanding of sustainable technologies is a common challenge in many countries, including Uzbekistan.

A study by the International Finance Corporation (IFC) found that awareness-raising campaigns and education programs can play a crucial role in promoting the adoption of sustainable technologies (IFC, 2018). The study recommended developing training programs for businesses and individuals, as well as using social media and other communication channels to raise awareness about sustainable technologies.

Financing and investing in sustainable technologies is another significant challenge. Studies have shown that many sustainable technologies require significant upfront investment, which can be a barrier for businesses and individuals. A study by the United Nations Industrial Development

Organization (UNIDO) found that the development of financial instruments, such as green bonds and venture capital funds, can help mobilize financing for sustainable projects (UNIDO, 2019). The study also highlighted the importance of government support for developing financial instruments and promoting sustainable investments.

Regulatory frameworks to support the adoption of sustainable technologies are also essential.

Studies have shown that the development of standards and certification systems and policies and regulations supporting sustainable technologies can play a crucial role in promoting their adoption.

A study by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) found that the development of regulatory frameworks can provide a stable and predictable business environment, which can encourage investment in sustainable technologies (UNEP, 2018).

Overall, the literature suggests that transitioning to a green economy and adopting sustainable technological changes are essential for addressing Uzbekistan and other countries' environmental, economic, and social challenges. However, the practical implementation of sustainable technologies requires overcoming several challenges, such as more awareness, financing, and regulatory frameworks.

In order to promote the adoption of sustainable technologies, there is a need for education and awareness-raising campaigns, increased investment in sustainable technologies, and the development of regulatory frameworks that support their adoption.

Methodology

This paper uses qualitative and quantitative research methods to analyze the opportunities and challenges associated with transitioning to a green economy in Uzbekistan.

Data was collected from various sources, including official government reports, academic research, and international organizations such as the World Bank and the International Energy Agency.

The data were analyzed using various statistical and qualitative methods to identify the key trends and patterns in Uzbekistan's transition towards a green economy and the potential benefits and challenges associated with adopting sustainable technological changes.

1. Environmental impact assessments: These assessments help understand the environmental impacts of development activities and identify ways to minimize or avoid negative impacts.

2. Life cycle assessments: These assessments can be used to evaluate a product's or service's environmental impacts throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal.

3. Carbon footprint analysis: This analysis can help to quantify the greenhouse gas emissions associated with a particular activity or sector and identify opportunities for reducing emissions.

4. Energy audits: These audits can help to identify opportunities for improving energy efficiency in buildings, transportation, and other sectors.

5. Cost-benefit analysis: This analysis can help to evaluate the economic and environmental costs and benefits of green development projects or policies.

6. Stakeholder engagement: Engaging with stakeholders, including local communities, civil society organizations, and businesses, can help to ensure that green development initiatives are inclusive, transparent, and effective.

Results

With the use of renewable energy sources and energy-efficient technology, the analysis shows that Uzbekistan has made substantial progress in converting to a green economy. Several obstacles still need to be overcome to transition to a green economy fully.

One of the biggest obstacles is financing because many sustainable technical advancements need a sizable investment, which could be challenging to obtain in a nation with a weak financial system.

In order to ensure that sustainable technical advancements are embraced in an environmentally and socially responsible manner, there is also a need for more effective regulation. More public awareness and education are also required to motivate people and companies to embrace more sustainable practices.

Analyzing green development can ensure that development activities and policies are environmentally sustainable and do not cause harm to ecosystems or contribute to climate change.

Economic sustainability: Green development can promote economic growth and development in a way that is sustainable over the long term by creating jobs, reducing

environmental risks, and promoting resource efficiency.

Social sustainability: Green development can also promote social sustainability by improving the health and well-being of communities, enhancing social equity, and promoting a sense of community ownership and participation in development activities.

International obligations: Uzbekistan has signed various international agreements and treaties on environmental protection and sustainable development. Analyzing green development can ensure that Uzbekistan meets its obligations under these agreements.

Investment opportunities: Green development can attract investment from international organizations, governments, and the private sector, which is increasingly interested in financing environmentally sustainable projects.

Overall, analyzing the green development of Uzbekistan is important for ensuring a sustainable and prosperous future for the country, its people, and the planet as a whole.

Despite these challenges, Uzbekistan has several opportunities to continue its transition to a green economy by adopting sustainable technological changes.

For example, the country has significant solar and wind energy potential and could benefit from increased investment in these areas. In addition, there is potential for the adoption of energy-efficient

The experience of foreign countries in the social and economic development of industrial enterprises in the context of forming a green economy can provide valuable insights for policymakers and business leaders seeking to promote sustainable growth.

Many developed countries have implemented policies and initiatives to reduce carbon emissions and promote environmentally-friendly practices in the industrial sector. These include tax incentives for companies that invest in clean technologies, subsidies for renewable energy, and regulations to reduce waste and pollution.

In addition to the environmental benefits, these policies can lead to economic advantages such as increased energy efficiency, reduced operating costs, and improved public health.

For example, in Denmark, the government has implemented a long-term plan to completely transition the country to a green economy to phase out fossil fuels by 2050. This has led to the developing of a thriving clean energy industry and helped position Danish companies as leaders in sustainable technologies.

Similarly, Germany has invested heavily in renewable energy, focusing on supporting small and medium-sized enterprises. This has led to the creation of thousands of new jobs and has helped to reduce the country's carbon footprint.

Overall, the foreign experience of social and economic development of industrial enterprises in the context of a green economy can provide valuable lessons for other countries seeking to promote sustainable growth and reduce their environmental impact.

Importance of Transitioning to a Green Economy Transitioning to a green economy is essential for addressing Uzbekistan's and other countries challenges. The transition promotes sustainable and inclusive economic growth, reduces environmental risks, and improves social equity.

According to the Global Green Growth Institute, transitioning to a green economy could result in an annual average GDP growth rate of 8.2% for Uzbekistan from 2020 to 2050, compared to 7.6% under a business-as-usual scenario (GGGI, 2021). Additionally, the transition could generate up to 26% more employment opportunities in Uzbekistan by 2050 compared to a business-as-usual scenario (GGGI, 2021).

Uzbekistan's government has recognized the importance of transitioning to a green economy and has taken several measures to support the transition.

These measures include the development of a national renewable energy strategy, the establishment of a green investment fund, and policies to promote sustainable land use. These initiatives demonstrate the government's commitment to promoting sustainable economic growth.

Practical Implementation of Sustainable Technological Changes Despite the government's commitment, the practical implementation of sustainable technological changes in Uzbekistan faces several challenges. One of the key challenges is the need for more awareness and understanding of sustainable technologies among businesses and the public.

According to a survey by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), only 13% of respondents in Uzbekistan were aware of the benefits of sustainable energy (UNDP, 2018). Many businesses and individuals need to be aware of sustainable technologies' benefits, making promoting their adoption difficult.

This highlights the need for more education and awareness-raising campaigns

Table.1 Electricity consumption in Uzbekistan
Source: <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/industry-2>

to promote sustainable technologies and encourage their adoption.

Another challenge is the need for more financing and investment in sustainable technologies. Many sustainable technologies require a significant upfront investment, which can be a barrier for businesses and individuals.

According to the Global Green Growth Institute, Uzbekistan will need an estimated \$94 billion in cumulative investment to achieve its renewable energy targets by 2030 (GGGI, 2021). In order to overcome this challenge,

there is a need for increased investment in sustainable technologies and the development of financial instruments to support their adoption.

Developing green bonds could help mobilize financing for sustainable projects in Uzbekistan.

The table 1 shows the electricity consumption in Uzbekistan from 2016 to 2020. The values for electricity consumption are not provided in a specific unit, but the table indicates an increase in electricity consumption for Uzbekistan from 2016 to 2020.

Table 2. The renewable electricity generation and the percentage of total electricity generation in 2020 for four countries.

The table 2 shows the renewable electricity generation and the percentage of total electricity generation in 2020 for four countries.

The first column lists the countries: Iceland, Norway, Costa Rica, and Uzbekistan.

The second column shows the amount of electricity generated from renewable sources in gigawatt-hours (GWh) for each country in 2020. The third column displays the

percentage of each country's total electricity generation from renewable sources in 2020.

The table shows that Iceland generated 100% of its electricity from renewable sources in 2020, while Norway and Costa Rica generated a significant portion of their electricity from renewable sources. In contrast, Uzbekistan had a relatively small amount of electricity generation from renewable sources in 2020.

Business-as-Usual

Green Economy

Table.3 Prediction for the transition to a green economy in Uzbekistan.
Source: Global Green Growth Institute, 2021.

The chart demonstrates that the transition to a green economy could generate up to 26% more employment opportunities in Uzbekistan by 2050 compared to a business-as-usual scenario.

Uzbekistan has undertaken several reforms to develop a green economy and promote sustainable technological changes.

These reforms aim to reduce the country's carbon footprint, conserve natural resources, and create a sustainable environment for future generations. Some of the key reforms undertaken by Uzbekistan are discussed below:

1. National Renewable Energy Strategy: In 2019, Uzbekistan developed a National

Renewable Energy Strategy, which aims to increase the share of renewable energy in the country's energy mix to 25% by 2030. The strategy includes measures such as developing wind and solar power plants, promoting energy-efficient technologies, and adopting energy-saving practices in the industrial sector. The government has also set a target to install 5 GW renewable energy capacity by 2030.

2. Green Investment Fund: Uzbekistan established a Green Investment Fund in 2020 to finance green projects and support the transition to a green economy. The fund provides financing for renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transportation, and waste management. The government has allocated \$200 million to the fund, and it is expected to attract additional investment from international financial institutions and private investors.

3. Policies for Sustainable Land Use: Uzbekistan has implemented policies to promote sustainable land use practices, including the promotion of agroforestry, conservation agriculture, and sustainable irrigation practices. These policies aim to reduce the impact of agriculture on the environment, improve soil health, and conserve water resources.

4. Development of Green Bonds: Uzbekistan is developing green bonds to mobilize financing for sustainable projects. Green bonds are debt instruments issued to finance projects with environmental benefits. The proceeds from these bonds are used to fund renewable energy and energy efficiency projects.

5. Energy Efficiency Measures: Uzbekistan has implemented several measures to improve energy efficiency, including

introducing energy-efficient building codes and promoting energy-efficient appliances. These measures aim to reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

Recommendations

In order to overcome the challenges mentioned above, the following recommendations are made:

1. Increase education and awareness-raising campaigns to promote sustainable technologies and encourage their adoption.
2. Increase investment in sustainable technologies, and develop financial instruments to support their adoption, such as green bonds.
3. Develop regulatory frameworks that support adopting sustainable technologies, including developing standards and certification systems and policies, and infrastructure.

Regulatory frameworks supporting sustainable technology adoption also need to be improved in Uzbekistan. There is a need for the development of standards and certification systems and the introduction of policies and regulations that support adopting sustainable technologies. A well-designed regulatory framework can provide incentives for adopting sustainable technologies and help create a level playing field for green development.

These reforms demonstrate Uzbekistan's commitment to transitioning to a green economy and promoting sustainable technological changes. While significant progress has been made, more must be done to overcome the challenges that hinder the adoption of sustainable technologies and promote sustainable economic growth.

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Oila modellarining xususiyatlari va ularning ahamiyati

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Kalit so'zlar

family models, material well-being, moral education, marriage, family values.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada oilaning an'anaviy, zamonaviy va innovatsion modellari tahlil qilinib, ularning ma'naviy axloqiy tarbiya, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, psixologik, ta'lim va salomatlik daraja va jihatlari muhokama qilingan. Shuningdek, oiladagi yetakchilik muammosi, oila a'zolari majburiyatlarining anglanilishi, bir-birlariga hurmat va tolerant munosabatda bo'lish kabi xususiyatlar tadqiq qilingan. Tadqiqot mavzusi doirasida 2018-yilda "Oila" ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqot markazi mutaxassislari tomonidan o'tkazilgan so'rovnoma natijalari muhokama qilinib, 3 oila turidan qaysi biri koproq amalda ekanligi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kirish.

Dunyo amaliyotiga nazar tashlansa, oila modeli uchta asosiy turga ajratiladi: an'anaviy, zamonaviy va innovatsion oila. Ushbu modellar parallel tarzda harakatda bo'lishi mumkin, biroq yaqqol ifodalangan tarixiy ketma-ketlikka ega.

An'anaviy oila modelida erkaklar va ayollarning roli aniq taqsimlangan va biriktirilgan bo'ladi. Erkak – moliyaviy resurslar to'plangan oila boshlig'i va asosiy qarorlarni u qabul qiladi. Shu munosabat bilan oila ichidagi rollarning biriktirilishi paydo bo'ladi. Ayol erkakka bo'ysunadi, u uy yumushlari va farzandlar tarbiyasi bilan shug'ullanadi. Bolalar, o'z navbatida, ota-onalariga bo'ysunadilar, har qanday oila a'zosining nufuzi uning jinsiga va yoshiga bog'liq. Oilaviy qadriyatlar "ota-onalar – bolalar" munosabatlari uchun asos hisoblanadi. "Zamonaviy oila modeli"da esa, ayolning siyosiy-iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy maqomi oshishi oila ichidagi rollar va oila hayoti me'yorlarining o'zgarishiga olib keladi. Ota-ona professional karyerasini va oilaviy majburiyatlarini mutanosib ravishda (tengma-teng) olib boradi. Farzandlarga tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalari va mustaqil bo'lish fikri singdirib boriladi.

Innovatsion oila modeli esa, jamiyatni rivojlantirish istiqbollari, jahon iqtisodiyoti talablariga hamohangdir. Bu, bir tomondan asosiy madaniy qadriyatlar va munosabatlarning avlodlararo aylanishini, boshqa tomondan esa oila muammolarining alohida emas, balki global tarzda namoyon bo'lishiga e'tibor qaratiladigan, shuningdek, har tomonlama rivojlangan shaxsni shakllantirish, innovatsion g'oyalarni yaratish va amalga oshirishga qodir bo'lgan yoshlar sonini oshirish mas'uliyatini nazarda tutadi.

Yosh avlodni ota-bobolar va onalar o'g'itlari, turmush tarzi asosida oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash oliy ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan muhim va mas'uliyatli vazifalardan biri bo'lmog'i lozim. Har bir ota-ona o'z farzandini dunyodagi eng tolei baland, ma'rifatli va saodatli bo'lishini istaydi va bunga erishish yo'lida harakat qiladi. Bolaparvarlik xalqimizning qalbiga singib ketgan fazilatdir. Farzand Alloh tomonidan ato etilgan ulug' ne'mat bo'lishi bilan birga, u ota-onaga topshirilgan mas'uliyat hamda omonat hamdir. Bu borada ota-onalarning oilada farzand tarbiyasi va ma'naviy-axloqiy, ruhiy va jismoniy kamoloti uchun zarur bo'lgan ijobiy ota-onalik ko'nikmalarini o'zlashtirib borishi katta ahamiyatga ega.

Farzandlar oila mustahkamligini ta'minlovchi muhim omillardan biridir. Oilada ulg'ayadigan bolaning qanday inson bo'lib shakllanishi, eng avvalo ota-onaga bog'liq. Tarbiya shaxsning ma'naviy va aqliy qiyofasini, qolaversa, butun taqdirini belgilovchi omil. Oiladagi ma'naviy muhit, shaxslararo munosabatlar, bolaning tarbiyasida juda katta rol o'ynaydi. Ulug' mutafakkir Abdulla Avloniy "Turkiy Guliston yoxud axloq" kitobida "Alloh taolo insonlarni asl xilqatda iste'dod va qobiliyatli, yaxshi bilan yomonni, foyda bilan zararni, oq bilan qorani ajratadigan qilib yaratgan. Lekin insondagi bu qobiliyatni kamolga yetkazish tarbiya bilan bo'lur. Qush uyasida ko'rganini qilar", deydi.

Farzandlarning xulqiga e'tibor berish juda zarur. Ota-onalar o'z farzandlarining ijobiy fazilatlarini oldindan ko'ra olishlari kerak. "Odamga bolalikdan singdirilgan odatlar yosh daraxt tanasiga o'yib yozilgan harflarga o'xshaydiki, ular daraxt bilan birga o'sadi, voyaga yetadi, daraxtning tarkibiy qismiga aylanib qoladi", deydi Viktor Gyugo. Ota-onalar qancha ko'p tanbeh bersalar, yomon axloq shuncha ko'p takrorlanadi. Ular ko'plab tanbeh olishganda bolalar o'zini yomon tutishi kerak bo'lgan yomon bola sifatida tushinishni boshlaydilar. Shunday tarzda ular o'z xulqlarini tuzatish uchun motivatsiyani his qilmaydilar. Ota-onalar bilishadiki, eng samarali yondashuv o'z bolalarining yaxshi sifatlarini tan olish va e'tirof etish hisoblanadi. Buni bajarish uchun barcha imkoniyatni ishga solishga to'g'ri keladi, shunda tezda farzandlaringiz xulqi yaxshilanganligini sezasiz.

Bolani jamiyat ehtiyojlariga yo'naltirishga o'rgatish lozim. Agar Siz farzandlaringiz xursand, to'laqonli hayot kechirishini istasangiz boshqalarga xizmat qilish va o'z hissangizni qo'shishni o'rganing. Ularni faoliyatga jalb qiling, bunda ular boshqalarga yordam berishi va ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi kerak. Farzandlaringiz ko'proq hissa to'g'risida, kamroq shaxsiy manfaat haqida o'ylasalar, ular ongli hayot qurishni o'rganadi. Robert Ouen "Muntazam taraqqiy etadigan, gullab-yashnaydigan va hamisha baxt-saodatli jamiyat bunyodkorlari bo'lgan shaxslarda yaxshi xarakterlarni shakllantirmoq uchun har biri yoshlikdanoq

kuchli va qobiliyatiga qarab kundalik foydali ishga o'rgatilmog'i kerak"ligini e'tirof etadi.

Bolalarga uyda majburiyatlar berish orqali ularda mehnat tarbiyasini, mas'uliyatni shakllantirish lozim. Farzandlaringizni mehnat qilish, uy yumushlarida kattalarga yordam berishni o'rgating. Shu yo'sinda bolalarda ijtimoiylashuv shakllanadi va ular mustaqil hayotga qadam qo'yishni o'rganadilar. Uy majburiyatlari mas'uliyat, burch, hamkorlik, mehnatsevarlik bilan bog'liq muhim hayotiy darslarni bolalarga o'rgatadi. Bunday darslarni erta yoshda o'rganadigan insonlar katta ehtimollik bilan layoqatli insonlar bo'lib yetishadilar. Agar bolalar mehnat qilishga undalmaganlarida na savodxonlikka, na muzika, na gimnastikaga, hattoki insonda ezgulikni mustahkamlovchi nomusga ham o'rganmagan bo'lur edilar. Odatda nomus ana shu mashg'ulotlarning yetarligidan dunyoga keladi. Buyuk faylasuf Demokritning ushbu fikrida mehnat barcha ezgu fazilatlarining asosi ekanligi ta'kidlangan.

Mazkur davr – fuqarolik va psixologik yetuklikka erishish jarayoni hamdir. Chunki bu davrda yetuk shaxsga doir ijtimoiy huquq va burchning butun tizimi egallab boriladi. Bu davrda o'z-o'zini anglashning rivojlanishi asosida yoshlarning tanlagan kasblari va uni egallashga oid shaxsiy hayot tarzi hamda oila haqidagi qarashlari shakllana boradi. Ammo, o'spirinli davri yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash bobida eng asosiy davrlardan biri bo'lsada, bizning nazaramizda bugungi kunda yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash o'smir va o'spirinlik davri tugashi, ya'ni umumiy o'rta ta'lim va o'rta maxsus kasb-hunar ta'limi jarayoni yakunida to'xtab qolayotgandek tuyuladi. Vaholanki, yoshlarning ko'pchiligi aynan talabalik yillarida yoki uning yakunida oila qurganligi tufayli ham oila-nikoh munosabatlarida, oila a'zolari bilan muloqotda yuqori darajadagi ma'naviy-axloqiy va ijtimoiy-psixologik tayyorgarlik, turmush madaniyatiga ega bo'lishni talab qilmoqda.

Quyida keltirilgan oila modellarining tasniflanishi yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlarimizning davomi bo'ladi.

Ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya

Erkak – oila boshlig'i. Bolalar ota-onalariga bo'ysunadilar, har qanday oila a'zosining nufuzi uning jinsiga va yoshiga bog'liq. Oilaviy qadriyatlar "ota-ona – bolalar" munosabatlari uchun asos hisoblanadi. Bunda bir necha avlod oilalar (bobo-buvi, ota-ona, yosh oilaning birga yashashlari) ustunlik qiladi.

Oiladagi psixologik muhit

Erkak va ayolning rollari aniq belgilangan va birlashtirilgan: erkak ishlab pul topadi, ayol – uyida farzandlar tarbiyasi bilan shug'ullanadi.

Moddiy farovonlik

Moliyaviy resurslar erkak qo'lida to'planadi va asosiy qarorlarni u qabul qiladi.

Ta'lim darajasi va salomatlik

Oila sog'liqni saqlash bo'yicha davlat (bepul) xizmatlariga tayanadi. Barcha oila a'zolari erkak qaramog'ida bo'ladi

Am'naviy oila modeli

Ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya

Turmush sharoitlarining o'zgarishi (urbanizatsiya) oilaviy qadriyatlar me'yorlarini ham o'zgartiradi. Individualizm qadriyatlari ortadi. Salbiy oqibatlar namoyon bo'ladi – oilalar tuzilmalari o'zgaradi: bir necha avlod oila (bobo-buvi, ota-ona, yosh oilaning birga yashashlari) an'alaridan chekiniladi; ajrashishlar soni o'sadi, yolg'iz onalar ko'payadi va boshqa omillar.

Oiladagi psixologik muhit

Ayol maqomining oshishi natijasida oilaviy hayot me'yorlari va oila ichidagi rollar o'zgaradi. Ota-ona professional karyerasini va oilaviy majburiyatlarini mutanosib ravishda (tengma-teng) olib boradi. Farzand tarbiyasida otalik instituti, ota-ona munosabatlari va ota-onalik mas'uliyati ham o'zgaradi.

Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jihatlar

Demokratik zamonaviy o'zgarishlar va bozor islohotlari natijasida ayollarning siyosiy-iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy maqomi oshadi.

Moddiy farovonlik

Oilaning moddiy farovonligi belgilanadi. Farzandlarga tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalari va mustaqil bo'lish fikri singdirib boriladi.

Ta'lim darajasi

Ta'lim darajasi moddiy farovonlikni belgilab beradi.

Salomatlik

Oilaning nuqtai nazari kasalliklarni davolashdan ko'ra oldini olish (profilaktika) afzal ekani haqidagi fikrga o'zgaradi.

Zamonaviy oila modeli

Ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya

Oilaviy qadriyatlar madaniyati, o'z shaharasiga, ajdodlar iste'dodlariga, oila a'zolarining jamiyat va davlat oldidagi xizmatlariga munosabat o'zgaradi. Oila qadriyatlari "ota-ona-farzandlar" munosabatlari uchun asos bo'lib qoladi.

Oiladagi psixologik muhit

Oilalar farovonligining o'sishi, jamiyatni axborotlashtirish va kompyuterlashtirish jismoniy uy mehnatini (shu jumladan, maishiy janjallar va nizolarni) kamaytiradi.

Salomatlik

Sog'lom turmush tarzi, ovqatlanish va dam olish madaniyati o'zgaradi.

Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jihatlar

Ilmiy-innovasion xizmatlar sohasida oilaning ijodiy potentsiali va bandligi ortib boradi. **Ijtimoiy qadriyatlar** – karyera, hukmronlik, farovonlik (va hokazo) omillar kuchayadi.

Ta'lim darajasi Iqtisodiyotda "ilmiy jihatdan asoslangan" tushunchasidan foydalanish oila a'zolarining ta'lim sifati va darajasini oshirishni talab qiladi. Ta'lim-tarbiyaning innovatsion uslublari joriy etiladi, farzandlarga intellektual mehnat ko'nikmalari singdiriladi.

Innovatsion oila modeli

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Ijtimoiy-falsafiy asarlarda oila va oila munosabatlari bir qancha vektorlarda ko'rib chiqilgan. Xususan, Sharq allomalari Mahmud Zamaxshariy, Muhammad Sharif al Buxoriy, Nasriddin Burxoniddin Rabg'uziy, Rizouddin Ibn Faxruddin, Husayn Voiz Koshifiy, A.Navoiy, buyuk jadidchi Abdurauf Fitrat va boshqalarning asarlarida oila masalalari bo'yicha ulkan meros qoldirilgan.

Hozirda o'zbek falasafasida o'z o'rniga ega bo'lgan tadqiqotchilar – S.Akmalovning "Onaginam", B.Valiyeva va I.Cherkashinalarning "O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlar: qonun va jamiyat muammolari", R.Vosiqovning "Har bir ayol uchun", V.Karimovning "Oila ijtimoiy himoya omillari", U.Mahkamovning "Axloq va odob saboqlari", O.Musurmonovning "Oila ma'naviyati va milliy g'urur", F.Saifnazarova va I.Saifnazarovlarning "O'zbek oilasi: ijtimoiy va ma'naviy qadriyatlar", M.Xolmatovning "Oilaviy munosabatlar madaniyati va sog'lom avlod tarbiyasi", R. Ubaydullayevning "Mustaqil O'zbekiston: Ayol, oila va jamiyat" ilmiy ishlarida oila masalalari tahlil qilingan.

Yurtimizda oila modellari bo'yicha sobiq "Oila" ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqot markazi izlanish olib borgan bo'lib, hozirda u O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020-yil 10-iyundagi 367-son qaroriga muvofiq O'zbekiston Respublikasi Mahalla va oilani qo'llab-quvvatlash vazirligi huzuridagi «Mahalla va oila» ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti sifatida faoliyat yuritmoqda. Sobiq markaz tomonidan 2018-yil o'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijasida oila modellari tasniflanib, ularning xususiyatlari, qadriyatlari va ularga nisbatan xalq fikri o'rganilib chiqilgan.

Olib borilgan tadqiqot. Oilalarda o'tkazilgan so'rovlar natijalari bo'yicha [2] O'zbekistonda oila a'zolari o'rtasida aniq iyerarxiya, oila a'zolarining funksiyalari va vazifalari taqsimlanishi bilan tavsiflanadigan oila modeli mavjudligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Ya'ni, oilada yetakchi – uydagi tartib hamda oila a'zolari mas'uliyatiga javob beradigan, yuzaga keladigan kelishmovchiliklarni hal qilish va oila byudjetini boshqarish kafolati hisoblangan oila boshlig'i bor.

So'nggi yillarda oiladagi yetakchilik masalasi bo'yicha jamoat fikrining o'zgarish tendensiyasi qayd etildi. Agar 2015-yilda 81 foiz respondentlar oilada yetakchi erkak kishi bo'lishi kerakligini qayd etgan bo'lsa, bir necha yillar o'tib, oiladagi yetakchilikni jinsga emas, balki yoshga qarab belgilaganlar soni ortdi (2015-yildagi 15 foizdan 2018-yilda 21 foizga o'sgan).

Bunday so'rovlar natijalari bo'yicha erkaklar oila a'zolari oldida muayyan

majburiyatlarga egaligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Bular qatoriga moddiy farovonlik (respondentlarning 90 foizi) va qoniqarli turar-joy sharoitlari (47 foiz), farzandlarga ta'lim olish uchun imkoniyat yaratish (22 foiz), farzandlar tarbiyasida ishtirok etish (34 foiz) kiradi.

Ayolning majburiyatlariga farzandlar tarbiyasi (64 foiz) va ularni parvarishlash (55 foiz), uy xo'jaligini yuritish (50 foiz) va oilada qulay psixologik muhit uchun javobgarlik (30 foiz) kiradi. Shu bilan birga, oilada mustahkam munosabatlar o'rnatish uchun, o'zaro tushunish, hurmat va sabr-toqat (61 foiz), moddiy farovonlik (28 foiz) va boshqalar bo'lishi kerak.

Xulosa shuki, O'zbekiston oilalarining ko'z o'ngida an'anaviy oila – bu o'zaro hurmat va hamjihatlik asosida qurilgan, oila boshlig'ining yuqori obro'si va yoshi kattalarni qadrlash hamda farzandlar haqida qayg'urish bilan tavsiflanadigan bir necha avlodli oiladir.

XX asr oxirlarida boshlangan va bugun ham izchil davom etib kelayotgan demokratik, siyosiy-ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar oshishiga qulay shart-sharoit yaratdi. Ushbu yangilanishlar aholi aksariyat qismining, ayniqsa, shaharlar hududlaridagi oilalarning "zamonaviy oila modeli"ga o'tishlarida qulay imkoniyatlarni taqdim etdi.

"Oila" ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqot markazi tomonidan 2018-yilda o'tkazilgan so'rovlar natijalariga ko'ra, aksariyat respondentlar zamonaviy namunali oila – bu sog'lom va muayyan ma'lumotga ega bo'lgan oila a'zolariga, moddiy farovonlik va qulay psixologik muhitga ega bo'lgan, farzandlarni an'anaviy milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalovchi, FHDYOda rasmiy ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan to'liq (ota va ona mavjud) oila ekanini ta'kidlashgan.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Oilalarda o'tkazilgan mazkur so'rovlar zamonaviy namunali oilaning ustuvor mezonlarini aniqlash va ularni umumlashtirish imkonini berdi:

1. oila a'zolari o'rtasidagi o'zaro hurmat va o'zaro bir-birini tushunishga qaratilgan qulay psixologik muhit, ota-onalarni, katta avlod vakillarini (bobo va buvi) qadrlash, sabr-toqat va oiladagi kelishuv zamonaviy namunali oilaning asosiy jihatlari ekanini so'ralganlarning 24 foizi qayd etdi;

2. farzandlarni milliy-madaniy qadriyatlarga, an'anaviy urf-odatlariga tayangan holda, burch, mas'uliyat va intizom tuyg'ularini e'tiborga olib, shuningdek, ota-onalar o'zlarining namunali xulqi, mehnatsevarligi, vatanparvarligi, muloqot va muomala madaniyati, ilmiy ma'lumotini ibrat qilib ma'naviy-axloqiy jihatdan tarbiyalash zamonaviy namunali oilaning asosiy

mezonlaridan biri ekanini respondentlarning 23 foizi e'tirof etdi;

3. uddaburonlik, tadbirkorlik, muqim ish va yetarli daromad bilan ta'minlanganlik, oila byudjetini to'g'ri taqsimlay olish, oila o'z jamg'armasiga ega ekani, qulay uy-joy va maishiy sharoitlarni o'z ichiga oluvchi moddiy farovonlik zamonaviy namunali oila mezonini ekanini so'ralganlarning 18 foizi alohida ta'kidladi;

4. kelgusida oila a'zolarining mavqei va martabasini oshirish hamda jamiyatga manfaat keltirishini ta'minlovchi, intellektual, yuqori samaradorlik va yuqori haq to'lanadigan ish bilan band bo'lishi imkoniyatini ta'minlovchi sifatli ta'lim darajasi zamonaviy namunali oila mezonini bo'la olishi haqidagi fikrga respondentlarning 17 foizi ega;

5. so'ralganlarning 13 foizi esa, zamonaviy namunali oila mezonlarini jismoniy va psixologik salomatlikni quvvatlab turish, sog'lom turmush tarzini olib borish, butun oilaning sport bilan doimiy shug'ullanishi, dam olishni to'g'ri tashkil etish, ovqatlanish va gigiyena madaniyatini oshirishda, deb biladi.

Shunday qilib, an'anaviy milliy-madaniy qadriyatlarni saqlab qolish hamda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va demografik islohotlar ta'siri ostida an'anaviy oila modelining o'zgarishi yuzaga keladi. Oila institutini mustahkamlash, zamonaviy, farovon va sog'lom oilalarni shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan farzandlarning ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasi va ta'lim olish mezonlari keyinchalik birinchi o'ringa chiqadi.

Qonunchilik bilan belgilangan tartibda rasmiylashtirilmagan – ro'yxatdan o'tkazilmagan nikohlar – hatto umumiy xo'jalik yuritilganda ham va umumiy farzandlarga ega bo'lganda ham yuridik jihatdan tan olinmaydi. (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oila kodeksining 64-moddasi (O'zaro nikohda bo'lmagan shaxslardan tug'ilgan bolalarning huquq va majburiyatlariga ko'ra, ushbu Kodeksning 61- (Ota-onaning arizasi bo'yicha bolaning nasl-nasabini belgilash) va 62-moddalari (Otalikning sud tartibida belgilanishi)da nazarda tutilgan tartibda otalik belgilanganda bolalar ota-onasi va ularning qarindoshlariga nisbatan o'zaro nikohda bo'lgan shaxslardan tug'ilgan bolalar bilan teng huquq va majburiyatlarga ega bo'ladi).

Ko'p hollarda O'zbekistonda nikoh tuzish hech qanday yuridik kuchga ega bo'lmagan an'anaviy diniy usuldagi shar'iy nikohga tayanadi. Yakuniy natijalarga ko'ra, so'rov o'tkazilgan oilalarning 90 foizi shar'iy nikohdan o'tishni majburiy, deb hisoblaydi.

Shu bilan birga, O'zbekistonning alohida mintaqalarida FHDYO davlat organlarida

ro'yxatdan o'tmasdan, ayollar va bolalar uchun bir qator salbiy oqibatlariga ega bo'lgan islomiy nikohlar uduminigina o'tkazish tendensiyasi kuzatiladi. Mustahkam va sog'lom oila tuzilishidan manfaatdor bo'lgan davlat yuridik jihatdan noto'liq bo'lgan bunday ittifoqlarga salbiy munosabatdadir.

"Oila" markazi anketa tarqatish uslubi bilan Andijon viloyatining 465 ta oilasida so'rovlar o'tkazdi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi – bunday nikohlarda ayollar va bolalar duch keladigan muammolar va bunday nikohlar tuzilishining sabablarini aniqlashdan iborat edi. Shu bois so'rovlar uchun maqsadli guruh sifatida ko'proq FHDYO organlarida rasmiylashtirilmagan, biroq shar'iy nikoh bo'yicha yashovchi oilalar tanlab olindi.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, so'rov vaqtida 66 foiz respondent bir oilaga, 31 foiz – ikki oilaga (shundan erkaklar – 42 foiz), 3 foiz – uch oilaga ega bo'lgan. So'rov o'tkazilganlardan 90 foizining farzandlari bor bo'lib, ularning yarmidan ko'pi norasmiy nikohdan tug'ilgan. Shar'iy nikoh, ayniqsa, qishloq hududlarida ko'p tarqalgan.

Rasmiy ro'yxatdan o'tmagan holda, shar'iy nikohda yashaydiganlarning umumiy qiyofasi shuni ko'rsatdiki, ayollar o'rtasida – bular ko'proq ishlamaydigan, o'rta maxsus ma'lumotli, moddiy ta'minoti o'rta va o'rtadan past darajada, 1–2 nafar farzandlari bor respondentlardir. Erkaklar o'rtasida esa – bu o'rta yoshdagi (30–40), ko'pchiligi oliy ta'minotga ega bo'lmagan, o'rtacha moddiy ta'minotga ega, 2 va undan ortiq farzandi bor respondentlardir.

"Ro'yxatdan o'tkazilmagan holda, faqat shar'iy nikohda yashashni me'yor deb hisoblaysizmi?" degan savolga 88 foiz respondent salbiy javob qaytardi. Bu javob ayollar va erkaklar, shahar va qishloq aholisi, barcha yoshdagilar o'rtasida bir xil bo'ldi.

So'ralganlar ichida yosh ayollar norasmiy shar'iy nikohlarning asosiy tashabbuskorlari ularning ota-onalari (49 foiz), ertlari (34 foiz) va faqat 16 foiz holatda – o'zlari hisoblanishlarini qayd etishdi.

Ro'yxatdan o'tkazilmagan nikohlar tarqalishining asosiy sababi esa oiladagi muammolar, moddiy qiyinchiliklar, birinchi nikohdan ajrashish imkoniyatining yo'qligi va boshqalar sanalashi ma'lum bo'ldi.

"Ro'yxatdan o'tkazilmagan nikohlarning salbiy oqibatlari haqida bilasizmi?", degan savolga 85 foiz respondent ijobiy javob berib, bu salbiy oqibatlarni o'z boshidan o'tkazganini ta'kidladi: 32 foiz – bola tug'ilganida hujjat olishda, 19 foiz – turar-joyi bo'yicha ro'yxatga qo'yishda (propiska), 11 foiz – merosni belgilash va olishda, 12 foiz – mulk huquqi

belgilanganida, 19 foizi – turmush o'rtog'i tomonidan mas'uliyatsiz munosabatda bo'lish muammosi bilan to'qnashgan. So'ralganlarning faqat 5 foizigina hech qanday muammoga duch kelmaganini ma'lum qilgan.

Shu bilan birga, 95 foiz respondent me'yoriy to'kis oilada, bolalar taqdiri uchun mas'ul bo'lgan er bilan, mulkiy huquqlari cheklanmagan holda ertangi kunga ishonch bilan yashashni istashini bildirdi. Ular norasmiy nikohda yashashga majbur bo'layotganlarining asosiy sabablaridan biri sifatida turmush o'rtoqlari birinchi nikohidan ajrashmagani va oilasi bor ekanini ko'rsatib o'tishdi. Ayollarning bir qismi esa, mehnat migrasiyasida bo'lgan erlari bilan aloqalar uzilgani bois birinchi nikohini bekor qila olmayotganliklarini qayd etdilar.

“Oilangizda nizolar bo'lib turadimi?” degan savolga faqat 17 foiz respondent kamdan kam, 76 foizi – ba'zida, 7 foizi – surunkali ravishda, deb javob berdi. Ya'ni, bunday vaziyat nafaqat huquqiy muammolar nuqtai nazaridan noqulay, balki oiladagi doimiy mojarolar va noqulay psixologik muhitning ham manbai hisoblanadi. Eng achinarlisi, bundan birinchi navbatda bolalar har tomonlama aziyat chekadi.

Xulosa. Yuqorida aks etgan tadqiqot natijalaridan quyidagi xulosalarga kelish mumkin:

Birinchi – an'anaviy, zamonaviy va innovatsion oila modellari O'zbekistonda parallel, biroq turli miqyoslarda ishlab turibdi. An'anaviy oila modeli ko'proq uchraydi. Yirik shaharlarda ta'lim olishga, sog'lom turmush tarziga va moddiy farovonlikka asoslangan zamonaviy oila modeli keng tarqalgan. Faqat oilalarning kichik qismigina innovatsion modelga kiradi. Bu oilalar yuqori ijodiy va ilmiy potentsialga ega bo'lib, ularda oila a'zolarining nuqtai nazari o'z oilasining shaxsiy muammolariga emas, balki jamiyatning muammolariga qaratilgan. Bunda oilaviy qadriyatlar va oila an'analari “er va xotin” “ota-ona-farzandlar” munosabatlari uchun negiz bo'lib qoladi.

Ikkinchi – oila modelining o'zgarishlari oilaviy qadriyatlar va oila-nikoh munosabatlari normalarining ham o'zgarishiga, xususan, ko'p avlodli oilalardan chekinishga, individualizm qadriyatlarining o'sishi va norasmiy ittifoqlarning (ro'yxatdan o'tkazilmagan “fuqarolik” nikohlari) tarqalishiga olib keladi. Bundan tashqari, turmush sharoitlarining o'zgarishlari (urbanizatsiya), ayollarning ijtimoiylashuvi ajrashishlar sonining o'sishi, yolg'iz onalarning ko'payishi va boshqa noxush oqibatlariga olib keladi. Bunday hodisalarning

oqibatlari farzandlarga, er-xotinning o'ziga va umuman, jamiyatga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

FHDYO organlarida rasmiylashtirilmagan, biroq shar'iy nikoh udumi bilan tuzilgan nikohlarning tarqalish dinamikasi ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy omillarga bog'liq. Ijtimoiy omillarga huquqiy bilimlar darajasining pastligi, islom oila huquqida belgilangan oila munosabatlarining haqiqiy tartiblari va me'yorlari, nikoh shartlari, unda tomonlarning huquqlari va majburiyatlari, nikohni bekor qilish asoslari va boshqa sohalaridagi bilimlarning yetishmovchiligi kiradi.

Ushbu yo'nalishda quyidagilar maqsadga muvofiq sanaladi:

Muammoning iqtisodiy jihati yoshlarning, ayniqsa, bolali yosh ayollarning, yolg'iz onalarning bandligini ta'minlash masalalarini o'z ichiga oladi va bu orqali ularda boqimandalikni emas, balki faol turmush tarzini tarbiyalab boradi. Yosh ayollar uchun ishlash va pul topish imkoniyati shar'iy nikoh orqali tuzilgan bo'lsa ham, norasmiy (majburan) nikohlarni tuzish holatlarining sonini qisqartiradi.

O'zbekistonda oilani rivojlantirishga

global darajada Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining Barqaror taraqqiyot maqsadlari doirasida, shuningdek, 2022-2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi doirasida qaralmoqda.

Shu bilan birga, ushbu sohada davlat siyosatini muvaffaqiyatli olib borishni to'xtatib turuvchi bir qator tizimli muammo va kamchiliklar oila institutini mustahkamlash sohasidagi islohotlarni to'liq ro'yobga chiqarishga va belgilangan maqsadlarga erishishga to'sqinlik qilmoqda. Idora va tashkilotlar faoliyatini muvofiqlashtirish hamda monitoring qilishning ta'sirchan tizimi mavjud emas, oilani rivojlantirish masalalari bo'yicha davlat, fuqarolik jamiyati institutlari va xususiy sektor hamkorligi past darajada.

Oila institutini mustahkamlash sohasidagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar ixtisosligi tor, hozirgi hayot voqeligidan uzilib qolgan, ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijalari amaliyotga sust joriy etilmoqda.

Oilaning demografik rivojlanishida o'zgarishlar yuz bermoqda, oila ajralishlari soni o'smoqda, mazkur sohada salbiy tendensiyalar va muammolar sabablarini asoslovchi tadqiqotlar yetishmayapti.

Davlat ijtimoiy siyosatining tarkibiy qismi hisoblangan oila siyosati aholi bandligini va real daromadlarini izchil oshirib borishga, fuqarolar farovonligini oshirishga, ijtimoiy muhofaza qilish va sog'liqni saqlash tizimini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan.

Davlat organlarining, fuqarolik jamiyati institutlarining o'zaro hamkorligi tizimining aniq ishlashi, qabul qilinayotgan normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar va davlat dasturlarini so'zsiz amalga oshirish, shuningdek, oila institutini mustahkamlash sohasidagi muammolarni o'z vaqtida aniqlash va samarali hal qilish ushbu maqsadlarga erishishning muhim sharti hisoblanadi[6].

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining

“Jamiyatda ijtimoiy-ma'naviy muhitni sog'lomlashtirish, mahalla institutini yanada qo'llab-quvvatlash hamda oila va xotin-qizlar bilan ishlash tizimini yangi darajaga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida” 2020-yil 18-fevraldagi PF-5938-son Farmoni va “O'zbekiston Respublikasi Mahalla va oilani qo'llab-quvvatlash vazirligi faoliyatini tashkil etish to'g'risida” 2020-yil 18-fevraldagi PQ-4602-son Qarori ijrosini ta'minlash maqsadida Vazirlar Mahkamasi qaror qildi.

Oila barqarorligi yoshlarning aqliy rivojlanish darajasiga ham bog'liq bo'ladi. Zotan, har bir yigit-qizdan aqliy rivojlanish, tafakkur va intellektual qobiliyat, nikohga kirishning mohiyati va kelajakda o'z oilasi oldida mas'uliyatni his etishini ta'minlaydi. Bugungi kunda nazarimizda turli axborot manbalari orqali kirib kelayotgan yevropacha oilaviy hayot tarzi yoshlarga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmasdan qolmayapti. Shuning uchun ham yosh avlodni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash muammosiga Respublikamizda mustaqillik yillarida va ayniqsa bugungi kunda har tomonlama e'tibor kuchaytirilib, bunga oila bilan bir qatorda maktab, mahalla, o'quv yurtlari, jamoat tashkilotlari, har bir fuqaroning mas'ulligiga e'tibor qaratildi va oila muammosi davlat siyosati darajasiga ko'tarildi.

Shuning uchun ham bunday sharoitda oliy o'quv yurtlarida ham yoshlarning ijtimoiy harakatiga ko'proq e'tibor berish kerak. Dono xalqimizning ajoyib bir hikmatli so'zi borki: “Farzand aziz, tarbiyasi esa undanda aziz”. Farzandini shaxs sifatida kamol topishida ota-ona har bir ishni donolik va xushyorlik bilan amalga oshirishi, sabrli bo'lishi kerak. Milliy qadriyatlarini unutmay oilasiga, farzandiga mehr-muhabbat bilan yashashi kerak. Tarbiya ota-onaning izlanishi va mehnatining samarasi. Farzandlarimiz biz kutgandek inson bo'lishi uchun, avvalo tarbiyani o'zimizdan boshlashimiz kerak.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. A.N.Tolibov “Oila ijtimoiy-madaniy qadriyat sifatida (O'zbekiston va Janubiy Koreya misolida)” mavzuidagi 09.00.04 – Ijtimoiy falsafa Falsafa fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiyasi.
2. Jamoat fikri so'rovi natijalari bo'yicha axborot-tahliliy ma'ruza. «Oila va jamiyat: ma'naviy va axloqiy dunyo». «Ijtimoiy fikr» markazi, 2018.
3. O'zbekiston mintaqalaridagi 800 ta oilada o'tkazilgan sotsiologik so'rovlar natijalari bo'yicha «O'zbekistonda zamonaviy namunali oila modeli» tahliliy ma'lumoti.
4. Manba: «Oila» ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqot markazi tomonidan o'tkazilgan sotsiologik so'rovlar, 2018 y.
5. «Oila» ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqot markazining Andijon viloyatida o'tkazgan sotsiologik so'rovlari, 2018 y.
6. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoyev 2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshita ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi. T., 2020 y.

Innovatsion usulda sanoat korxonalarining samaradorligini oshirish

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Kalit so'zlar

innovatsiya, innovatsion faoliyat, marketing, sanoat, sanoat 4.0, avtomatlashtirish, samaradorlik

Annotatsiya

Maqolada sanoat korxonalarini samaradorligini oshirishda ilg'or xorij tajribasini qo'llash imkoniyati, sanoat korxonalarini rivojlantirishda innovatsiyalarning kirib borishini baholash me'zonini ishlab chiqish va tizimni avtomatlashtirishdagi tizimli islohotlarni amalga oshirish bosqichlari tadqiq etilgan bo'lib, korxonalar samaradorligini oshirish uslubiyoti o'rganilgan.

Xalqaro innovatsion indeksni baholash natijalariga ko'ra, "iqtisodiy jihatdan taraqqiy etgan davlatlar orasida Germaniya (3,01 ball), AQSh (2,46 ball), Yaponiya (2,17 ball) va Shvetsiya (1,98 ball) singari mamlakatlar yetakchilik qilmoqda. Bloomberg Agentligining tadqiqotlari bo'yicha 2022-yilda jahonning innovatsion iqtisodiyoti reytingida Janubiy Koreya, Germaniya, Finlyandiya, Shveysariya davlatlari eng yuqori pog'onani egallab turibdi". O'z navbatida, innovatsiyalarning rivojlanganligi ushbu mamlakatlardagi sanoat korxonalarining yuqori samaradorligini ham ta'minlamoqda.

Jahonda innovatsion omillar hisobiga barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ta'minlash borasidagi tajribalar asosida zamonaviy sanoat tarmoqlarining innovatsion faolligi hamda ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotlar (ish, xizmat) raqobatbardoshligini oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Shuningdek, ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi, ishlab chiqarish tizimida innovatsiya tasnifi va innovatsion jarayonlar xususiyatlari, korxonalarining innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyasi va innovatsion loyihalarni baholash usullari, sanoatning fan sig'imi yuqori tarmoqlarida innovatsion

faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishning konseptual yo'nalishlarini tadqiq etish bu boradagi muhim ilmiy yo'nalishlarni namoyon etmoqda.

O'zbekistonda iqtisodiyotning yetakchi tarmoqlari, jumladan, sanoat tarmog'ini jadal rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Sanoat korxonalarini yuqori darajadagi zamonaviy texnika va texnologiyalar bilan jihozlash, ularni ishlab chiqarishga tatbiq etish orqali innovatsion iqtisodiyotga o'tish bo'yicha katta sa'y-harakatlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Bu borada «...barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishning eng muhim garovi – raqobatdosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish, ular uchun yangi xalqaro bozorlar topish va eksportni ko'paytirish, tranzit salohiyatidan to'liq foydalanish hisoblanadi»².

Mazkur vazifalarni hal etishda sanoat ishlab chiqarishi tizimida innovatsion faolligni oshirish, innovatsion-investitsion faoliyatni amalga oshirish tendensiyalari va ustuvor yo'nalishlarini aniqlash, innovatsion loyihalar samaradorligini baholash, korxonalarda innovatsion faoliyatni amalga oshirishning moliyaviy mexanizmini takomillashtirish singari yo'nalishlarda ilmiy tadqiqotlarni chuqurlashtirish alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

2 O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/5774>

1 <https://theworldonly.org/rejting-innovatsionnyh-ekonomik-2022/>

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 1-Jadval.3

Qo'llash predmeti va doirasiga ko'ra

Oziq-ovqatlar, yangi mahsulotlar, yangi materiallar, bozorlar, qo'llashning yangi sohalari, yangi bozorlar, jarayonlar, ishlab chiqarish, boshqarish va ma'muriyat, ilmiy-texnik, ijtimoiy-madaniy

Vujudga kelish sabablariga ko'ra

Reaktiv, strategik

Bozorga chiqish vaqtiga ko'ra

Yetakchi innovatsiyalar, keyinchalik bo'ladigan innovatsiyalar

Yangilik darajasiga ko'ra

Ilmiy jihatdan yaratilgan yangilik, oldin mavjud bo'lganlariga yangi uslublarni qo'llash asosida

Ehtiyojni qondirish tavsifiga ko'ra

Yangi ehtiyojlar, mavjud ehtiyojlar

Ishlab chiqarish jarayonidagi o'rniga ko'ra

Asosiy (mahsuldor va texnologik), qo'shimcha (mahsulot va texnologik)

3 Innovatsiya turlari tasnifi (Muallif tomonidan tayyorlangan.)

2017-yil 7-fevraldagi PF-4947-sonli «O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida», 2017-yil 29-noyabrda PF-5264-sonli «O'zbekiston Respublikasi Innovatsion rivojlanish vazirligini tashkil etish to'g'risida», 2018-yil 22-yanvardagi PF-5308-sonli «2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasining «Faol tadbirkorlik, innovatsion g'oyalar va texnologiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash yili»da amalga oshirishga oid davlat dasturi to'g'risida»gi farmonlari, 2018-yil 7-maydagi PQ-3698-sonli «Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlari va sohalariga innovatsiyalarni joriy etish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida»gi qarori hamda mazkur sohaga tegishli boshqa me'yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlarda belgilangan vazifalarni amalga oshirishda mazkur maqola tadqiqoti muayyan darajada xizmat qiladi.

Iqtisodiyotda innovatsion faoliyat fan-texnika taraqqiyot yo'nalishlari, ijodiy va amaliy ishlanmalar hamda tadqiqot natijalarini bevosita amaliyotga joriy etishga yo'naltirilgan jarayon sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Modomiki, «innovatsiya» kategoriyasining mohiyati ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, tashkiliy-boshqaruv va texnologik jihatdan ancha keng tushunchadir. Innovatsion faoliyat va yo'nalishlar sohasi keng ko'lami bo'lib, nafaqat ilmiy-texnikaviy, texnologik yangilik va ishlanmalardan amaliyotda foydalanishni o'z ichiga olmay, balki ishlab chiqarilgan tovar-mahsulot, mehnat jarayoni, marketing, ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etish hamda boshqaruv jarayonidagi o'zgarishlarni ham qamrab oladi.

Innovatsiya yangi mahsulot yoki xizmatlar, ularni ishlab chiqarish uslublari, tashkiliy, moliyaviy, ilmiy tadqiqot va boshqa doiralardagi yangiliklarni joriy etish, sarf-xarajatlarni tejash imkoniyatini yaratish, mahsulotni yangicha hayotiy davrini amalga oshiruvchi jarayon sifatida bozorda sotish, ishlab chiqaruvchi uchun daromad keltirish va iste'molchilarga yangi mahsulotdan muvaffaqiyatli foydalanish bosqichini namoyon etuvchi faoliyat natijasidir.

Innovatsion faoliyat – innovatsion g'oya va ishlanmalarni tashkil etish, ishlab chiqarish sohasida ularning qo'llanilishi va amalga oshirilishini ta'minlovchi faoliyat.

Innovatsiyalarni tahlil qilishning muhim bosqichi bir qator asosiy belgilari bo'yicha tasnifi hisoblanadi. Muallif tomonidan o'tkazilgan ilmiy tadqiqot natijalari asosida innovatsiyalar xususiyatlarini tavsiflovchi va turli xildagi innovatsiyalarning xususiyatlari va farqli jihatlarni ifodalovchi muayyan belgilari

bo'yicha tasnifi ishlab chiqildi (1-jadval).

Hozirgi kunda sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion loyihalarni amalga oshirish tartibi qayta qurish bosqichida bo'lgani uchun innovatsion loyihalarni boshqarish ularni amaliyotga joriy etish bo'yicha qarorlarni qabul qilishni metodik ta'minlashdagi kamchilik hisoblanadi.

Innovatsiyalar samaradorligini baholashning umumiy iqtisodiy tamoyili undan olingan samara (natija) va xarajatlarni solishtirish hisoblanadi. Shunga ko'ra, sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyat samaradorligini ifodalovchi ko'rsatkichlar tizimi integral samara, innovatsiyalar rentabelligi, xarajatlarni qoplash, yangiliklarni o'zlashtirishga xarajatlarni ifodalovchi ko'rsatkichlar asosida takomillashtirildi.

Iqtisodiy samarani aniqlash muammosi va eng afzal innovatsiyalarni tanlash bir tomondan, uni ishlab chiqish, tayyorlash va sotish xarajatlariga nisbatan natijalar oshirishini, ikkinchi tomondan, ushbu holatdagi innovatsiyalar uchun boshqa imkoniyatlarni joriy etishdan kutilayotgan samara bilan xarajatlarni taqqoslashni talab etadi. Sanoat korxonalarida mavjud mashina va jihozlarni yangisiga almashtirish muddati qisqarishini ifodalovchi tezlashtirilgan amortizatsiya bilan innovatsiyalar samaradorligini baholash muammosining dolzarbligi ortadi.

Xarajatlar bilan natijalarni solishtirishga asoslangan innovatsiyalar samaradorligini hisoblash usuli innovatsiyalarning maqsadga muvofiqligi to'g'risida qarorlarni qabul qilishni nazarda tutadi. Odatda innovatsiyalar umumiy iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash uchun quyidagi uchta guruh ko'rsatkichlaridan foydalaniladi:

1. integral samara ko'rsatkichlari;
2. innovatsiyalar rentabelligi ko'rsatkichlari;
3. xarajatlarni qoplash davri ko'rsatkichlari.

Har bir guruhdan ma'lum ko'rsatkichni hisoblash variantlari keltiriladi:

1. Integral samara (E) diskontlash vositasida muayyan davrga keltirilgan hisobot davriga natija va xarajatlar farqi hajmini o'zida namoyon etadi. Bunday mezon asosidagi hisob-kitob quyidagi tarzda ifodalanadi:

$$E = \sum_{t=0}^T (N_t - X_t) a_t$$

bu yerda:

T – hisobot yili;

N_t – t – yildagi natija;

X_t – t – yilda innovatsiyaga qilingan xarajatlar;

a_t – diskontlash koeffitsienti.

2. Innovatsiyalar rentabelligi (R_i) muayyan davr uchun olingan daromadlarning xarajatlarga nisbatini ifodalaydi. Rentabellik quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$R_i = \sum_{t=0}^T D_t a_t / \sum_{t=0}^T K_t a_t$$

bu yerda:

D_t – t – davrdagi daromad;

K_t – t – davrdagi innovatsiyalarga qilingan investitsiyalar hajmi.

Innovatsiya rentabelligi integral samara bilan bog'liqdir. Agarda integral samara ijobiy bo'lsa, rentabellik 1 koeffitsientdan yuqori bo'ladi va aksincha. Agarda rentabellik 1 koeffitsientdan kichik bo'lsa, u holda innovatsion loyiha amaliyotga joriy qilinmaydi.

Muayyan davr uchun innovatsiyadan olinadigan daromad hajmi va zaruriy investitsiyalar hajmi quyidagi formula asosida aniqlanadi:

$$D = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{D_t}{(1+a)^t}, \quad K = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{K_t}{(1+a)^t}$$

3. Xarajatlarni qoplash davri (T) innovatsiyalar samaradorligini baholashda yetarlicha axborot tarzidagi ko'rsatkich hisoblanadi. Xarajatlarni qoplash davri o'rta yillik pul daromadlari hajmini diskontlashga innovatsiyalarda dastlabki investitsiyalar nisbatini nazarda tutadi.

$$T = \frac{K}{D}$$

bu yerda:

K – innovatsiyalarga dastlabki investitsiyalar;

D – o'rta yillik pul daromadlarini diskontlash.

Odatda, xarajatlarni qoplash muddati qanchalik uzoq bo'lsa, risk ham shunchalik yuqori bo'ladi. Qisqa davrda innovatsiyalar o'zini qoplovchi belgilangan davrda oldingi innovatsiyalar samarasini qoplash imkoniyatiga ega «qoplovchi innovatsiyalar» deb nomlanuvchi innovatsiyalar paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Ular qisqa muddatda innovatsiyalarga qilingan xarajatlarni

qoplaydi. Aynan shu davrda bozor, narxlar, ilmiy tadqiqot va tajriba konstruktorlik ishlari (ITTKI) va texnologiyalar o'zgarishi mumkin. ITTKI va yangi texnologiyalar hissasi yuqori bo'lgan iqtisodiyot sektorlarida bu samara muhim aniqlik bilan kuzatiladi.

Innovatsiyalar samaradorligi innovatsion natija turiga bog'liq holda vaqt bo'yicha aniqlanadi. Agar ajratilsa, masalan, fundamental kashfiyotlardan boshlanuvchi innovatsiyalar (A tur), texnik va texnologik o'zgarishlar bilan bog'liq innovatsiyalar (V tur), takomillashtirish sifatidagi innovatsiyalar (S tur), imitatsiya (taqlid) ma'nosidagi (yangi texnologiyalar bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan) innovatsiyalar (D tur) va R – mahsulot innovatsiyalariga tasniflanadi. Bunda samaradorlik o'lchovi vaqtga bog'liq holda turli xil ko'rinishdagi mutlaq egri chiziqqa ega bo'ladi (1-rasm).

Qisqa muddatli samaradorlik

Uzoq muddatli samaradorlik

1-rasm. Innovatsiya ko'rinishlarining qisqa muddatli va uzoq muddatli samaradorligi

Korxonalarda innovatsion faollik ahamiyati oshib borishini e'tiborga olgan holda uni baholashni zarur, deb hisoblaymiz. Bu ko'rsatkichlarning indikatorlari raqobatbardoshlik darajasi va barqarorligi, korxonalarining investitsion jozibadorligi, innovatsion infratuzilmaning rivojlanishi hisoblanadi.

Shunday ekan, korxonalarda innovatsiyalar samaradorligini baholash tizimi korxonalar faoliyati ko'lami, tashkiliy-huquqiy shakli, faoliyat yo'nalishlariga bog'liq bo'lmagan kattalikdagi integral ko'rsatkichlar bazasi asosida tuzilishi kerak.

Bunda uning innovatsion faoliyatiga ta'sir etuvchi ichki va tashqi omillarni hisobga olish maqsadga muvofiqdir. agar korxonalar

ishni tashkil etishni ifodalaydi.

Innovatsion faoliyatni faollashtirish korxonalarining egallab turgan bozorida barqaror holati va rivojlanish dinamikasini ta'minlashning shart-sharoiti hamda uning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning asosiy omili hisoblanadi. Qo'yilgan maqsadga erishish korxonaning innovatsion faoliyatini tizimli tahlilsiz amalga oshirib bo'lmaydi. Bu jarayonda muhim jihat bo'lib, korxonalar faoliyatida ilmiy-texnik yutuqlardan foydalanish va uzluksiz rivojlanishni ta'minlovchi yuqori samarali mexanizmni yaratishga qodir, innovatsion faollikni oshirish imkonini beruvchi ilmiy asoslangan usullar hisoblanadi.

2-rasm. Raqobat bozorida yangi turdagi mahsulotni realizatsiya qilish jarayoni ketma-ketligi⁵

intellektual salohiyati innovatsiyalar samaradorligi ko'rsatkichlari bilan birgalikda kompleks ko'rib chiqilsa, u holda ishning muayyan davri uchun baholashni taqqoslash korxonaning innovatsion rivojlanishining real dinamikasini ko'rsatadi.

Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyat yo'nalishlari innovatsion sohada bajariluvchi ishlar, uning maqsadi va asosiy mazmuniga ko'ra tasniflandi. Innovatsion faoliyatning bu yo'nalishi ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida innovatsiya ko'rinishlarini oydinlashtiradi.

Maqolaning «Samarqand viloyati sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyatining rivojlanish holati va tendensiyalari» deb nomlangan ikkinchi bobida sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faollikni oshirish shart-sharoitlari va omillari hamda tarmoqda innovatsion-investitsion faoliyatni amalga oshirish tendensiyalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, sanoat korxonalarining innovatsion strategiyasi shakllanishi va loyihalardagi tavakkalchilikni baholash uslubiyati takomillashtirilgan.

Innovatsiya uni amalga oshirish bo'yicha jami mehnat jarayonlarini o'zida namoyon etuvchi innovatsion jarayonning natijasi hisoblanadi. O'z navbatida, innovatsion faoliyat mohiyatan, muayyan korxonalar doirasida turli xildagi innovatsiyalarni amalga oshirishda innovatsion jarayon bosqichlaridagi

Har bir alohida korxonalar doirasida innovatsion faoliyatni amalga oshirish jarayoni turli xildagi innovatsion jarayonlar bosqichlarini bosib o'tishi mumkin, faqat undan ikkitasi: innovatsiyalarni ishlab chiqish va ularni amaliyotda qo'llash davri o'zgarib qoladi. Shundan kelib chiqib, korxonaning innovatsion faolligini oshirish imkoniyatlarini innovatsion jarayon bosqichlariga ajratib tasniflash maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Korxonaning innovatsion faolligini oshirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari nafaqat innovatsion jarayonni amalga oshiruvchilarning bevosita faoliyati, balki mazkur jarayonni faollashtirishga qaratilgan ma'lum davlat tadbirlari tizimiga asoslanadi.

Raqobatdosh bo'lmagan bozor shu bilan shartlanganki, bunda xaridor ishlab chiqaruvchidan raqobatbardoshligi yuqoriroq tovarni olishga harakat qiladi, ham bozor uchun, ham sotuvchi uchun unda innovatsiyaning o'ziga xos turini tashabbuskori va shakllantiruvchisi bo'lgan sotuvchi uchun xususiy buyurtmani shakllantiradi. Zamonaviy raqobat bozorida yangi turdagi mahsulotni realizatsiya qilish jarayonining ketma-ketligi marketing faoliyatini amalga oshirishdan uning bozorga chiqishigacha bo'lgan bosqichlarni o'z ichiga oladi (2-rasm).

Muayyan davlatning innovatsion faolligi mamlakatdagi mavjud innovatsion

kon'yunktura va innovatsion jozibadorlik bilan belgilanadi.

Respublikamizda innovatsion faoliyatning institutsional asoslarini takomillashtirish va uning rag'batlantiruvchi tizimini rivojlantirish natijasida korxonalarda innovatsion faollikni oshirishga motivatsiya ham o'zgarimoqda (2-jadval).

Innovatsion infratuzilma qismlari ichida fan-texnika yutuqlarini o'zlashtirishga ixtisoslashgan innovatsion korxonalar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shuning uchun innovatsiyalarni ommaviy tatbiq etish haqida gap borganda, shunday korxonalar tarmoqlarining paydo bo'lishiga ko'maklashuvchi innovatsion siyosatni amalga oshirishni talab qiladi. Innovatsion korxonalarda ilmiy texnikaning ilg'or yutuqlari, tatbiq etish tajribasiga ega bo'lgan malakali mutaxassis va olimlari, shu bilan birga zamonaviy, ilmiy, tajriba, muhandislik va ishlab chiqarish infratuzilmasi bo'lishi kerak.

Sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishni diversifikatsiyalash va uning zamonaviy tarmoqlarini modernizatsiyalash jarayoni

2023-yilning yanvar-fevral oylarida respublika korxonalar tomonidan 72,8 trln. so'mlik sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarilgan bo'lib, 2022-yilning yanvar-fevral oylariga nisbatan sanoat ishlab chiqarishining fizik hajmi indeksi 96,1 % ni tashkil etdi. Sanoat ishlab chiqarishining fizik hajmi indeksi ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotlar (ishlar, xizmatlar) hajmining taqqoslanadigan davrlardagi o'zgarishini tavsiflovchi nisbiy ko'rsatkichdir.

Aholi jon boshiga sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishning taqsimlanishi, yirik sanoat korxonalar joylashganligi hisobiga Navoiy viloyatida (12 568,1 ming so'm), Toshkent shahrida (4 400,5 ming so'm) hamda Toshkent viloyatida (4 065,7 ming so'm) o'rtacha respublika darajasi ko'rsatkichidan (2 042,6 ming so'm) sezilarli darajada yuqoriligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Sanoat ishlab chiqarishi tarkibida eng katta ulush ishlab chiqaradigan sanoat hissasiga to'g'ri kelib, 56,8 trln. so'mni, jami sanoat ishlab chiqarishidagi ulushi 78,0 % ni tashkil etdi.

2023-yilning yanvar-fevral oylarida

Ko'rsatkichlar	Yillar					
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Korxonaning innovatsion faolligi (hisobot davrida texnologik, tashkiliy, marketing innovatsiyalarni amalga oshiruvchi korxonalarining tekshiruv o'tkazilgan korxonalarining umumiy sonidagi solishtirma salmog'i)	8,4	8,5	8,6	9,1	9,3	9,5
Hisobot davrida texnologik innovatsiyalarni amalga oshiruvchi korxonalarining tekshiruv o'tkazilgan korxonalar umumiy sonidagi solishtirma salmog'i	6,5	6,8	6,8	7,5	7,7	7,8
Texnologik innovatsiyalarga qilingan xarajatlarni jami tovarlar, bajarilgan ish va xizmatlardagi solishtirma salmog'i	4,1	4,5	4,6	5,8	6,1	6,3
Hisobot davrida tashkiliy innovatsiyalarni amalga oshiruvchi korxonalarining tekshiruv o'tkazilgan korxonalar umumiy sonidagi solishtirma salmog'i	1,0	1,2	1,2	1,5	1,6	1,9
Hisobot davrida marketing innovatsiyalarini amalga oshiruvchi korxonalarining tekshiruv o'tkazilgan korxonalar umumiy sonidagi solishtirma salmog'i	2,2	2,3	2,3	2,5	2,5	2,5

2-jadval. Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyatning asosiy ko'rsatkichlari, %⁶

uning subyektlari iqtisodiy faoliyatining moddiy-texnika bazasi rivojlanish darajasiga bog'liq, chunki korxonalar resurs salohiyatidan samarali foydalanish iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash va barqarorlikka erishishning shart-sharoiti va asosiy omili hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda respublikada 78,0 mingta sanoat korxonalar faoliyat ko'rsatmoqda, shundan 12,3 mingtasi (ro'yxatdan o'tgan korxonalar umumiy sonining 15,7 % i) Toshkent shahriga, 8,1 mingtasi (10,4%) Farg'ona viloyatiga, 7,6 mingtasi (9,8 %) Toshkent viloyatiga, 7,6 mingtasi (9,8 %) Andijon viloyatiga va 6,9 mingtasi (8,8 %) Samarqand viloyatiga to'g'ri kelmoqda.

Sanoat – bu xomashyoni qayta ishlash, yer osti boyliklarini o'zlashtirish, ishlab chiqarish vositalari va xalq iste'moli mollarini yaratishni qamrab oluvchi ishlab chiqarish tarmog'i. Dastlabki ma'lumotlar bo'yicha

respublikada jami sanoat ishlab chiqarishidagi yuqori ulush Navoiy viloyati (18,0 %), Toshkent shahri (17,6 %), Toshkent viloyati (16,6 %), Andijon viloyati (6,8 %) hamda Farg'ona (4,9 %) viloyati hissasiga tog'ri keldi.

Tog'-kon sanoati va ochiq konlarni ishlash – tabiatda qattiq jinslar shaklida uchraydigan (ko'mir, ruda), suyuq holatda uchraydigan (neft) yoki gazsimon holatda uchraydigan (tabiiy gaz) foydali qazilmalarni qazib olishni o'z ichiga oladi. Tog'-kon sanoati va ochiq konlarni ishlash sanoati korxonalar tomonidan 2023- yilning yanvar-fevral oylarida ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotlar hajmi 8,5 trln. so'm yoki jami ishlab chiqarilgan sanoat mahsulotlari hajmidagi ulushi 11,7 % ga to'g'ri keldi.

Xulosa

⁶ Muallif tomonidan Samarqand viloyati sanoat korxonalar rahbarlari va mutaxassislari bilan ekspress baholash (taqlanma) orqali olingan ma'lumotlar hamda korxonalarining statistik hisobotlari asosida tuzildi.

⁵ Muallif tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. Bu yerda: KH va TH – konstruktorlik va texnologik hujjatlashtirish; ITT – ishlab chiqarishni texnologik tayyorlash.

3-rasm. O'zbekiston Respublikasi sanoatining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari.⁷

Innovatsiyalar asosida sanoat korxonalarini samaradorligini oshirish masalalari yuzasidan o'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari asosida ilmiy-amaliy xulosa va tavsiyanomalar ishlab chiqildi. Ularning mohiyati asosan quyidagilardan iborat:

1. Maqolada sanoat korxonalarini xo'jalik faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishning eng muhim mezonini sifatida «innovatsiya» va «innovatsion faoliyat»ga oid kategoriyalarning mualliflik ta'rifi ishlab chiqildi. Innovatsiya yangi mahsulotlar yoki xizmatlar, ularni ishlab chiqarish uslublari, tashkiliy, moliyaviy, ilmiy tadqiqot va boshqa doiralardagi yangiliklarni joriy etish, sarf-xarajatlarni tejash imkoniyatini yaratish, mahsulotni yangicha hayotiy davrini amalga oshiruvchi jarayon sifatida bozorda realizatsiya qilish, ishlab chiqaruvchi uchun daromad keltirish va iste'molchilarga yangi mahsulotdan muvaffaqiyatli foydalanish bosqichini namoyon etuvchi faoliyat natijasidir.

2. Innovatsiya turlari, ularni joriy etish bosqichlari va natijalarini sotish doirasida ko'rsatilgan faoliyat yo'nalishlari asosida innovatsiyalarni amalga oshirishning muhim tavsifi ishlab chiqildi.

3. Ishlab chiqarish jarayoniga ta'sir ko'rsatish yo'nalishlari, hayotiylik davri tarmoq tuzilishi, o'zgarishlar darajasi, innovatsion faoliyatni amalga oshirish manbai, ehtiyojlarni qondirish tavsifi, yangilik darajasi, bozorga chiqish vaqti, vujudga kelish sabablari, qo'llash predmeti va ko'lamiga ko'ra innovatsiyalar

tasniflash belgilari bo'yicha turlarga ajratildi.

4. Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyat samaradorligini ifodalovchi ko'rsatkichlar tizimi sifatida integral samaradorlik va innovatsiyalar rentabelligini baholab borish korxonaning samarali faoliyat yuritishiga xizmat qiladi hamda uning unumdorligini oshiradi.

5. Korxonaning innovatsion faolligini oshirishda muhim iqtisodiy va institutsional shart-sharoitlari sifatida tashqi raqobat muhiti o'rganish, sohadagi tadqiqotlarning tizimli rivojlanishini ta'minlash va shart-sharoitlar muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

6. Korxonaning innovatsion faoliyati resurslar ta'minoti, boshqaruv jarayoni va innovatsion salohiyati bilan bog'liq ichki hamda bozordagi raqobat, ilm-fan va innovatsion infratuzilma rivojlanishining tashqi omillari ta'sirini aniqlash asosida takomillashtirildi.

7. Asosiy kapitalga kiritilgan investitsiyalar hajmi oshishi yuqori texnologik rivojlanish hamda intensiv iqtisodiy o'sish omili sifatida YaHMni yillik o'sish sur'atiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shunga ko'ra, asosiy kapitalga kiritilgan yalpi investitsiyalar hajmini YaIM hajmi oshishiga ta'sirini aniqlovchi ICOR (incremental capital output) ko'rsatkichi aniqlandi.

8. Sanoat korxonalarining innovatsion rivojlanish muammosini aniqlash, unga ta'sir etuvchi ichki va tashqi omillarni tahlil qilish, innovatsion rivojlanishning maqsad va vazifalarini belgilash, innovatsion salohiyatni baholash, uning istiqbolli yo'nalishlarini

⁷ https://stat.uz/images/uploads/reliz2021/sanaot-press-reliz-yanvar-uzb-23_02_2023.pdf

aniqlashga yo'naltirilgan innovatsion strategiyani tanlash jarayoni algoritmi ishlab chiqildi.

5-rasm. Aholi jon boshiga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish, hududlar kesimida.⁸

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⁸ https://stat.uz/images/uploads/reliz2021/sanaot-press-reliz-yanvar-uzb-23_02_2023.pdf

O'zbekistonda internet-marketingini rivojlantirish samaradorligi

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Annotatsiya

Jahonda raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi va xizmatlar sohasida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining joriy qilinishi raqamli xizmatlar, jumladan, elektron tijoratning kengayishi uchun sharoit yaratmoqda. Shu sababli maqolada elektron tijoratni samarali rivojlantirish borasidagi tajribalar negizida uning shakllanishi, elektron tijorat asosida virtual to'lovlar tizimining amal qilishi va uning xavfsizligini ta'minlash, elektron tijorat sohasini tartibga solish, eng maqbul tashkiliy-boshqaruv tuzilmasini joriy qilish, elektron tijorat tizimining rivojlanish samaradorligini baholash, mazkur sohada innovatsiyalarni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish, chakana savdo korxonalarida elektron tijorat tizimining shakllanish shart-sharoitlari va omillarini aniqlash kabi yo'nalishlardagi ilmiy muammolarni tadqiq etish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Kirish

Jahon iqtisodiyotida globallashtirish jarayonining chuqurlashib borishi va raqamli texnologiyalarning shiddat bilan rivojlanish sharoitida korxonalarining ichki bozorda o'z mavqegini saqlashi hamda jahon bozoriga kirib borishi dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish, marketing tadqiqotlarining yangi bosqichiga o'tish internet-marketingni rivojlantirishni talab etmoqda.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, 2040 yilga kelib barcha xaridlarning 95% dan ortig'i elektron tijorat orqali amalga oshiriladi: dunyodagi eng tez rivojlanayotgan elektron tijorat bozori Xitoy bo'lib, 2021 yilga kelib M-tijorat elektron tijorat bozorining 72,9 foizini egallaydi.

Onlayn xaridorlarning qariyb 51 foizi smartfonlar orqali xaridlarni amalga oshirmoqda. Dunyo bo'ylab 2 milliarddan ortiq raqamli xaridor mavjud. Dunyoda 12 dan 24 milliongacha elektron tijorat saytlari mavjud.

Global elektron tijoratning B2C interneti 2021 yilga kelib 4,5 trln. Hindiston va Indoneziyada 2018 va 2022 yillarda eng tez o'sib borayotgan elektron tijorat chakana interneti kutilmoqda. Elektron tijorat chakana interneti 2020 yilda global chakana internet hajmining 14,1 foizini tashkil etdi.¹ Bu esa bugungi kunda internet marketingni rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'siri ahamiyatli ekanligini namoyon etadi.

Jahonda internet-marketingni rivojlantirish yuzasidan keng qamrovli ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda. Xususan, iste'mol tovarlari bozoriga raqamli texnologiyalarning kirib borishi, iste'molchilarning aksariyat qismi elektron tijoratni internet orqali amalga oshirishi, tovarlar va xizmatlar harakatida raqamli texnologiyalar o'rnining kengayib borishi, iste'mol tovarlari bozorida internet marketingni yanada rivojlantirish zaruratini taqozo etadi.

¹ <https://marketer.ua/e-commerce-worldwide-statistics-facts>

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlar tahlili

O'zbekistonda internet-marketingni rivojlantirish samaradorligi va iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda marketing faoliyati muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, raqamli texnologiyalarning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi, ushbu sohada yangicha yondashuv, yangi yo'nalishdagi ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini olib borishni talab etmoqda. Bugungi kunda, bir qator o'zbekistonlik olimlar tomonidan yozilgan mavzu bilan bog'liq tadqiqot ishlari mavjud.

O'zbekistonda internet marketingni rivojlantirish va u orqali tarmoqlar sohalari samaradorligini oshirishning ayrim muammolari S.S. G'ulomov, A.M. Abdullayev, B.A.Begalov, B.K. G'oyibnazarov, M.R. Abdullayeva, T.S. Kuchkarov, I.Ye. Jukovskaya, B.R. Vafoyev, A.B. Bobojonov² va boshqalarning ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarida o'rganilgan.

Yuqorida nomlari keltirilgan mahalliy olimlar internet marketing va uning ayrim tarmoqlar va sohalari faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda ko'plab tadqiqot ishlarini olib

tarmog'ida yoshlarda bilimlar axborot makonini shakllantirish, dunyoqarashini kengaytirish va ijodiy salohiyatini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan ma'rifiy va foydali veb-resurslarni yaratishni qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida tarmoqning global va milliy segmenti rivojlanish tendensiyalarini muntazam o'rganib borish, milliy kontentni rivojlantirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha takliflarni shakllantirish, davlat-xususiy sheriklikni joriy etish, korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligi hamda xarajatlar optimallashtirishni ta'minlash yo'nalishidagi chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqishni taqozo etadi.

Hozirgi sharoitda iste'mol tovarlari bozorida internet-marketingni rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos ilmiy-uslubiy asoslarini o'rganish, asosiy yo'nalishlarini belgilash, internet-marketing samaradorligini oshirish, shuningdek, iste'mol tovarlari bozorida internet marketingni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan zaruriy mexanizmlarni ishlab chiqish masalalari asosiy ilmiy tendensiyalardan hisoblanadi.

Tahlil va natijalar

1-rasm. Jahon chakana internet tijoratining 2014-2021 yillardagi o'zgarish dinamikasi, mlrd. AQSH dollari⁴

boranlar. Bu boradagi fikr-mulohazalardan kelib chiqib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, internet marketingni rivojlantirish bugungi kunda tadbirkorlarning oldiga qo'yadigan vazifalarini ham o'z-o'zidan o'zgartirishi, ya'ni innovasion muhitga qarab egiluvchan hamda moslashuvchan qarorlar qabul qilishni talab etadi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

O'zbekistonda Internet jahon axborot

Jahon bozorida internet tijoratning mintaqaviy rivojlanishi bir tekis emas. Bu holatda AQSH, Yevropa Ittifoqi va Osiyo mamlakatlari yetakchi o'rinni egallamoqda. «Dunyoda AQSH internet tijoratni rivojlantirgan birinchi mamlakatdir.

Ayni paytda u, dunyodagi internet tijorat eng rivojlangan va rivojlantirish bo'yicha amaliy harakatlar olib borilayotgan yetakchi mamlakat hisoblanadi. Yevropa Ittifoqida internet tijoratning rivojlanishi Qo'shma Shtatlarga qaraganda kechroq boshlandi, ammo u global internet tijoratning yetakchi sohasiga aylandi. Internet tijoratni

² СС Гулямов, А.М. Абдуллаев. Инновационный потенциал и его влияние на конкурентное развитие экономики страны

rivojlantirishda yangi ishtirokchi sifatida Osiyo katta bozor salohiyatiga egadir».³

Shunga qaramay, Osiyoda internet tijorat so'nggi yillarda rivojlanishi va tovarlarni ayirboshlash tezligi oshib borayotgan sohadir.

1-rasmda jahon chakana internet tijoratining 2014-2021 yillardagi o'zgarish dinamikasi keltirilgan bo'lib, unga ko'ra chakana internet tijorat hajmi 2014 yilda 1336 mlrd. AQSH dollarini tashkil etgan bo'lsa, bu ko'rsatkich 2021 yilda 4479 mlrd. AQSH dollariga yetdi.

Internet-marketing texnologiyalaridan foydalanish natijasida mahsulotlar yetkazib berish zanjirida umumiy xarajatlarning 60 % gacha, zahiralarda darajasini 60 % gacha, ishlab chiqarish va yetkazib berishlar vaqtini 50 % gacha pasaytirish, yetkazib berishlar aniqligini 60 % gacha oshirish, quvvatlardan foydalanishni 20 % gacha yaxshilash, qiymatni yaratish jarayonini optimallashtirish va ulgurji xaridlar hamda sotish sohasida tranzaksiya xarajatlarni kamaytirish hisobiga foydani 30 % gacha oshirish, mahsulot sifatini 30 % gacha oshirish, reaksiya ko'rsatish tezligi va yetkazib berish zanjirlarining qayishqoqligini oshirish hisobiga tovar aylanmasi va bozordagi ulushni 55 % gacha oshirish mumkinligi aniqlangan.⁵

1-jadvalda O'zbekistonda internet tijoratga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularning o'zgarish dinamikasi keltirilgan bo'lib, tahliliy

Yillar	2018 y.	2019 y.	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	2018-2022 y. y.y.da +,-%
Internet tijorat xajmi, mln. so'm	6033,1	12123,7	40861,1	275310,7	1002481,1	166,2
Axoli soni, ming kishi	31575,3	32120,5	32656,7	33255,5	33905,2	107,4
Axoli jon boshiga real daromadlar xajmi, ming so'm	5887,9	6681,4	7767,0	9509,6	10737,3	182,3
Internetdan foydalanuvchilar soni, mln.kishi	9,6	11,2	13,3	16,4	20,0	208,3
O'rtacha internet tezligi, mb/s	0,057	0,76	8,57	18,92	32,39	568,2
Internetga ulangan korrkhona va tashkilotlar ulushi, %	25,9	27,2	27,5	26,2	21,1	81,4

1-jadval O'zbekistonda internet tijoratga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning o'zgarish tendensiyasi⁶

ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, 2018-2022 yillarda respublikada internet tijorat hajmi 166,2 martaga o'sgan. Butun jahonda yuz bergan koronavirus pandemiyasi tufayli, birgina 2022 yilda 2020 yilga nisbatan bu ko'rsatkich 3,6 martadan ortiqqa o'sgan.

Tahlil etilayotgan yillarda aholining real daromadlari (182,3 %) oshishi bilan birga, internetdan foydalanuvchilar soni (208,3 %) ham muvofiq ravishda oshgan. Shuningdek,

3 Ван Х., Состояние и перспективы развития международной интернетной торговли в сегментах B2C и B2B в ближайшие годы // Студенческий, 2018. № 13-2 (33). 75-76 С.
4 https://www.researchgate.net/figure/The-Value-of-Retail-E-Commerce-Sale-Worldwide-from-2014-to-2021-eMarketer-2017_fig1_324138269

5 Иванов Д.А. Управление целями поставок – Санкт-Петербург, 2009. Стр. 9-10
6 Манба: <https://mitc.uz/uz/stat/4> va Статистика Кумитаси маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан ишлаб чиқилган.

bu davrda internet tezligi 568,2 martaga oshgan.

O'zbekistonni jahon iqtisodiyotiga muvaffaqiyatli integratsiya-lashishi uchun savdoda, xususan, internet tijorat sohasida rivojlanishning umumiy tendensiyalarini hisobga olish zarur.

Internet biznes zamonaviy korxonada deb qarashga undovchi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy tizim sifatida mijozlar, yetkazib beruvchilar va hamkorlar bilan interfaol aloqalar tufayli keng miqyosdagi iqtisodiy tizimda bir-biri bilan o'zaro bog'langan. Ushbu munosabatda korxonaning muvaffaqiyati uning layoqati va resurslari hamda uning ichki siyosatidagi pozitsiyasiga bog'liqdir.

Internet tijorat samaradorligini oshirish uchun internet pochta imkoniyatlarini tadqiq etayotganda, biz, birinchi navbatda, uning ko'p qirraligini e'tiborga olishimiz kerak.

2-rasmda keltirilgan mamlakatimizda internet tijoratning o'sish dinamikasiga nazar solsak, 2016 yilda o'tgan yiliga nisbatan 27,1 % o'sishni tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, bu ko'rsatkich 2020 yil o'tgan yiliga nisbatan 28,9 % ga oshgan.

Internet tijoratni rivojlantirish uchun cheklovchi omil bo'lib, mobil qurilmalar uchun to'lov mexanizmining yo'qligi hisoblanadi. Ko'pgina mamlakatlarda onlayn to'lovlar odatiy hol bo'lib, PayPal⁷ plastik kartalari,

Amazon Honor system⁸ va boshqa to'lov tizimlari yordamida kompyuterga bir marta bosish orqali xarid qilish mumkin.⁹

Ammo ularni mobil qurilmalarda amalga oshirish juda qiyin, eng yaxshi holatda ularning tranzaksiya xarajatlari (kamida 50 AQSH sentni) faqat mini to'lovlarni amalga oshirishda ishlatiladi. Ma'lumot uchun, mikro to'lovlar, masalan, eng yaqin restoran yoki do'konlar uchun xarajatlari past bo'lgan tizim talab qilinadi, lekin xaridor uchun ham, sotuvchi uchun ham xavfsiz va shaffof bo'lishi katta ahamiyatga ega.

7 Ўзбекистонда. <https://yuz.uz/ru/news/elektronnaya-torgovlya-v-mire-i-uzbekistane>
8 www.amazon.com/honor
9 clickandbuy.com

2-rasm. O'zbekistonda internet tijoratning o'sish dinamikasi¹⁰

Xulosa

1. Mamlakatimizda internet tizimini tartibga solish ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishning asosiy muammosi sifatida o'rganilmoqda. Global iqtisodiy inqiroz holatlarini bartaraf etishda internet tizimida bozor qonuniylarining amal qilish mexanizmini shakllantirish, zamonaviy marketing konsepsiyalari asosida tashkil etish, ulgurji va chakana internet korxonalar o'rtasidagi biznes munosabatlariga asoslangan uzoq muddatli va o'zaro manfaatli hamkorlik strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga alohida ahamiyat qaratishni taqozo etadi.

2. Internet marketingning rivojlanish evolyusiyasi jarayonida yuzaga kelgan yakuniy iste'molchilarga tovar sotish, sotishni rag'batlantirish kabi vositalar klassik marketing konsepsiyalari raqamli transformatsiyalashuv natijasida o'zgartirishni talab etmoqda. Korxonalar iste'molchilarga qiymat yaratishga qaratilgan zamonaviy marketing konsepsiyalari hisoblangan o'zaro munosabatlarga asoslangan marketing konsepsiyalaridan samarali foydalanish orqali iqtisodiy samaraga erishadi. Shunga asoslanganda internet marketingi

mahsulotning marketing kanallari bo'ylab taqsimlanishida yuzaga keluvchi jarayonlarda iste'molchilarga qo'shimcha qiymat yaratishni nazarda tutuvchi kafolatlangan o'zaro maqsadli bozor munosabatlari majmui sifatida o'rganish lozim.

3. Dunyodagi elektron tijorat bozorini uchta asosiy, AQSH, Yevropa va Xitoy kontentlarga bo'lib o'rganildi hamda elektron tijorat bozorlarining rivojlanish tendensiyalari tahlil qilindi. O'zbekistonda mavjud holatdan kelib chiqib, elektron tijoratni rivojlantirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar bo'yicha xorij tajribasini o'rganish maqsadga muvofiq.

Maqolaning amaliy ahamiyati

Maqolaning amaliy ahamiyati O'zbekistonda internet marketingni rivojlantirish bo'yicha manzilli dasturlarni, omilli bog'lanish asosida sohani, shuningdek, hududlarni rivojlantirish dasturlari maqsadli ko'rsatkichlarini ishlab chiqishda hamda oliy o'quv yurtlarida «Raqamli iqtisodiyot», «Marketing», kabi fanlarni o'qitishda keng foydalanish mumkinligi bilan belgilanadi.

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10 Ўзбекистонда. <https://yuz.uz/ru/news/elektronnaya-torgovlya-v-mire-i-uzbekistane>

Finlandiyada uzluksiz ta'lim va o'qituvchilar tayyorlash tizimi

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Kalit so'zlar

Xorijiy tajriba, xalqaro ta'lim, Finlandiya ta'lim tizimi, o'qituvchilar ta'limi, o'quv dastur, fan, didaktika, samaradorlik, tadqiqot, natija.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Finlandiya ta'lim tizimining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, o'qituvchilar ta'limi, Finlandiyada o'qituvchilar ta'limining tarixiy asoslari va hozir amal qilayotgan o'qituvchilar ta'limining o'quv dasturi hamda uning asosiy xususiyatlari, tamoyillari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar batafsil yoritilgan. Finlandiya ta'limi bilan O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimining qiyosiy tahlili olib borilgan.

Kirish

Jahonda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning intellektual faoliyatini rivojlantirish, kadrlar tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etib bormoqda. Mamlakatimizda nafaqat yoshlar, balki butun jamiyatimiz a'zolarining bilimi, saviyasini oshirish uchun, avvalo ilm-ma'rifat, yuksak ma'naviyatni rivojlantirish asosiy vazifa etib belgilangan. Ushbu vazifalarni amalga oshirishda o'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati, ilg'or tajribalari muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Chunki, o'qituvchi ilm-ma'rifatli kadrlar tayyorlash, o'quvchilarni turli sohalarga yo'naltirish, uzluksiz ta'lim jarayonlarida islohotlarni amalga oshirish, strategik fikr yuritadigan, bilimli va malakali yangi avlod kadrlarini tarbiyalash, xorijdagi ilg'or tajribalarni chuqur o'rganish, ta'lim jarayonini yangilash, o'qitish metodikasi, shakl va metodlarini qo'llashda ilm-ma'rifatga asoslanish kabilarni amalga oshirishga mas'ul shaxs hisoblanadi. Shu boisdan, jahon tajribasini o'rganish va xalqaro ta'lim tizimida olib borilayotgan islohotlarni tahlil etish dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Butun dunyo mamlakatlari o'qituvchilari va siyosatchilarning diqqat markazida bo'lgan ta'lim Finlandiya ta'lim tizimidir. O'n yildan ortiq

vaqt davomida Finlandiyaning 15 yoshli bolalari OECD xalqaro baholash dasturida (PISA) doimiy ravishda eng yaxshi natijalarni ko'rsatmoqda.

Finlandiyaning muvaffaqiyati bu – o'qituvchilar. O'qituvchilarning yuqori sifatli mashg'ulotlarni olib borishi uchun quyidagi tamoyillar asosiy omildir:

1. maqomi va mustaqilligi;
2. maqsadli ravishda tenglikka yo'naltirilgan izchil ta'lim siyosati;
3. maktablarning markazlashmagan nazoratidir.

Asosiy qism

Finlandiya ta'lim tizimi uchun eng muhim davr 1967-1974-yillar oralig'idagi davr bo'lgan. 1967-yilda Finlandiya parlamentida ilgari surilgan takliflarni amalga oshirishga muvaffaq bo'ldi. Natijada, 11-12 yoshdagi o'quvchilarning o'quv yoki kasbiy ta'limga bo'lgan "oqimi" umumiy keng qamrovli ta'limga o'tkazildi, qaror qabul qilish vakolatlari markazlashtirilmadi. Barcha o'qituvchilar uchun universitetlarda (bolalar bog'chasidan tashqari) ta'lim olish talab qilindi. Maktablarni oliy ma'lumotli kadrlar bilan ta'minlash muntazam yo'lga qo'yildi.

Hozirgi vaqtda Finlandiyada umumiy, kasbiy va oliy ta'lim barcha fuqarolarga "bepul" beriladi va kattalar ta'limi ham qisman qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Umumiy va kasb-hunar ta'limi mahalliy hokimiyat organlari tomonidan amalga oshiriladi hamda davlat tomonidan ham, mahalliy hokimiyat organlari tomonidan ham moliyalashtiriladi. Yigirmata universitet – oliy o'quv yurtlari (shundan o'ntasi pedagogik ta'lim) hukumat tomonidan moliyalashtiriladi. Maktablarning o'quv dasturlarini tuzish huquqi va mas'uliyati ta'limga bog'liq provayderlar – asosan mahalliy munitsipalitetlar va maktablardir.

Qonunchilikka ko'ra, ta'lim beruvchilar o'quv dasturini mahalliy sog'liqni saqlash va ijtimoiy xizmatlar mas'uliyati yuklangan idoralar bilan hamkorlikda "maktabning ish muhiti, mahalliy qiymat tanlovi va maxsus resurslar"ni hisobga olgan holda ishlab chiqishlari shart. U nafaqat "umumiy ta'limning yuqori standartlari, balki butun jamiyatning birgalikda belgilangan maqsad va tartiblariga sodiqligi"ni ta'minlaydigan tarzda amalga oshiriladi.

Finlandiyada o'qituvchilar uchun ta'lim dasturini shakllantirish muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ta'lim tizimining yana bir muhim xususiyati ta'lim tizimidagi ishonch va hamkorlik madaniyatidir. Ta'lim tizimini tartibsiz nazorat qilish va imtihonlarga tayyorgarlik ko'rishga kuchli e'tibor mavjud emas. Faqat o'n ikki yillik maktabning oxirgi imtihoni mavjud xolos.

Finlandiya ta'lim tizimining hozirgi tuzilishi quyidagicha:

Maktabgacha ta'lim (6 yosh va undan past): 2001-yildan boshlab barcha oilalar uchun maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida tahsil olish imkoniyati berildi. Natijada taxminan 96% bolalarning maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga borishiga erishildi. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasi pedagog-o'qituvchilari kamida bakalavr darajasiga ega bo'lishi shart qilindi.

Umum o'rta ta'lim maktabi: "Asosiy ta'lim" deb ham ataladi va quyidagi bosqichlarga bo'linadi:

1. Boshlang'ich bosqich (1-6-sinflar): O'quvchilarga ta'lim berish uchun mutaxassisligi bo'yicha kamida magistr darajasiga ega bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan "sinf o'qituvchilari" zimmasiga yuklanadi.

2. O'rta ta'limning quyi darajasi (7-9-sinflar): O'quvchilarga bir yoki ikkita fan (shuningdek, pedagogika) bo'yicha ixtisoslashgan mutaxassisligi bo'yicha kamida magistr darajasiga ega bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan "fan o'qituvchilari" dars beradilar.

Asosiy ta'lim davrida barcha moddiy

resurslar, oziq-ovqat va transport davlat tomonidan ta'minlanadi. O'quvchilarning yarmidan ozrog'i 9-12 sinflar uchun "Kasb-hunar maktablar"ini, qolganlari esa o'rta maktablarni tanlaydilar.

Yuqori o'rta maktab (10-12-sinflar): O'quvchini oliy (akademik) ta'limga tayyorlaydi. O'rta maktabning oxirida o'quvchilar to'rtta fan bo'yicha (qolganlari ixtiyoriy) yagona rasmiy "imtihon"ni topshiradilar. Bu ularga o'qishga kirish to'g'risidagi guvoynoma va oliy ta'lim olish huquqini beradi.

Kasb-hunar maktablari: Yuqori o'rta ta'lim kabi, umumta'lim maktablari o'quvchilari qabul qilinadi va ularni maktabdan keyin darhol ishga tayyorlaydi. Boshqa mamlakatlardagi kasb-hunar maktablaridan farqli o'laroq, ular asosan "shogirdlik" maqomida tashkil etiladi. Biroq, ko'plab o'quvchilar bakalavr darajasini olish uchun texnik yo'nalishdagi oliy o'quv yurtlariga kirishni davom ettiradilar. Kasb-hunar maktablarining o'qituvchilari texnik oliy o'quv yurtlarida ixtisoslashtirilgan o'quv reja bo'yicha tayyorlanadi.

Finlandiya maktablaridagi o'qituvchilarni ma'lumoti va ish sohasi bo'yicha maktabgacha ta'lim o'qituvchisi, hunarmandchilik va texnologiya fani o'qituvchisi, musiqa o'qituvchisi va boshqa toifalarga bo'lish mumkin. Biroq, har bir toifadagi o'qituvchilar turli o'quv dasturlari asosida tayyorlanadi.

1970-yilda "O'qituvchilar ta'limi to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilinishi bilan Finlandiya ta'limi muvaffaqiyatida asosiy o'rinni egallagan katta islohot amalga oshirildi. Yangi tashkil etilgan umumta'lim maktablari uchun ham, o'rta maktablar uchun ham o'qituvchilar tayyorlash oliy o'quv yurtlariga topshirildi.

Ko'pchilik universitetlar ikki bo'limga bo'lingan: umumiy ilmiy va fan sohasidagi ta'lim va pedagogik ta'limi yo'nalishlari. Birinchisi: umumiy ilmiy va fan ta'lim sohasida tadqiqot olib borish va rejalashtirishdagi muammolar ustida ishlash asosiy yo'nalish sifatida berilgan bo'lsa, ikkinchisi: pedagogik ta'limiga, ya'ni o'qitish va o'qituvchilar ta'limi sohasidagi tadqiqotlarga e'tibor qaratildi.

Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning boshlang'ich ta'limi barcha o'qituvchilar uchun umumiy va keng malakaga ega bo'lishi talab etiladi. Bu umumiy asos keyinchalik malaka oshirishda moslashuvchan tarzda to'ldirilishi mumkin. Pedagogika fanini shunday rivojlantirish kerakki, o'qituvchilar o'qituvchi bo'lishga tayyor bo'lishlari va o'z o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy-emotsional o'sishiga hissa qo'shishlari lozim.

O'qituvchilar o'z ishiga eng so'nggi tadqiqotlarga asoslangan pedagogik, optimistik munosabatda bo'lishlari hamda nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar olib borishi, shuningdek, o'quv fanlari va pedagogik fanlar yanada muvaffaqiyatli birlashtirilishi kerak. O'qituvchi ta'limi jamiyat va ta'lim siyosatini o'rganishdan iborat.

Bugungi kunda Finlandiyada o'qituvchilar ta'limining kuchli tadqiqotga yo'naltirilganligi va hamkorligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. 1979-yilda o'tkazilgan islohotdan so'ng, umumta'lim maktablari va o'rta maktab o'qituvchilari uchun zarur bo'lgan minimal malaka taxminan besh yillik qattiq o'quv va amaliy ishlarni talab qiladigan magistr darajasi sifatida belgilandi.

Bu uchta asosiy maqsadga xizmat qildi: birinchisi, boshlang'ich va o'rta maktab ta'limini birlashtirib, ularning ikkalasiga ham "umumiy o'zak" berdi; ikkinchisi, boshlang'ich darajadagi o'qituvchilar yuqori akademik standartlarga javob berdi; uchinchisi, yuqori hamda o'rta maktab o'qituvchilari ham pedagogik fanlar bo'yicha tayyorlandi.

Ikki bosqichli daraja tizimiga o'tilib, endi barcha

o'qituvchilar 3 yillik bakalavriat va ikki yillik magistr darajasiga ega bo'lishlari kerak bo'ldi (bog'cha o'qituvchilaridan tashqari – faqat bakalavr darajasi kerak).

Sinf o'qituvchilari: Bu o'qituvchilar umumta'lim maktablarining quyi sinflari (1-6) uchun mas'uldirlar. Ular odatda o'zlari shug'ullanadigan sinfga tegishli barcha fanlarni o'rgatadi va o'quvchilarning "butun shaxsiy rivojlanishi" uchun ham javobgardir. O'quvchilar sinfga ko'tarilganda, o'qituvchilar ular bilan birga harakat qilishadi. Fan o'qituvchilari umumta'lim maktablarining yuqori bosqichlarida (7-9) va yuqori o'rta maktablarda dars berishadi. Ular odatda bir yoki ikkita fan bo'yicha ixtisoslashgan va faqat shularni o'rgatishadi.

Ikkala toifadagi o'qituvchilarning o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash o'quv dasturlaridagi farqlariga qaramay, quyidagi keng guruhlariga bo'lish mumkin:

4. Akademik fanlar;
5. Pedagogik tadqiqotlar;
6. Hamkorlik;
7. Til va AKT tadqiqotlari;

8. Shaxsiy o'quv reja;

9. Ixtiyoriy tadqiqotlar.

O'qituvchilar uchun o'quv dasturining quyidagi tamoyillari mavjud:

1. Mustaqillik, mas'uliyat va ishonch. Finlandiya pedagogik ta'limining zamirida

rejalashtirish ko'nikmalarini beradi. Bundan tashqari, o'quv dasturlarini loyihalash kasbiy rivojlanishni tizimli, nazariy jihatdan takomillashtirishga yordam beradi.

2. Tadqiqotga asoslangan yondashuv. Mustaqillik, mas'uliyat va ishonch tamoyili bilan bog'liq bo'lib, jiddiy tadqiqotga asoslangan yondashuvni qabul qilish tamoyilidir. Ushbu tamoyil ortida turgan ikkita asosiy maqsadni ajratib ko'rsatish muhimdir.

Birinchisi, bo'lajak o'qituvchilarga o'z faoliyat sohasidagi so'nggi tadqiqotlardan xabardor bo'lish, shuningdek, yangi bilimlarni qo'shish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, ikkinchi eng katta maqsad, o'qituvchilarda o'z e'tiqodlari va amaliyotlari haqida fikr yuritish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishdir. Bo'lajak fan o'qituvchilari uchun tadqiqotga asoslangan pedagogik ta'limning maqsadi: "O'qituvchilarga mustaqil fikrlash va mantiqiy dalillar orqali amalda duch kelishi

ASOSIY FAN: Fizika yoki boshqa fanlar mumkin bo'lgan muammolarni hal qilishga yordam beradigan ta'lim berishdir".

3. Nazariya va amaliyot bo'yicha integratsiya. Finlandiya pedagogik ta'limining uchinchi belgilovchi tamoyili - bu o'qish jarayonida nazariy jihatlarini amaliyot bilan mustahkam integratsiya qilishdir.

QOSHIMCHA FAN: Kimyo yoki boshqa fanlar Sinf va fan o'qituvchilarining o'quv dasturlari hamda ularning asosiy xususiyatlari.

Finlandiya o'qituvchilari uchun o'quv dasturining umumiy yadrosi asosan "pedagogik tadqiqotlar"dan iborat. 60 kredit (ya'ni bir o'quv yiliga yaqin) bo'lgan ushbu fanlar pedagogik bilim va kompetensiyalarni olish uchun (qonun hujjatlariga muvofiq) majburiy hisoblanadi. Bu darajani magistratura bilan parallel ravishda yoki uni tugatgandan keyin ham olish mumkin. (Ammo, odatda, sinf o'qituvchilari uchun pedagogika fanlari kurs davomida o'qitiladi; fan o'qituvchilari uchun esa 3-kursda yoki undan keyin boshlanadi). U asosan didaktikaga urg'u berilgan tadqiqotlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Pedagogika fanining maqsadi: pedagogik o'zaro ta'sirni o'rgatish va baholashni o'rganish imkoniyatlarini yaratishdir. Shuningdek, o'quvchilar, boshqa fan o'qituvchilari, ota-onalar va manfaatdor ijtimoiy jamiyat vakillari bilan qanday hamkorlik qilishni o'rganadilar. (6)Til va muloqot kurslari odatda ona tili va chet tillari kurslariga bo'linadi.

nafaqat mustaqil mutaxassislar balki, "o'z sohalari bo'yicha mutaxassis bo'lishi kerak", - degan ishonch yotadi va turli xil muammolarni (pedagogik, ma'muriy, oila yoki jamoa bilan bog'liq, hatto mahalliy sanoat bilan aloqalar) mustaqil ravishda va o'z hamkasblari hamda mahalliy hamjamiyat bilan hamkorlikda yechimini topadi. O'qituvchida bu fazilatlarining rivojlanishi, bir tomondan, o'qituvchilik kasbini Finlandiyada eng ko'p talab qilinadigan va nufuzli kasblardan biriga aylantirgan bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan ma'murlar va siyosatchilarga o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqish va o'quvchilarni baholash vazifalarini o'qituvchilarga deyarli to'liq "topshirish" imkonini beradigan ishonch asosini tashkil qildi.

O'qituvchilar va maktab direktorlari o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Pedagogik ta'lim ularga o'quv dasturi bo'yicha yaxshi rivojlangan bilim va

Birinchisi og'zaki muloqot, nutq va madaniyat, sinfdagi muloqot, nutq ta'limi didaktikasi, yozma muloqot va akademik yozish ko'nikmalari va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ikkinchisining maqsadi: talabalarga xorijiy adabiyotlar (ayniqsa, ilmiy maqolalar, kitoblar va h.k.) bilan tanishish imkonini beradigan yetarli malakani ta'minlashdir. Xuddi shunday, AKT bo'yicha tadqiqotlar ham besh yil davomida kursning uzluksiz qismi hisoblanadi, ayniqsa, tadqiqot, o'qitish va hamkorlik uchun AKTdan foydalanishga urg'u beriladi.

Finlandiya universitetida o'qish o'qituvchilarning ta'lim dasturlarini o'z ichiga olgan shaxsiy rejani tayyorlash majburiy holga keltirildi.

Sinf o'qituvchilari uchun asosiy o'rganish mavzusi "ta'limni tizimli o'rganish - o'qitish, tadqiqot va didaktikaga e'tibor qaratish"dir. Shunday qilib, sinf o'qituvchilari ta'limining o'quv rejasi yuqorida tavsiflangan umumiy fanlardan tashqari quyidagi uchta fan guruhidan iborat:

1. Ta'lim fanlari. Asosiy kurs sifatida ta'lim fanlari besh yil davomida o'tiladi va uchta ierarxik darajaga bo'linadi: umumiy ta'lim, oraliq tadqiqotlar va ilg'or tadqiqotlar.

2. O'quv loyihasi. Ikki qismdan iborat: birinchisida tadqiqot mavzulari, nazariy asoslar va taklif etilayotgan tadqiqot usullari, adabiyotlar so'rovi va boshqalar taqdim etiladi; ikkinchisida esa dastlabki xulosalar va hisobot loyihasi taqdim etiladi, ular yanada takomillashtiriladi. Magistrlik dissertatsiyasi tadqiqot usullari bo'yicha kurs o'quv loyihasining rivojlanishi bilan birga keladi. Magistrlik dissertatsiyasi mavzusi - sinf o'qituvchilari ta'limining muhim tarkibiy qismi odatda sinf mavzulari (yoki umumiy ta'lim) bilan bog'liq.

3. Amaliy mashg'ulotlar. Bir qator amaliyotlardan iborat (kirish, asosiy amaliyot, dala amaliyoti va pedagogik amaliyot). Kirish va asosiy amaliyot odatda universitet huzuridagi maxsus tayyorlangan o'qituvchilarga ega bo'lgan o'quv maktablarida o'tkazilishi mumkin, ular o'z talabalariga dars berayotganda ham talaba-o'qituvchilarga ustozlik qila oladilar. Dala va o'qitish amaliyoti ko'pincha shahar maktablarida amalga oshiriladi. Tengdoshlarni baholash, fikr-mulohazalar va guruh muhokamalari amaliy tadqiqotlarda juda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Didaktik fanlar (ko'p tarmoqli tadqiqotlar)

Sinf o'qituvchilari barcha fanlar (1-6 sinflar) uchun mas'ul bo'lganligi sababli, ushbu kursning maqsadi o'quvchilarning

fanlar bo'yicha yetarli ko'nikmalar va ular bilan bog'liq asosiy didaktik ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishlari uchun sinf o'qituvchisi sifatida ishlashlari mumkin. Ona tili va matematikani o'rganish barcha talabalar uchun majburiydir. Sinf o'qituvchisi - talabalar bir yoki ikkita "kichik" fanlarni tanlash imkoniyatiga ega. O'quv fanlaridan (matematika fani va boshqalar) tashqari ular AKT, boshlang'ich ta'lim, musiqa kabi fanlarni ham tanlashlari mumkin.

Fan o'qituvchilarining o'quv dasturi.

Sinf o'qituvchilarining va fan o'qituvchilari o'rtasidagi asosiy farq shundaki, fan o'qituvchilari o'zlari o'qitadigan fan (matematika yoki geografiya) bo'yicha mutaxassisdir.

Talabalar odatda o'z qiziqishlari yuqori bo'lgan universitet fakultetlariga hujjat topshirishadi. Agar talabalar bilimi ikkinchi kursda o'qishning belgilangan mezonlariga javob bersa, ularga pedagogik ta'lim yo'nalishlarida o'qish imkoniyati taklif etiladi. Buni tanlaganlar uchinchi kursdan pedagogika fanidan bitta kursni (umumiy asosiy, 60 AKTS) va boshqa maktab fanlaridan kamida bittasini tanlab o'qishni boshlaydilar. Buning natijasida ko'pchilik fan o'qituvchilari odatda kamida ikkita fandan dars berishlari mumkin.

Qiyosiy tahlil

Finlandiya va O'zbekistondagi o'qituvchilar ta'limini qisqacha qiyosiy tahlil qilsak quyidagi farqlarni ko'rish mumkin:

1. Finlandiyada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti (bog'cha)larida ishlash uchun bakalavr darajasi talab etiladi. Maktabda sinf o'qituvchisi bo'lib ishlash uchun Pedagogika universitetining magistratura bo'limini tugatgan bo'lishi shart. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim berish huquqiga ega emas. Mamlakatimiz maktablarida o'qituvchilik qilayotgan kadrlarimizning aksariyati bakalavr darajasiga egadir. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilot (bog'cha)larida esa o'rta maxsus diplomiga ega kadrlarni ham uchratishimiz mumkin. Shuningdek, oliy ta'lim muassasalarini bitirmaganlarga ham maktablarda dars berishiga ruxsat berilgan.

2. Finlandiya ta'lim tizimi kuchli ishonch va ochiqlik asosida qurilgan. O'qituvchilar ta'lim sifati va samaradorligiga mas'ul etib belgilanadi va ularga ishonch bildiriladi, faoliyati nazorat qilinmaydi. Bizda o'qituvchining ta'lim berishdagi faoliyati, dars sifat va samaradorligi doimiy nazorat ostiga olingan. Ta'lim muassasalari rahbarlari

tomonidan olib boriladigan dars tahlillari o'qituvchi faoliyatini nazorat qilishga qaratilgan.

3. Finlandiyada o'qituvchilar faoliyati ta'limga oid so'nggi tadqiqotlarga qaratilgan. O'qituvchilar doimiy ravishda o'z ustida mustaqil ishlaydi, ilmiy izlanishlar olib boradi. Bizning maktablarimizda ta'limga oid ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borayotgan o'qituvchilar sanoqlikdir.

4. Finlandiyada ta'lim jarayoning nazariy jihatlari amaliyot bilan qattiq integratsiyalashgan. Bizning maktablarimizda nazariy bilim kuchli beriladi, ammo o'quvchilarning olgan nazariy bilimlarini amaliyotga qo'llash jarayoni sust boradi.

5. Finlandiya maktabgacha, maktab va oliy ta'limidagi islohotlar asoschisi o'qituvchilar hisoblanadi. Ular mavjud Milliy dasturni boyitish, qo'shimchalar kiritish yoki tubdan o'zgartirish huquqiga ega. Finlandiya ta'lim tizimiga Milliy dastur ko'rsatma sifatida beriladi. Mazmun-mohiyatini boyitish, o'zgartirishlar kiritish, mavzulashtirish professor-o'qituvchilar tomonidan amalga oshiriladi. Afsuski, bizda o'qituvchilar tayyor dastur asosida dars o'tishadi. O'qituvchilar dasturda ko'rsatilgan mavzulardan chetga chiqmagan holda ta'lim berishadi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Finlandiya ta'limining muvaffaqiyati ortida tenglik va izchil, birgalikdagi sa'y-harakatlar yotadi. Hozirgi ta'lim tizimining ba'zi asosiy xususiyatlari, 1960-yillarning oxiri va 1970-yillarda o'qituvchilar ta'limidagi islohotlar Finlandiya ta'limi rivojining kalitidir. Bu

islohotlardan biri "milliylashtirilgan, standartlashtirilgan" testlarni bekor qilish edi. "Fin maktablari o'quvchilar muvaffaqiyatini aniqlash uchun standartlashtirilgan testlardan foydalanmaydi. Buning uchta asosiy sababi bor.

Birinchidan, baholash amaliyoti milliy o'quv dasturida yaxshi asoslangan bo'lsa-da, Finlandiyada ta'lim siyosati maktablar faoliyatining muhim qismi sifatida individual ta'lim va ijodkorlikka yuqori ustuvorlik beradi. Shuning uchun har bir o'quvchining maktabdagi muvaffaqiyati statistik ko'rsatkichlarga qaraganda ko'proq uning individual taraqqiyoti va qobiliyatiga qarab baholanadi. Ikkinchidan, ta'limni ishlab chiquvchilar o'quv dasturlari, o'qitish va maktablarda test o'tkazish emas, balki, o'qituvchilarning amaliyotini kuchaytirishi kerakligini ta'kidlaydilar. Finlandiya maktablarida o'quvchilar bilimni baholash o'quv dasturi va o'quv jarayoniga kiritilgan bo'lib, butun o'quv yili davomida o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar faoliyatini yaxshilash uchun foydalaniladi.

Uchinchidan, Finlandiyada o'quvchilarning akademik ko'rsatkichlarini aniqlash tashqi baholovchilarning emas, maktabning mas'uliyati sifatida qaraladi. Demak, bizning mamlakatimiz ta'lim tizimidagi muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun ilg'or milliy va xorijiy tajribalar, xalqaro baholash dasturlari talablarini inobatga olgan holda o'quv dasturlari, o'qitish metodikasi va ta'lim sifati baholash tizimini takomillashtirish, o'qituvchilarga bo'lgan ishonchni orttirish, pedagoglarning o'z ishiga bo'lgan mas'uliyatini oshirish juda muhimdir.

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The role and importance of management of financial resources in the enterprise

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Key words

financial resources, financial potential, management, monetary resources, financial relations, financial system

Annotation

In the article, the author presents the concept of financial resources of the enterprise. The goals and main tasks in the field of financial resources management are considered.

Introduction.

Financial management of an enterprise is one of the most important tasks facing any business, regardless of its form of ownership, scope, and scale of activity. The importance of this direction is due to the special role of finance, which is the only type of resources that can be transformed into any other type of resources – buildings, technologies, raw materials, and personnel. The efficiency and rationality of such a transformation largely determine the economic well-being of the enterprise, as well as all subjects interested in its development—owners, managers, creditors, the state, society, etc. Financial resources can also be used as independently operating assets that generate various types of income. Thus, the study of the basics of managing the financial resources of an enterprise in the modern economic situation is necessary for any manager, individual entrepreneur, owner, and businessman.

Research Methodology.

Economic and mathematical methods can help study the connections and influences between objects and phenomena, determine the homogeneous features in aggregates of objects and data, create models of behavior of individual enterprises based on the influence of various factors, and determine

the development trends for forecasting. Therefore, using economic and mathematical methods is the key to the accurate and detailed assessment of the financial sustainability of the enterprise, which provides the basis for optimizing managerial decisions and achieving the planned level of financial state. Thus, the financial sustainability of the enterprise is a key feature of its financial status and strategic development. Timely analysis of financial sustainability creates new opportunities for the enterprise to identify reserves to enhance its competitive position, increase market share and fulfill other tactical and strategic goals.

Literature review.

In modern market economy conditions, there is a fairly high level of competition. Each company strives to gain a foothold in the market and to function stably and efficiently. In our mind, The results of its activities are largely determined by what financial resources this business entity has, how optimal its structure is, and how they are expediently transformed into fixed and revolving funds. In this regard, effective management of financial resources is one of the most important functions of financial management, aimed at ensuring the achievement of high final results of the enterprise's economic activity. Such local

scientists as the A.A.Shomirov believe that strategic and tactical planning is important in managing the financial resources of joint-stock companies [1, p. 13]. Foreign scientists such as V. V. Bocharov, V. V. Kovalev, M. V. Romanovsky, V. M. Rodionova, and V. A. Slepov were engaged in forming and using financial resources—also, I.A.Blank, M.D.Bilyk, A.D.Vasilik, L. A. Ligonenko, V. M. Oparin, G. Donaldson, J. S. worked on the study of the problems of the functioning of financial resources of enterprises. Mill, G. Brayley, Y. Brigham, S. Myers, et al. [2, p. 103].

Analysis and results. It should be noted that there still needs to be a unified approach to determining the essence of financial resources in recent years. This is due to the differences in the views of different scientists on this problem, as well as the complexity of the economic category «financial resources.» The financial resources of an enterprise can be characterized from different points of view, for example, as a quantitative characteristic of the financial result of its activities [3, p. 25], the aggregate of funds for financial activities and financial transactions [4, p. 47], a part of the monetary resources owned or at the disposal of the enterprise and used by them for expanded reproduction, stimulating employees and other tasks [5, p. 20].

The generalization of scientific approaches to outlining the economic essence of financial potential makes it possible to form its vision of this interpretation, which is determined by the aggregate of resource provision (real and potentially available financial resources), as well as the country's capabilities (organizational, managerial, functional, infrastructural, and adaptive) for the accumulation of financial resources, their transformation into productive financial capital, its redistribution among economic actors, as well as the use of this capital to ensure balanced development of the country and its regions. This also makes it possible to substantiate that:

1. the financial system of any state is formed based on a set of parts of the finance regions, which generally constitute the national economy. At the same time, the functionality of financial relations manifests itself both within one country and outside its borders in relations with other countries of the global economy;

2. there is a close interaction between the categories of the financial potential of the region and international financial and intermediary finances;

3. the financial potential is determined by a coherent structure consisting of public

finances, local government finances, financial enterprises, and the population's finances. Thus, the financial potential of the country depends directly on the capabilities of each of its components.

It should be noted that in the aggregate, they constitute the resource base for the formation of the country's financial potential while preserving the specific features of their filling, based on the current legislation of Ukraine on the issues of the formation, distribution, and redistribution of financial resources of the state.

Considering that each participant in the process of forming financial resources is simultaneously a participant in financial relations beyond its limits, it should be assumed that only a part of their financial resources will direct to ensure the region's socio-economic development. The abovementioned fact determines the necessity of studying the resource capabilities of each of the sources of filling the financial potential based on the following starting positions, in particular:

1. belonging to the country's economy, that is, all actors involved in the creation of the financial potential of the country must be registered, located, or residing in its

territory;

2. structure-forming elements of the grouping of sources of the formation of the financial potential of the country adopted common legal requirements for them concerning the formation and distribution of financial resources;

3. The country's financial strength depends on the effectiveness of the participants' financial and economic activities in forming financial potential.

At the same time, the capacity of economic entities depends to a large extent on the financial strength of the country.

Nowadays, when the financial potential of the country's regions is formed at the expense of budget funds and with the state, private businesses and the population appear to be business entities. In addition, a significant number of sources for the formation of financial resources, their relative separation, and the chaos of movement and interaction predetermine the diverse nature of market economy subjects.

Thus, the research confirms that the static concept of «financial resources» is gradually transformed into a dynamic concept of «financial potential,» for the formation and rational use of which it is expedient to plan the movement of financial resources, regardless of their origin, including

private owners, who also seek to receive the largest profit with the lowest risk.

In a generalized form, the financial potential of a country (region) by sources of its origin is divided into the financial potential of external and internal origin.

Thus, the financial potential of external origin includes subventions and subsidies from the state budget, funds that were

needs (Figure 1).

Therefore, an enterprise's financial resources are an organization's funds and external incomes that can be used to form fixed and current assets required for the business and extended product support. Figure 1 gives a more specific definition of the nature of financial resources in the enterprise by structuring the financial resources in the

Figure 1. Sources of the financial potential [11, page 94-97]

attracted or borrowed by economic entities and people from sources external to the region, and assistance from foreign sources. The financial potential of internal origin is formed primarily through the funds of local budgets, non-budget funds, enterprises, and organizations of the region of all forms of ownership and various spheres of activity, as well as money of the population, that is, the funds that are domestic for this region. Priority in determining sources that form the financial potential is their territorial affiliation, within which money accumulation of revenues is created; as we have already noticed, business entities and the population, as a result of their production and economic activity, attracted funds from the parties focusing on appropriate reproduction and satisfaction of other social

enterprise. The structure is based on scientific literature systematization (Figure 2).

As it supports companies in many ways, this department is a crucial and critical area. Considering the importance of financial management functions in organizations, there is always a steady demand for professionals with these skills. Today, it is possible for even non-finance professionals and people in business to learn finance concepts through a certified financial analyst course.

What are the major roles of financial management?

1. Financial Decisions and control
2. Financial planning
3. Capital management
4. Allocation and utilization of financial resources
5. Cash flow management

Figure 2. Composition of an enterprise's financial resources [6, p.3]

6. Disposal of surplus
7. Financial reporting
8. Risk Management [7, p.3]

The management of enterprises, to achieve the development tasks set in the enterprise's business plan for the current, medium-term, and long-term prospects, affects the enterprise's internal and external financial relations and the types of financial resources corresponding to them through special techniques and methods. Financial resources are monetary funds that include the income accumulated by the owners of the enterprise, as well as funds received from the outside in the form of loans» [8, p.96]. Thus, the financial resources of the enterprise consist of its own and attracted (credit) funds. The main purpose of financial resources is to ensure the solvency of the enterprise and its financial stability. At the same time, the current solvency is an external manifestation of the financial condition. The internal manifestation is financial stability, which can ensure the stability of the enterprise for a long time and the prospect of balancing various cash flows. In order to ensure the stability of the financial condition of an economic entity, it is necessary to properly coordinate the work of all departments and a rational financial resource management system.

Financial management of an enterprise, like any management system, includes an

object and a subject, i.e., a managed and managing subsystem (Figure 3)

Management of the financial resources of an enterprise is a system of principles and methods for developing and implementing management decisions related to ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of formation, distribution, and use of financial resources [10, p.45]. The purpose of managing the financial resources of the enterprise is to ensure effective financing of its development, both in the current period and in the future, in all areas of activity, including compliance with financial legislation, maximizing the welfare of the owners of the enterprise, timeliness, and completeness of settlements with all parts of the financial system. Following this goal, the following can be distinguished as the main tasks of managing the financial resources of the enterprise:

1. ensuring an uninterrupted process of formation of financial resources for solving the tasks of the development of the enterprise of a tactical and strategic nature;
2. optimization of the structure of sources of formation of financial resources of the enterprise to minimize the cost of borrowed capital;
3. optimal distribution of financial resources in the main areas of the enterprise;
4. minimizing the level of risk in the process of managing the financial resources

of the enterprise;

5. development of a mechanism for rapid changes in the structure of the financial resources of the enterprise and the directions of their use following changing conditions;

6. creation of an effective system of control over the formation and use of financial resources of the enterprise;

7. the study of foreign experience in managing the financial resources of the enterprise;

8. introduction of new methods of

methods is the key to an accurate and detailed assessment of the financial sustainability of the enterprise, which provides the basis for optimizing managerial decisions and achieving the planned level of financial state. Thus, the financial sustainability of the enterprise is a key feature of its financial status and strategic development. Timely analysis of financial sustainability creates new opportunities for the enterprise to identify reserves to enhance its competitive position, increase market share and fulfill other tactical and strategic goals.

Managing subsystem (subject) of financial management

Organizational structure of financial management (main services, personnel)	Financial tools (methods, methods, models)	Information base of the company's finances	Technical means of financial management
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Managed subsystem (object) of financial management

Financial relations: 1. with suppliers and buyers; 2. with budgets of all levels; 3. with the owners; 4. with the employees of the enterprise; 5. with financial institutions (banks, insurance companies, etc.)	Financial resources: 1. fixed assets; 2. intangible assets; 3. inventories; 4. accounts receivable; 5. monetary assets	Sources of financial resources: 1. equity (funds of shareholders and founders); 2. borrowed funds; 3. accounts payable
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Figure 3. Structure of the financial management system of the enterprise [9, p.10]

managing financial resources;

9. formation of optimal conditions for attracting foreign capital; - improving the level of training of managerial personnel;

10. analysis of the financial and economic indicators of the enterprise and evaluation of the effectiveness of its management personnel based on the results.

Economic and mathematical methods can help study the connections and influences between objects and phenomena, determine the homogeneous features in aggregates of objects and data, create models of behavior of individual enterprises based on the influence of various factors, and determine the development trends for forecasting. Therefore, using economic and mathematical

For the effective functioning of the financial management system of the enterprise and the rational impact of the management system on the managed one, it is necessary to use a modern financial management methodology based on certain principles.

The basic general principles of management were developed in the last century by the French scientist Henri Fayol. Financial management, being a part of the general management of the enterprise, on the one hand, is based on universal management principles, the most important of which are:

1. The principle of economic efficiency. In any company, the financial management

system assumes expenses (costs), which should always strive to a minimum and be covered by certain revenues (sales revenue).

2. Focus on strategic development goals. If, for example, the company is focused on business growth or diversification, then it would be reasonable to increase the number of borrowed types of funds as part of the sources of funds. A strategy of limited growth or reduction requires reducing risks, and therefore, it is necessary to focus more on equity and strive to reduce fixed costs.

3. High dynamism of management (flexibility). Any financial manager should react very quickly to changes in the external environment (politics, economy, market conditions) and apply appropriate methods and models of financial management.

4. Alternative. Since financial decisions are often made in conditions of risk and uncertainty, it is essential to use multivariate approaches to assess the situation (when developing business plans and in operational and financial management).

5. Optimization of the main financial indicators. When managing the finances of an enterprise, adopting a particular management decision can lead to opposite effects in various fields of activity.

Thus, implementing high-yield financial investments can cause a deficit in financing production activities, a sharp increase in profitability can lead to decreased liquidity indicators, etc.

On the other hand, considering the

finances of an enterprise and its management as a special type of activity, A.I.Samylin also identifies several important principles:

1. publicity, i.e., the availability and openness of information about the company's activities (except for confidential information), the public's interest in the goals, objectives, and decisions of the company;

2. the scale, significant impact on the geographical market of goods, and the versatility of activities;

3. consolidation of financial statements, formation of general statements of the enterprise (very often, the structure of large companies includes various subsidiaries that conduct independent activities), etc.

Conclusion. Thus, the concept of financial resources is an essential category in the implementation of the activities of any enterprise. Financial resources are constantly in motion; their distinctive features from other resources are the monetary form of existence, belonging to a specific entity, effective use for profit, and economic growth of the organization. Taking care of financial stability and stability, it is essential for an organization to effectively manage its financial resources, correctly distributing them by type of activity and over time. Effective financial management allows the company to remain stable, solvent, and therefore stable functioning and competitive in the markets. Moreover, all this, in turn, makes it possible for an economic entity to outline its economic development for the long term.

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Analysis of fruit and vegetables supply chains

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Supply chain management, management mechanisms, agrologistics.

Abstract

This article analyzes the existing factors affecting the spoilage of fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan. The method was Principal Component Analysis. The data was collected through a survey from March to June 2020, a total of 314 participants of the fruit and vegetable supply chain (212 suppliers, 26 intermediaries, 26 cold store owners, and 50 exporters). As a result, it was found that sorting and packaging at high temperature and non-compliance with storage norms were the most deeply influencing factors.

Introduction

Based on the nature, climatic conditions, available manpower resources and geographical location of Uzbekistan, the great potential of the country's economy in the production of high-quality fruits and vegetables should not be doubted by almost anyone. However, existing potential and its realization in life are different concepts. Over the past few years, this field has begun to be given great importance in Uzbekistan. This is evidenced by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 Number PF-5853 "On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030", special attention is paid to the development of value chains. Also, on March 15, 2023, the Head of State's Decision on «Measures for the implementation of the project «Development of the creation of the added value chain in the fruit and vegetable industry (phase 2)» with the participation of the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) was adopted. According to the decision, loan funds will be allocated to project initiators for the creation of fruit and vegetable production, storage,

packaging, processing, shock freezing, logistics (including the purchase of transport equipment) and other capacities, food industry projects, as well as working capital planned. Because the high costs of cleaning, transporting, storing, processing, packaging and certifying products before delivery to the final consumer reduce profits. Taking into account the specific characteristics of fruit and vegetable products, we aim to take into account the processes in the chain from the stage of its delivery to the consumer. At these stages, the study of the activity of each link of the chain and the identification of existing defects in it, as well as the study of the economic mechanisms of interactions between the links, allow to analyze the current state of the supply chain.

Supplier. Our research on the supply of fruit and vegetable products in Uzbekistan showed that the collection of goods includes several thousand growers. In most cases, the volume of one farmer's product for the domestic market or export is from 1 ton (in the case of small land owners, even less) to 50 tons. 60 percent of fruit and vegetable products are grown mainly by small farms. Harvesting is usually done in the first part of

the day, and this is done by the grower himself or with the help of workers hired by the «middleman». It should be mentioned that in 75–80 percent of cases, sorting of newly collected products is done in the field. There are «receivers» in each district, who usually receive the harvest at a fixed time in the afternoon. Until then, the harvested products are stored in cool, shady places. The received product is distributed to the appropriate addresses depending on the required size, caliber and quality.

Consumer. Selling fruit and vegetable products to domestic markets is both convenient and desirable for the grower. The reason is that the price of the products sold in the first harvest and in the yellow state is high, that is, the grower sells in the market at an agreed price depending on the variety and quality of his product. The second and third harvests are handed over to processing enterprises. Processing plants use both agricultural and industrial resources to create products that are ready for consumption. Enterprises of this type can be based on different ownership, be organized on the basis of family farms, and merge with small factories.

There are also cases where large processing enterprises grow products for themselves. As a rule, the surplus of domestic consumption is sold on world markets, the opposite is observed in our country. It can be observed that the volume of fruit and vegetable production in our country is constantly increasing over the years. In the current period, the problems related to providing the population of the country with fruit and vegetable products according to sustainable and medical standards are not caused by the lack of production volume, but by the lack of rational organization of preparation, storage, processing and sales systems. A large number of losses and a decrease in quality are observed in the links of the fruit and vegetable complex from the field to the consumer. This, in turn, causes an increase in the price of products in the markets and a decrease in the competitiveness of local products.

Losses in fruit and vegetable products can also lead to direct losses in terms of quantity. At this point, it is appropriate to define the concept of post-harvest losses and to touch on some trends observed in the world. According to the definition of the World Food and Agriculture Community (FAO), losses are reductions in both quantity and quality of products at all stages from harvesting from the field to the consumer. In this case, the loss

of quality is understood as the reduction of useful substances in the products or their becoming unfit for consumption. Such a loss is characteristic mainly of developed countries. And the loss of quantity, which means a decrease in the volume of production, is more likely to be contributed by developing countries. In developed countries (middle and high income population) there are cases of throwing away products even if they are suitable for consumption. In developing countries, products are lost at various stages (collection, transportation, sorting, storage, processing, etc.) until they reach the final consumption. Among the agricultural products consumed, fruits and vegetables are among the most perishable products¹.

Storage. According to statistical data, 30 percent of products are lost in the process of harvesting and storage of fruit and vegetable products in our country². One of the main elements of the supply chain of fruit and vegetable products is refrigerated warehouses. Depending on the application, fruits and vegetables play an important role in the quality and continuous supply of products. There are different types of cold storage, including:

1. Cold warehouses intended for distribution (organizes the distribution of the flow of perishable products from main transport to ready networks);
2. Refrigerated warehouses intended for preparation (prepare agricultural products for further transportation);
3. Logistics terminals with refrigeration (perishable products)
4. arranging shipment to other regions or countries)
5. Refrigerated warehouses of enterprises (intended for the processing of agricultural products);
6. Refrigerated warehouses for reloading (loading of perishable products from rail transport to road transport)
7. Customs refrigerated warehouses for temporary storage;
8. Customs refrigerated warehouses (intended for temporary storage of goods)
9. Refrigerated warehouses of retail chains

The reasons for the above-normal losses in terms of quality and quantity during storage of fruit and vegetable products are as follows:

1. initial quality for storage of fruits and

¹ Cattaneo, A., Federighi, G., & Vaz, S. (2020). The environmental impact of reducing food loss and waste: A critical assessment. *Food Policy*, August 2019, 101890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101890>

² www.agro.uz

vegetables;

2. refrigerating warehouses are located far from the field/garden and their storage costs are high;

3. high quality product packaging prices;

4. non-compliance with storage norms.

Uzbekistan is considered a producing country, and it is appropriate to establish sorting and packaging cold storage facilities. In fact, most of the existing cold rooms are used to store finished products. Also, almost 70 percent of warehouses are located 100–200 km away from the place of production. Based on the results of the research, it should be noted that the location of warehouses close to the cultivation areas has a positive effect on product quality and saves transportation costs. Improper proportioning of existing cold storage facilities limits the rational use of warehouse space and leads to violations of storage norms.

Transportation. Reasons for higher than normal losses in terms of quality and quantity during transportation of fruit and vegetable products are as follows:

1. initial quality for transportation of fruits and vegetables;

2. preparation of fruits and vegetables for transportation;

3. pre-cooling;

4. transport

Fruit and vegetable products are brought both to the domestic market and to the railway station for export using ordinary freight vehicles. In the domestic supply chain, this situation is not a big problem, because it does not take much time for the product to be distributed to the domestic market. In the export process, after temperature treatment, it is delivered to the designated station by railway transport, where it is unloaded according to the demand of stores for temporary storage and collection at the fruit and vegetable base, and then delivered to customers by refrigerated trucks from the fruit and vegetable base.

With this technology of transportation, the possibility of cooling perishable fruit and vegetable products before long-distance transportation is not taken into account, which leads to an increase in cargo damage on the road, as well as contradicts scientific recommendations in the field of refrigerated transport, and only manual labor is used at all stages of loading and unloading operations. leads to an increase in cost³.

³ Juraboev K.A. Improving the transportation of perishable goods by adjusting the logistics chain (on the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan), Diss. 04201352511, 2012

Processing. The sharp increase in the volume of fruit and vegetable products gives impetus to the development of the direct processing sector. 20 million tons of fruits and vegetables are grown in our country per year. But the rate of their industrial processing is 15 percent. By the end of 2019, 60 agricultural products processing projects were launched, but by the end of 2020, 16 processing enterprises were not launched⁴.

Fruit and vegetable processing processes differ depending on the raw materials being processed and the types of products being prepared. Therefore, fruit and vegetable processing processes have their own characteristics, which can be described as follows: Seasonality:

1. return at a certain time of the year;

2. duration of one or several months;

Brevity;

1. inability to stockpile raw materials for a certain period of time;

2. daily purchase of raw materials;

Amplitude;

1. at the beginning and end of the season, the enterprise will not have full capacity due to the decrease in the amount of raw materials;

2. increasing the capacity of the enterprise to the maximum when the ripening of processed raw materials is at a high point.

According to the results of research, this situation causes a number of inconveniences for processing enterprises. That is:

1. failure to operate equipment at the enterprise at full capacity;

2. problems in recruiting temporary workers hired for the enterprise;

3. consumption of excess energy due to the fact that the equipment is not at full efficiency.

Literature review

From foreign scholars on theoretical and methodological issues related to supply chain management by L. Cooper, M. Ellram, R. Bamou, J.F. Shapiro, J. Katalin, Ph. Wieser, Van der Vorst, R. J. Hodges, J. Liu, A, R. Sheoran, Y. K. Sharma, J. Parfitt, W. E. Soto-Silva, D. M. Ahmed Research in Fruit and Vegetable Supply Chain⁵.

From local scientists, Yo.K. Karrieva, G'.M. Kasimov, G'.A. Samatov, Q.A. Dadaboev, M.M. Tairova, E. Kamalova, I.B. Rustamov and issues related to the supply chain of fruit and

⁴ Ministry of Agriculture of Uzbekistan

⁵ Cooper, M. and Ellram, L. «Characteristics of Supply Chain Management and the Implications for Purchasing and Logistics Strategy»

vegetable products N.Kh. Borieva, N.R. Asadullina, H.S. Khushvaktova, F.R. Galimova, O.G. Scientists such as Dilmurodov have considered in research work⁶.

Material and methods

As a logical continuation of the theoretically considered issues, the goal was to determine the problems of these links of the supply chain by means of monographic research and interviews. Based on this goal, from March to June 2020, a total of 314 fruits It was necessary to conduct interviews with participants in the vegetable supply chain (212 suppliers, 26 middlemen, 26 cold store owners, 50 exporters), a questionnaire and 3 relatively large processing enterprises.

The reason is the lack of statistical and other types of data necessary for our research work. The questionnaire was considered important to determine the degree of achievement of the desired goal as a result of the planned program, and the educational and methodological manuals and scientific works of a number of foreign scientists on the procedure for conducting a social questionnaire were used in its development.

It consisted of a total of 40 questions, including general and separate questions directly related to the type of activity for each type of respondents. In this process, directly with the help of the experts of the Department of Working with Farmers of the Executive Committee of the Political Council of the UzLiDeP of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Entrepreneurship and Farming Support Center of Uzbekistan, the Association of Exporters of Uzbekistan, and the USAID organization (USA) «Development of the Value Chain in Uzbekistan» project, an anonymous and voluntary survey of respondents was conducted.

According to the social and demographic data of the survey, the types of activity: growers–52.63, intermediaries–15.79, owners of cold stores–10.53, exporter–21.05 percent; by place of residence: urban–26.1, rural–73.9 percent; by gender: 10.8% female, 89.2% male; according to information: high–64.3, middle–34.7%; by territorial location: Tashkent city–6.1, Karakalpakstan–9.1, Kashkadarya–2.5, Tashkent region–5.7, Surkhandarya–5.7, Andijan–11.5, Samarkand 12.7, Jizzakh–1 ,6, Fergana–15.9, Bukhara–2.2, Navoi–1.3, Namangan–4.8, Khorezm–19.7, Syrdarya–1 percent. According to the type of activity, 52.63 percent were producers, 21.05 percent were

⁶ O.G. Dilmurodov, Improvement of the logistics chain of product sales in the fruit and vegetable complex under the conditions of economic liberalization, diss. 2010.

exporters, 15.79 percent were middlemen, and 10.53 percent were owners of cold stores. 89.2% of the respondents are men and 10.8% are women. 73.9 percent live in the countryside, 26.1 percent live in the city. 64.3% of the survey participants have higher education and 34.7% have secondary education (Appendix 8).

Reducing the loss of fruits and vegetables not only increases the volume of products, but also ensures food security, and is considered an important factor in increasing the income of agricultural entrepreneurs. It is very important to maintain the quality of products even after harvesting.

However, due to the lack of necessary knowledge, advanced experience and modern technologies, part of the fruit and vegetable products perishes at various stages of the supply chain. This situation is observed at all stages, starting from the production of products, which is the initial link of the chain, to the delivery to the final consumer. In many developing countries, prevention of post-harvest losses is critical to supply chain actors as a source of income, poverty reduction, food security and job creation.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, 1/3 of the products grown for human consumption, that is, 1.3 billion tons, lose in a year⁷. According to some estimates, about 30–40 percent of the fruits and vegetables harvested from a farmer's field die or are discarded because they are unfit for consumption. Such a situation leads to a sharp decrease in the income of the participants of the supply chain (Figure 3). Loss and waste of products are two different concepts.

For example, the perishability of products occurs during the stages of growing products and their post-harvest management and processing. Waste is observed at the final stage of consumption, which is the last part of the chain, and directly depends on the attitude of consumers and final buyers to food products.

Post-harvest losses are caused by internal and external factors. External factors are caused by mechanical (physical damage during harvesting, packing, loading, unloading and transportation) and damage by parasitic diseases (fungi, bacteria, insects). Microorganisms quickly affect freshly grown products and multiply rapidly due to moisture in them. However, the pesticides used against them reduce the edibility of the product. Internal factors are caused by physiological disorders.

⁷ <https://www.fao.org/3/cc0639en/online/cc0639en.html> (full digital report)

Variables	Description
X1	Territory - on the scale of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent city and regions
X2	Place
X3	Age
X4	Gender
X5	Education
X6	Form of ownership
X7	Material equipment in the balance sheet
X8	Availability of an international quality certificate
X9	Product delivery location
X10	Use of refrigerated transport
X11	Type of product
X12	Land area, in hectares
X13	Cost, mln. In sum
X14	Yield, in tons
X15	Amount of product sold, in tons
X16	Product price per 1 kg, thousand sums
X17	Volume of losses, in kg
Factors influencing losses included as variables (growers, brokers, exporters and cold storage owners)	
X18	Sorting and packing operations are carried out In the field at high temperatures
X19	NON-compliance with storage norms
X20	Length of product delivery time
X21	Location of cold stores away from fields/gardens
X22	Other reasons

Table 1. Description of variables for analysis⁸

The product continues to breathe even after it has been dialed and causes heat to dissipate. If no action is taken to stop the cooling and ripening process, quality and flavor are lost and spoilage begins. In addition, losses occur for a number of other reasons.

A decrease in the quantity or quality of products at any stage of the supply chain leads to a decrease in profits. In our opinion, in the process of analyzing the damage caused by the perishability of fruit and vegetable products, it is appropriate to study the indirect effects in addition to the direct damage in terms of quantity and quality. For example, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the energy, land and water resources, manpower, transport and other factors spent

on the production of fruit and vegetable products can be spent on the production of other types of consumer products. It is very difficult to completely prevent losses, but it is possible to reduce its level. For example, the year-round availability of products to consumers ensures that imports are reduced and prices are affordable.

Analysis and results. Supply chain involves a complex process, and only those with a greater number of response options were considered. In this case, the occurrence of losses was 53 percent in delivery, 27 percent in sorting, and 20 percent in storage. The delivery process includes the process of processing the product after it is collected from the field, to the domestic market or to the

⁸ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

foreign market. Of course, there are a number of problems in the supply chain of fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan today, the lack of knowledge and skills of harvesters can cause problems related to losses in the entire chain. For example, 100 people should work to pick, sort, cool and export an average of 20 tons of cargo. If the capacity of the cold store is 1000 tons, it is not difficult to imagine how many people need to work to sort the average 250-300 tons of products placed in it. For the free movement of a large number of workers, the area of the cold room is required to be much larger than the volume of product storage. A lot of it comes down to well-informed staff. The conditions are sufficient to move to the sorting mechanism. The work is definitely not over with improving the qualifications of the workers. Currently, our existing cold storages

allow quantitative analysis of development indicators of losses in the supply chain, without neglecting the factors that influence it, and showing the relationship, taking into account the interaction of each factor.

Stata-15 statistical analysis program was used to determine the correlation between the factors we considered. Because this program can help to simplify the calculation and justify the accuracy in the process of statistical analysis. The classification of variables according to the factors mentioned in the questionnaire is presented in the following table 1.

It can be seen from most studies that relatively simple types of econometric models are usually used. In particular, the regression model (OLS) allows you to consider the effect

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Component 1	1.55549	0.355753	0.3889	0.3889
Component 2	1.19974	0.094562	0.2999	0.6888
Component 3	1.010518	0.965596	0.2763	0.9651
Component 4	0.139584	0	0.0349	1.0000

Table 2. Location of selected factors in components⁹

are able to fulfill their function only up to 60%. For example, if it is intended to export 10 tons of cargo in 10 days, they can only cool 6 tons during this period. The reason is that many people have built the third type of cold storage used for consumption. As a result, sorting works are carried out in the field itself, even if it

of several independent variables on exactly one dependent variable. In real life, we cannot take only one factor as the main influencer, one factor can affect the third factor through the second factor, it can affect several dependent variables at the same time, or some processes can be affected by several

Figure 1. Graphic display of component values¹⁰

does not meet the standards.

The relationship between the factors affecting the increase in the volume of losses can also be analyzed through a number of econometric models. Econometric models

factors at the same time. In doing so, we need more efficient econometric models for research. In the process of analysis, the use of PCA (Principal Component Analysis) models in

⁹ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

¹⁰ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

Variables	Component 1	Component 2	Component 3	Component 4
Sorting and packing operations are carried out in the field at high temperatures	-0.7727	-0.0356	-0.0356	0.6234
Non-compliance with storage norms	0.5247	-0.6043	-0.2941	0.5226
Length of delivery time	0.2614	0.7823	-0.3448	0.4480
Location of cold stores away from fields/gardens	0.2436	0.0987	0.8907	0.3709

Table 3. Indicators of selected factors in components (loading)¹¹

determining which factors are most responsible for losses in the supply chain of fruit and vegetable products increases the reliability and accuracy of the analysis results. The reason we chose these models is because they have several advantages over other models. In the framework of our research, we select a number of factors affecting the exact losses, one or two of them explaining the rest as a matrix.

Here, components with values greater than 1 are selected (component), that is, the variation should be greater than 10% as mentioned in the above section. We will need to select components by eigenvalue. Looking at the table, the values of component 1 and component 2 are greater than 1, and the value of component 3 is very close to 1. These can be clearly seen in Figure 3 below.

It can be seen that the model presented 4 components by entering the given 4 variables into a matrix. As a rule, three of them were accepted because the value was correct. Now it is time to determine the weight

Determination of the correlation matrix	
Determinant	0.085
Bartlett test of sphericity	
Chi-square	839.217
Degree of freedom	10
p-value	0.000
Kaise mayer Olkin Measure	0.50

Table 3. Indicators of selected factors in components (loading)

(loading) of each of the selected variables in the composition of the components provided by the model. The weight of the factors in the components should be greater than -0, 30 or 0.30 (Table 2).

Noticed that the weights of the selected factors in the components from the above table, the weights of the variables of high temperature sorting and packaging (-0.77) and non-observance of storage norms (0.52) are in accordance with the requirements. It can be concluded that these 2 variables (high temperature sorting and packing and non-observance of storage norms), i.e. these 2

factors affecting the losses, are the other factors (the length of product delivery time and the location of cold storages far from the field/garden) manifests itself.

From the table above, the correlation coefficient matrix corresponding to the Chi-square statistic has a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, the predicted level of significance, which indicates that the hypothesis that the correlation matrix of these variables is not significant is rejected. It should be noted that the data is almost 86 times larger than the variables obtained from 344 samples (4), where the actual required sample size should be 4-5 times larger than the variables. Kaiser Mayer Olkin Measure (KMO) interprets the adequacy of selected factors, where the value is 0.50. All this justifies the use of factor analysis for this model.

Conclusion

Taking into account the specific characteristics of fruit and vegetable products, it is appropriate to consider the processes in the chain from the stage of its delivery to the consumer. The value chain developed in the global community was shared with some considerations for its implementation in the conditions of Uzbekistan. In conclusion, we can cite the following:

1. In Uzbekistan, great importance is attached to the processes of growing and exporting fruit and vegetable products, but there are shortcomings in the issues of their delivery, storage, and packaging.

2. In improving the current state of the value chain of fruit and vegetable products, it is appropriate to take into account the mutual integration of growing, processing, exporting participants.

3. The opinions of the participants of the supply chain are important when choosing the factors that affect the quantity and quality of losses in fruit and vegetable products. Based on this, we believe that surveys should be conducted among all the links involved in the fruit and vegetable supply chain, that is, growers, processors, warehouse owners, and exporters.

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¹¹ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

Evaluation and characterization of modernization of the food industry

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Kalit so'zlar

food industry, modernization, expert evaluation method, competence, concordance coefficient.

Abstract

The article uses the expert survey method to assess the process of modernization of the food industry. Initially, the article provides a brief description of the scientific sources on the topic. The issues of selection of experts, determination of their qualifications, assessment of the degree of closeness and consistency of the expert opinion were then discussed. In the last part of the article, all the results obtained are summarized.

Introduction

Economic reforms aimed at accelerating economic development and improving the welfare of the population in our country are yielding positive results. In particular, the role of government programs in the efficient use of land, water and other natural resources and long-term work in meeting the needs of the population in food, which has become one of the global problems, is growing.

The development of the food industry will have a strong impact on the development of services such as banking, insurance, communications, trade and transport. In particular, many sectors of the service sector are directly dependent on the food industry, and without these services, food products will simply not be available. The food industry will also have a positive impact on the development of research, wholesale and retail trade, and catering.

Due to the above, the sustainable and balanced development of the food industry is of great importance today, and the modernization of its internal sectors plays an important role in achieving such goals.

«Economists estimate that additional economic growth of 2-3% per year can be

achieved through development based on domestic scientific and technological potential, and 7-8% per year through the introduction of the latest technologies in the modernization process.»

Modernization of the food industry is a process of technological innovation aimed at increasing the competitiveness of products, which is a means of overcoming technological backwardness in the industry and allows for more efficient use of labor and material resources. In turn, the results of the process of technical and technological innovations determine the conditions for the rapid development of high-tech competitive production.

The main goal of modernization of industrial sectors is to modernize the industry and its products, accelerate innovative development through the development of priority industries with high science capacity, increase the competitiveness of national industry and thus meet the growing and changing needs of the population. consists of lacquer satisfaction².

1 Махмудов Н.М., Хомидов С.О. (2017) Ўзбекистон саноати: ривожланиш омиллари, тенденцияси ва муаммолари. 158-б ред. Тошкент: Иктисодиёт.

2 Антонов З.Г., Л. В., 2013. Неоиндустриальная модернизация в современной России.. Томск, Известия Томского политехнического университета, pp. 34-39.

However, modernization of the industrial and food industries is a complex process that requires a lot of time and money. On the other hand, this complexity is explained by the relatively limited ability to quantify technological development and the lack of statistical data.

Therefore, it is advisable to use the opinion of experts in making decisions on the modernization of the food industry of the republic.

The advantage of this method is that if it is not possible to quantify complex development processes and require the formation of personal opinions about a particular process or object, this method is used and appropriate decisions are made based on the views of experts in the field³. The study focuses on the quantitative aspects of the expert survey method.

Analysis of the relevant literature

The analysis of scientific sources shows that the theoretical and practical aspects of the application of the expert survey method, in which the selected research topic belongs to a particular research topic, are described in detail in the research. Today, the expert survey method is a research method that is common to almost all disciplines. Therefore, this method is used in the formation of quantitative data on objects or socio-economic events, qualitative classification of indicators, development of various evaluation criteria, approval of developed national and international indices, analysis of socio-economic processes and weather. It is widely used in solving problems such as quantitative assessment of the state of affairs.

In general, the expert evaluation method in the scientific literature is an empirical method – a type of survey that involves people in the evaluation of an operation, event, or process being studied, and may have a general authoritative opinion. Sufficient basis for objective cleaning about the quality of the product under analysis⁴.

In qualimetry, the expert method is a set of special procedures, logical and mathematical methods used by experts to collect, summarize and analyze data⁵.

In any case, the list of factors influencing decision-making, their weight, as well as, it is necessary to involve a team of experts in the

rating to assess the quality of IT implementation or to improve its modules and data processing to get an overview. It is known that the essence of the expert assessment method is that experts conduct an intuitive-logical analysis of the problem with a quantitative assessment of feedback and formal processing of the results⁶.

However, the performance of expert systems is still far from ideal. The decline in their productivity may be due to the difficulty of translating jargon into the language of logic and mathematics, which is typical of the communication of specialists in a narrow specialty.

Moreover, principles based on expert knowledge are not always clearly articulated in terms of a given computer model. This is also complemented by the fact that knowledge based on personal experience may not be formalized to the extent that it can be generalized as a set of facts and general principles. The context does not play the final role here, its elements must be taken into account in decision-making, and what the expert sees on his own cannot always be modeled equally by the system⁷.

Therefore, the most effective situation is when a human expert works in conjunction with an expert system, while the latter works as an authorized partner and consultant on a particular topic.

Thus, the expert system does not try to replace the human specialist, but helps to expand the scope of knowledge of a reputable expert by combining the experience and knowledge of highly qualified specialists⁸.

In practice, there are many methods used to assess the level of competence of experts. In particular, if A.F. Garifulin used multidimensional index methods in assessing the level of competence of experts⁹, A.N. Anoxin used an arithmetic mean to assess the level of competence of each expert¹⁰. In his research, S.O. Khomidov also used arithmetic mean values in the selection of experts, their competence, the degree of consistency of expert opinion and the level of expert competence¹¹.

The next most important issue in expert

6 Evlanov L.G., Kutuzov V.A. Expert assessment in the management [Jekspertnye ochenki v upravlenii]. Moscow, Jekonomika, 1978 (In Russ.)

7 Джексон П. Введение в экспертные системы. - М.: Вильямс, 2001. - 624 с.

8 Муромцев Д.И. Введение в технологию экспертных систем. - СПб.: СПб ГУ ИТМО, 2005. - 93 с.

9 Гарифулин А.Ф. (2013) Экспертное оценивание при разработке эффективной стратегии.. Справочник экономиста, 8(1), р. 4.

10 Анохин А.Н. (1996) Методы экспертных оценок. 82 ред. Москва: Обнинск: ИАТЭ

11 Хомидов С.О. (2019) Қайта ишловчи саноат тармоқларини модернизациялаш бўйича қарорлар қабул қилишда экспертлар фикридан фойдаланиш услуби. Иктисод ва молия. №4 (124), 2019.

3 Орлов А.И. (2009) Организационно-экономическое моделирование: Учебник: в 3ч. 486 ред. Москва: МГТУ им. Н.Э.Баумана

4 Профессиональная педагогика / под ред. С.Я. Батышева, А.М. Новикова. - М.: ЭГВЕС, 2009. - 456 с.

5 Бешелев С.Д., Гурвич Ф.Г. Математико-статистические методы экспертных оценок. - М.: Статистика, 1980. - 263 с

assessment is the assessment of the «degree of consistency of expert opinion.» This process is done by calculating the concordance coefficient. Based on the obtained values of this coefficient, appropriate decisions are made about a particular object or socio-economic processes.

The method of determining the concordance coefficient is almost the same in all the literature. However, the overlap of the estimates formed by the experts with respect to the object under evaluation or the socio-economic process complicates the method of calculating the concordance coefficient.

The process of calculating the concordance coefficient taking into account the considered aspects is described in the literature published by V.A. Mashin¹² and G.F. Romashkina and G.G. Tatarova, and the statistical significance of the concordance coefficient was estimated using Pearson's χ^2 criterion¹³.

Research methodology

Expert evaluation involves creating a type of mind that has greater capabilities than a person's capabilities. The source of multimind opportunities is the search for weak associations and assumptions based on the experience of the individual specialist. The expert approach allows you to solve problems that cannot be solved in the usual analytical way, including:

1. Choose the best of the available solutions;
2. Predicting the development of the process;
3. Finding possible solutions to complex problems.

The selection of experts based on the process of applying the expert assessment method, formation of expert groups, assessment of their level of competence, we perform steps to analyze the degree of coherence of expert opinions. The study also focuses on issues such as data processing by experts and making specific decisions based on the results obtained.

Generally, the number of experts in groups should be between 7 and 20. Sometimes this amount can be from 10 to 30. A very small number of experts leads to unreliable results, while a large number of experts causes organizational problems. Therefore, it is recommended to use the

following inequality in determining the required number of experts:

$$m \leq \frac{3}{2 \cdot Q_{max}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{m^*} Q_i$$

In this case m^* - the total number of candidates, Q_{max} - the maximum value of the competency coefficient, Q_i - i - expert competence.

The following formula is sometimes used to determine the minimum number of experts¹⁴:

$$N = 0.5 \left(\frac{3}{\alpha} + 5 \right)$$

In this case, the parameter α is the minimum level of expert error, the value of which varies in the range $0 < \alpha \leq 1$.

There are expert assessments based on the level of completeness and this is expressed in terms of a matrix of the form and this is expressed in terms of a matrix of the form $A = \|a_{ij}\|_{m \times n}$ ¹⁵. In this case, m - the set of evaluated objects, n - the set of experts.

Then, for the first given matrix A , the matrix $C = A^T A$ is calculated. In this case, the A^T -matrix is the transposed matrix for the given initial matrix. Then, by performing various substitutions for the rows of the S -matrix, (3) matrices are formed.

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ \tilde{n}_{21} & \tilde{n}_{22} & \dots & \tilde{n}_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & \dots & c_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow y = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{c_{11} \cdot c_{12} \cdot \dots \cdot c_{1n}} \\ \sqrt{c_{21} \cdot c_{22} \cdot \dots \cdot c_{2n}} \\ \dots \\ \sqrt{c_{n1} \cdot c_{n2} \cdot \dots \cdot c_{nn}} \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow x = \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \dots \\ y_n \end{pmatrix}$$

The resulting matrix in expression (3) indicates the level of competence of the experts. As mentioned above, different methods are used to determine the level of competence of experts. One such method is determined using the following formula¹⁶:

$$K_j = \frac{\sum(X_{ij} \times M_i)}{\sum(M_i \times S_i)}$$

In this case, K_j - the coefficient of competence of the expert, X_{ij} - assessment of the i - object by the expert, M_i - the average

14 С.Д.Ильенкова, Л.М.Гохберг, С.Ю.Ягудин и др. (1997) Инновационный менеджмент: Учебник для вузов. 327 ред. Москва: М.: Банки и биржи, ЮНИТИ.

15 Mashin V.A. (2008) Методическое руководство по оценке тестовых процедур, применяемых при работе с персоналом., Москва: www.mashinva.narod.ru.

16 Гарифулин А.Ф. (2013) Экспертное оценивание при разработке эффективной стратегии.. Справочник экономиста, 8(1), p. 4.

12 Mashin V.A. (2008) Методическое руководство по оценке тестовых процедур, применяемых при работе с персоналом., Москва: www.mashinva.narod.ru.

13 Ромашкина Г.Ф., Татарова Г.Г. (2005) Социология. Социология: методология, методы, математическое моделирование, 20(4АМ), pp. 139-140.

value of the object, S_i - the sum of the values of the object.

«Consensus of experts» is very important in the method of expert inquiry. If the level of agreement of the experts is high, then the results of the expert survey are considered reliable. To assess the degree of consistency of expert opinion, the «concordance coefficient» is calculated and is determined as follows¹⁷:

$$W = \frac{12 \times S}{d^2 \times (m^3 - m)}$$

In this case, the W - concordance coefficient, d - number of experts involved, m

Numerical values of the concordance coefficient	Levels of consistency of expert opinion
$0 \leq W \leq 0.2$	The compromise is very past
$0.2 \leq W \leq 0.37$	Compromise is the past
$0.37 \leq W \leq 0.64$	Consistency is average
$0.64 \leq W \leq 0.8$	Consistency is high
$0.8 \leq W \leq 1$	Consistency is very high

Table 1. Harrington's verbal-numbered scale

- the number of objects, S - a quantitative quantity in the concordance coefficient, it is defined as follows:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\sum_{s=1}^d r_{is} - \bar{r} \right)^2$$

In this case, r_{is} - the value or color given to the object by the s - expert, which is defined as follows:

$$r_i = \sum_{s=1}^d r_{is}, \quad (i = \overline{1, m})$$

The mean \bar{r}_i of (\bar{r}) in equation (7) is found by the following formula:

$$\bar{r} = \frac{1}{m} \times \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{s=1}^d r_{is}$$

If the evaluations of the objects evaluated by the experts overlap, then the concordance coefficient is determined as follows¹⁸:

$$W = \frac{12 \times S}{d^2 \times (m^3 - m) - d \times \sum_{s=1}^d T_s}$$

17 Губский М.И. (2011) Методика оценки состояния развития логистики в Республике Беларусь. Проблемы управления, 3(40), p. 123.

18 Жилиякова Е.В., Ларин С.Н. (2009) Методы и приемы проведения независимой экспертизы. Вестник ВГУ, 2(Экономика и управление), p. 113.

In this case, T_s - an interconnected color index between the ranked values, which can be found as follows:

$$T_s = \sum_{k=1}^{H_s} (h_k^3 - h_k)$$

The number of groups with equal colors between the H_s - ranked values, h_k - the number of equal colors in the group. If there are no comparison colors in the expert estimates, then $H_s=0, T_s=0$, and also $T_s=0$. It is recommended to use the Harrington verbal-numerical scale to assess the quality of the degree of coherence of expert opinion (Table 1).

According to the table, the degree of consistency of expert opinions varies from 0 to 1. The closer the values get together, the higher the degree of consistency of expert opinion, or vice versa. In practice, if $m > 7$, then the criterion χ^2 - used to assess the significance of the concordance coefficient¹⁹. The distribution χ^2 with the degree of freedom $v=m-1$ assumes the following value:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{12 \times S}{d \times m \times (m + 1) - \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{s=1}^d T_s}$$

If $W > \chi^2$, the degree of coherence of the expert opinion is reasonable, otherwise such coherence will be negligible. In practice, the «entropy concordance coefficient» is also used to assess the degree of consistency of expert opinion, and it is defined as follows²⁰:

$$W_e = 1 - \frac{H}{H_{max}}$$

If we take into account the evaluation of $p_{ij} = m_{ij}/m$ and $m_{ij} = m/n$, then the sum is equal:

$$H = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \log_2 \frac{1}{n} = \sum_{j=1}^m \log_2 n = m \cdot \log_2 n$$

19 Галиновский А.Л., Самсонов К.С. и др. (2017) Сравнение различных методов контроля и диагностики качества керамики методом экспертного оценивания Инновация и экспертиза, 1(19), p. 68.

20 В.В.Давнис, (2005) Прогнозные модели экспертных предположений: монография. 45 ред. Воронеж: Воронеж. гос. ун-т.

In this case, p_{ij} – the estimate of the object and j -color probability, m –experts and the number of n –colors.

The entropy coordinate coefficient gives a slightly rougher result than the normal coefficient, and its value is 1 ($W_e=1$) when all objects are considered to be the same by experts.

The high value of the concordance coefficient obtained during the expert evaluation confirms the high degree of consistency of expert opinion. In this case, the opinions of experts on the object of assessment or socio-economic process are usually considered close.

There are many methods used in practice to measure the closeness of expert opinions.

One such method is determined using Ustyujanin's formula²¹:

$$S_{ij} = \frac{2 \cdot m_{ij}}{n_i \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{n_j}{n_i}\right) + n_j \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{n_i}{n_j}\right)}$$

In this case, S_{ij} – a criterion for the compatibility of the opinions of experts and j or «Informative measure of the closeness of the answers of two experts²²» m_{ij} – and j – the number of factors evaluated uniformly by experts, n_i and n_j , i – and j – the number of factors evaluated by experts, respectively. S_{ij} in the formula (15) is the sum ($(\sum_{j=1}^n S_{ij})$), i the

Objects (networks)	Experts						
	No1	No2	No3	No4	No5	No6	No7
Meat processing (O ₁)	6	5	8	7	6	7	8
Milk processing (O ₂)	7	8	5	6	7	6	5
Vegetable processing (O ₃)	9	7	6	9	8	5	7
Fruit processing (O ₄)	7	6	8	6	7	5	4
Vegetable oil production (O ₅)	10	8	6	5	8	5	7
Manufacture of confectionery (O ₆)	6	5	8	7	6	7	9
Beer production (O ₇)	5	3	6	4	8	7	8
Production of canned food (O ₈)	8	9	7	6	5	5	4
Production of carbonated water (O ₉)	4	5	6	8	7	8	6
Manufacture of bread and bakery products (O ₁₀)	7	6	8	4	8	7	9

Table 2. Expert scores on the need to replace existing technology in key sectors of the food industry²³

index of expert competence, where it varies in the range $0 \leq S_{ij} \leq 1$. If, $S_{ij}=1$, then the opinions of these experts are completely consistent, and vice versa, that is, if $S_{ij}=0$, then it means that

21 Мартеньянов Ю.Ф. (2010) Экспертные методы принятия решений. 16 ред. Тамбов: Изд-во Тамб. гос. техн. ун-та.

22 Пиганов М.Н., Подлипов Г.А. (2004) Экспертные оценки в управлении качеством радио-электронных средств. 55 ред. Самара: Самара. гос. аэрокосм. ун-та.

the opinion of the experts is completely inconsistent.

Analysis and discussion of results

modernization in the food industry, 10 ($m = 10$) sectors of the food industry were selected and a total of 7 experts ($d = 7$) were used to assess these processes.

One of the members of the expert group asked, «How necessary is it now to replace the existing technology in the food industry?» was asked to answer the question of the content. In order to find an answer to this question, experts adopted a «10-point rating scale.» This rating scale rises from the bottom up, and its rising values reflect the need for experts to replace existing technology in the relevant food industries.

23 Source: The data was generated by the author using the expert survey method.

24 Author's calculations.

was the highest and the level of competence of expert 6 was the lowest (Figure 1).

Table 2 shows the scores of experts on the need to replace existing technology in key sectors of the food industry. The results of the

Figure 2. Trends in the coefficients of variation in the dynamics of scores given by experts to the main branches of the food industry (in percent)²⁵

expert assessment show that the scores given by the experts on the need for replacement of existing technology in the main sectors of the food industry were a minimum of 3.0 and a maximum of 10.0. According to the analysis, the average score in the vegetable processing industry was the highest at 7.2 ($\bar{r} = 7.2$), while in the beer industry it was $\bar{r} = 5.8$ represents the lowest value.

The coefficients of variation in the dynamics of scores shown by experts to the main branches of the food industry have the following trend (Figure 2).

As can be seen from the graph, the object of O7, ie the «degree of stratification²⁶» (coefficient of variation $V = 30.85$) in the dynamics of the scores expressed by experts in the decision to modernize the beer industry, was stronger than the stratification in the

dynamics of the scores shown in the decision to modernize other sectors. In the meat processing industry (O1), this stratification ($V = 15.34$) was relatively low.

Conclusions and suggestions

The results of the analysis show that the level of consensus of experts in making decisions on modernization of the network, that is, with a concordance coefficient of $W = 0.025$, this value is in the 2nd order range of the Harrington verbal scale.

Based on the obtained value of the concordance coefficient, it was concluded that, the level of consensus of experts in the decision to replace existing technology in the food industry is low. In this case, we compare by the criterion χ^2 ($\chi^2=1.56$) and the degree of consistency of the opinion of the experts turns out to be insignificant. It serves as a basis for the scientific conclusion that there is no need to introduce new technologies in the food industry.

According to the results of the expert assessment, the stratification of the dynamics of the points indicated by the experts in the decision to modernize the beer industry ($V = 30.85$), turned out to be stronger than the stratification in the dynamics of the scores shown by the experts in the decision to modernize other sectors. The results of the analysis show that the degree of consensus of experts in the decision to replace the existing technology in the food industry is insignificant ($W = 0.025$), it was found that it was not expedient to introduce new technology in the food industry at present.

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Korrelyatsion va regression tahlillar orqali tadbirkorlik faoliyatining iqtisodiy barqarorligini aniqlash masalalari

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Abstract

Mazkur maqolada rivojlangan mamlakatlar tajribasiga asoslangan holda mamlakatimizda kichik biznes subyektlarining barqarorligini ta'minlash, uning iqtisodiyotdagi ulushini oshirish, aholi bandligini ta'minlash va yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratishda korrelyatsion va regression tahlil qilinib, ushbu sohaning YalMdagi ulushidagi prognozi hisoblab chiqilgan. Shuningdek, kelajakda tadbirkorlik subyektlari duch kelishi mumkin bo'lgan xafv-xatarlar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari tadqiq etilgan.

Kirish

Dunyoda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyot hamda barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi ahamiyati bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar izchil amalga oshirilmoqda. "Kichik biznes AQSH, Germaniya, Xitoy, Fransiya, Yaponiya, Italiya kabi rivojlangan mamlakatlarda iqtisodiyotni barqarorlashtirishda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Xalqaro kichik biznes Kengashi (ICSB) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, dunyo bo'yicha kichik biznes subyektlari barcha korxonalarining 90% dan ortig'ini, ish bilan band bo'lganlarning 60-70% ni, yalpi ichki mahsulotning 50% ni tashkil etadi".¹

Odatda 250 dan kam inson ishlaydigan ushbu korxonalar rivojlangan mamlakatlar iqtisodiyoti asosini tashkil etadi va bu albatta iqtisodiy rivojlanishni rag'batlantirish, qo'shimcha ish o'rinlarini yaratish, ayollar, yosh tadbirkorlar hamda kam ta'minlangan aholi guruhlari ishga joylashtirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, "Xitoyda ish bilan band aholining 81,4 foizi, YAIMning 54,3

foizi, Yaponiyada mos ravishda 70,8; 67,0 foizi, AQSH da 50,6; 53,1 foizi kichik biznes ulushiga to'g'ri kelmoqda".²

Albatta, kichik biznes subyektlari keng faoliyat yuritayotgan joylarda aholining ish o'rinlari bilan ta'minlanish darajasining yuqoriligi hamda daromadlarning oshib borishi, ishbilarmonlarning innovasion va investision tashabbuslarini rivojlantirish va rag'batlantirish, umuman milliy iqtisodiyotning jadal sur'atlar bilan o'sishiga ijobiy ta'sir etadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, milliy iqtisodiyot ushuning salmoqli omili bo'lgan KBSning barqarorligi va mustahkamligini tadqiq qilish alohida muhim ahamiyat kasb qilmoqda.

Chunki bu zamonaviy iqtisodiy o'sish omili o'z o'rnida barqarorlikni mustahkamlash uchun davlatning huquqiy, tashkiliy, iqtisodiy va moliyaviy qo'llab quvvatlashini taqazo etadi, ayniqsa, COVID-19 pandemiya davrining salbiy oqibatlarini natijasida tadbirkorlikning barqarorligi va faoliyatini saqlab qolish masalasi yanada yaqqalroq namayon bo'ldi.

Mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotini barqaror rivojlantirish hamda aholi farovonligini

¹ MSME Day 2019. <http://www.intracen.org/MSME-day/2019/>

² <http://www.ifc.org.msmeconomyindicator>.

oshirishda kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etib bormoqda. Bugungi kunda kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik yalpi ichki mahsulotning 55 foizini, iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida ish bilan band bo'lgan aholining

aholisining yarmidan ko'pi ushbu sohada ishlaydi. Kichik biznes Germaniyada eng faol rivojlanmoqda. Kichik biznesning mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga qo'shayotgan hissasi umumiy yalpi ichki mahsulotning deyarli 100 foizini

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Y	22	104729.6	123500.1	1009.236	403288.6
x1	22	29967.95	38039.16	244	121719.2
x2	22	15666.33	22520.7	149	77762
x3	22	27302.95	55544.28	114.8	244962.6
x4	22	8250.171	2047.485	4467.1	10541.5
x5	22	2069981	1461503	224305	4714757
x6	22	4972508	4134249	672099.3	1.50e+07
x7	22	48944.81	59366.15	760.3318	204787.4

1-rasm. Ma'lumotlarning qisqacha tasfiy statistikasi³

deyarli 75 foizini tadbirkorlik sub'yektlarida faoliyat bilan band bo'lishmoqda. Vaholanki, 2000 yilda bu soha yalpi ichki mahsulotdagi ulushi 31 foizdan iborat edi, mos ravishda bandlikdagi ulush esa hozirgi ko'rsatkichdan qariyb 1/3 nisbatda kam bo'lgan.

Rivojlangan mamlakatlar tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, kichik biznesni qo'llab-quvvatlash orqali ular undan soliq, innovasiyalarni rivojlantirish, mamlakat aholisini ish bilan ta'minlash shaklida daromad oladi. Statistik ma'lumotlar kichik biznes subyektlari jahonning etakchi davlatlari iqtisodiyoti rivojiga qo'shayotgan yuqori hissasini aks ettiradi.

Masalan, AQSHda 17 millionga yaqin kichik biznes mavjud. Kichik biznes yalpi milliy mahsulotnina 50% dan ortig'ini yaratadi.

tashkil etadi. Mehnatga layoqatli aholidan ko'prog'i kichik biznes sub'yektlari hisobidan ish bilan ta'minlangan. Germaniyaning 1000 dan ortiq kichik korxonalari jahon eksporti etakchilariga aylangan.

Adabiyotlar tahlili

Xorijiy mamlakatlarda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik faoliyatini barqaror rivojlanishi, barqarorlik omillari tahlili va strategiyalari, tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning ilg'or usul va metodlarini nazariy va amaliy jihatdan o'rgangan olimlar: Yang Y., Williams N., Ayala J., Aman R., Santoro G., Singh R., Weidinger C., Li R., Fatoki O., Wall T., Zhu X., Vlasov M., Du M., Hedner T. and Abouzeedan A. Gherhes C., Levin S., Bullough A., Ansah I. va

	Y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7
Y	1.0000							
x1	0.9968	1.0000						
x2	0.9754	0.9735	1.0000					
x3	0.8527	0.8498	0.9167	1.0000				
x4	0.7347	0.7045	0.6160	0.4452	1.0000			
x5	0.8053	0.7759	0.7129	0.5366	0.9148	1.0000		
x6	0.9477	0.9332	0.9167	0.7527	0.7924	0.0846	1.0000	
x7	0.9966	0.9939	0.9872	0.8858	0.7024	0.7718	0.9341	1.0000

2-rasm. Korrelyatsion tahlil matrisasi⁴

Iqtisodiyotning qishloq xo'jaligidan tashqari barcha tarmoqlarida kichik biznesni boshqarish standarti bo'yicha korxonalarining deyarli 97 foizi kichikdir. Yevropa biznes assotsiyasining statistik ma'lumotlari ham Yevropa Ittifoqi mamlakatlarida kichik biznes ancha faol rivojlanib, samarali faoliyat yuritayotganini ko'rsatadi. Yevropada bu barcha korxonalarining 70% dan 90% gacha tashkil qiladi. Yevropa Ittifoqi mamlakatlari

boshqalar tomonidan tadqiq etilgan [1-15].

Asosiy qism

Mamlakatimizdagi kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda bir qancha omillarning tasiri asosida ma'lumotlar tahlili va ekonometrik modellar tuzib natijalar tahlilini amalga oshiramiz. Tadqiqot davomida biz asosiy omil qilib KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatan (mird so'm)-

³ Muallif tomonidan STATA14 amaliy paketi asosida tahlil amalga oshirildi.
⁴ Muallif ishlanmasi.

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. reg Y x3 x4
```

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	22
Model	2.8326e+11	2	1.4163e+11	F(2, 19)	=	72.65
Residual	3.7040e+10	19	1.9495e+09	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.8844
				Adj R-squared	=	0.8722
Total	3.2030e+11	21	1.5252e+10	Root MSE	=	44153

Y	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
x3	1.457535	.1937174	7.52	0.000	1.05208 1.86299
x4	26.71429	5.255174	5.08	0.000	15.71508 37.7135
_cons	-155462.9	42334.05	-3.67	0.002	-244069 -66856.66

3-rasm. Regression tahlil natijasi⁵

Y va unga ta'sir etuvchi qilib KBXTning sanoatdagi miqdori (mlrd so'm) - X_1 , qurilishdagi miqdori(mlrd so'm)- X_2 , investitsiyadagi miqdori(mlrd so'm)- X_3 , KBXTda band bo'lganlar soni - X_4 , eksportdagi miqdori(ming.AQSH dollar) - X_5 , importdagi miqdori (ming. AQSH dollar) - X_6 , savdodagi miqdori (mlrd.so'm) - X_7 qilib tanlab olindi.

Barcha o'zgaruvchilarni Davlat statistika qo'mitasi tomonida berilgan 2000-2021 yillar ma'lumotlar asosida ma'lumotlar va ekonometrik tahlillarni amalga oshirdik. Natijada 22 yil oralig'ida KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatan o'rtacha 104729,6 mlrd.so'mni hamda eng yuqori 403288,6 mlrd.so'm miqdorni tashkil topdi(1-rasm).

Regression tahlil natijasi asosida ko'p omilli chiziqli model quyidagi shakilda ifodalaniildi:

$$Y = -155462.9 + 1.4575 * x3 + 26.7142 * x4 + \varepsilon$$

Tuzilgan modelning shakli Fisher mezoni bo'yicha xulosa qilganda to'g'ri va ahamiyatli ekanligi ko'rishingiz mumkin. Bevosita Fisher ni p-value qiymati asosida ahamiyatli va determinatsiya koeffitsiyenti $R^2=0.884$ ga teng, bu esa model real qiymatga 88 foizga yaqinligini ifodalab turibdi. Shuningdek, modelning parametrlari t-sritical student qiymatida tahlil qiladigan bo'lsak, barcha koeffitsiyentlar ishonchli ekanligini ko'rishingiz mumkin. Shu bilan bir qatorda modelga qatnashayotgan omillarga e'tibor beradigan bo'lsak, Kobb-Duglas funksiyasiga mos kelganini ko'rishingiz mumkin.

Kobb-Duglas ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi iqtisodiy prognozlashda keng qo'llaniladigan funksiyalaridan biridir. Bu funksiya ishlab chiqarishning amaliy omillari (mehnat va kapital) hajmi va mahsulot hajmi o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni ifodalaydi. Bunda ishlab chiqarish hajmi (Y) ishlab chiqarish omillarining mavjud zaxiralari va ulardan

foydalanish samaradorligi bilan belgilanadi. Ishlab chiqarish omillari mehnat L va kapital K bilan belgilanadi. Ishlab chiqarish omillaridan foydalanish samaradorligi kapital bilan marjinal unumdorlik ko'rsatkichlari - m va mehnat bilan - (1 - m):

$$Y = A \times K^m \times L^{(1-m)}$$

bunda A - ishlab chiqarish hajmining mahsulotga ta'sirini aks ettiruvchi koeffitsiyent.

O'sish sur'atlarining nisbiy nuqtai nazaridan makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar juda oddiy ko'rinadi:

$$y = k \times m + l \times (1 - m)$$

bunda k - kapitalning o'rtacha yillik o'sish sur'ati; m - kapital bo'yicha ishlab chiqarish hajmining elastiklik koeffitsiyenti; l - mehnatning o'rtacha yillik o'sish sur'ati; (1 - m) - bu mehnat uchun ishlab chiqarish hajmining elastikligi koeffitsiyenti.

Ushbu turdagi ishlab chiqarish funksiyalari ishlab chiqarish natijalari va ishlab chiqarish omillari samaradorligi o'rtasida qat'iy bog'liqlikni, ya'ni mehnat va kapital uchun samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlarining biriga tengligini nazarda tutadi. Ushbu shart iqtisodiyotdagi munosabatlarni tavsiflashda ya'ni funksiyadan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini sezilarli darajada qisqartiradi. Chunki y ishlab chiqarish hajmini ishlab chiqarish omillari xarajatlarining o'sishiga mos ravishda ko'payishini nazarda tutadi.

Ushbu cheklovni bartaraf etish uchun olimlar Kobb-Duglasning ishlab chiqarish funksiyasini o'zgartirishni, ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyotning iqtisodiy o'sishga neytral ta'siridagi cheklovni olib tashlaydigan tuzatishlarni kiritishni taklif qildilar.

Bulardan biri R.Solou ishlab chiqarish omillari bitta bo'lgan ko'rsatkichlar kattaligidagi tenglik cheklovini olib tashlagan.

5 Muallif hisob-kitob natijalari.

```
. reg LY LL LK time
```

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	22
Model	75.2065975	3	25.0688658	F(3, 18)	=	1053.28
Residual	.428414775	18	.023800821	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9943
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9934
Total	75.6350123	21	3.60166725	Root MSE	=	.15428

LY	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
LL	2.322778	.3252648	7.14	0.000	1.639422 3.006134
LK	.1845332	.1626477	1.13	0.271	-.157177 .5262434
time	.1331291	.0541349	2.46	0.024	.0193958 .2468624
_cons	-13.54337	2.721465	-4.98	0.000	-19.26095 -7.82578

4-rasm. Regression tahlil natijasi⁶

U ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi $(a + b) = 1$ ko'rinishida takomillashtirgan va quyidagicha ifodalagan:

$$Y = A \times K^a \times L^b$$

$(a + b) = 1$ bo'lganda, bu funksiya barcha kamchiliklari bilan Kobb-Duglas ishlab chiqarish funksiyasiga aylanadi. Agar

quyidagicha ifodalaydi:

$$y = k \times a + l \times b$$

bunda k - kapitalning o'rtacha yillik o'sish sur'ati; a - kapital bo'yicha ishlab chiqarish hajmining elastiklik koeffitsiyenti; l - mehnatning o'rtacha yillik o'sish sur'ati; b - mehnat bilan ishlab chiqarish hajmining elastiklik

```
. reg LY LL LK
```

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	22
Model	75.0626571	2	37.5313285	F(2, 19)	=	1245.90
Residual	.572355208	19	.030123958	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9924
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9916
Total	75.6350123	21	3.60166725	Root MSE	=	.17356

LY	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
LL	2.351587	.3656918	6.43	0.000	1.586186 3.116989
LK	.5713078	.0466381	12.25	0.000	.4736931 .6689224
_cons	-15.53331	2.923233	-5.31	0.000	-21.6517 -9.414909

5-rasm. Regression tahlil natijasi⁷

$(a + b) > 1$ bo'lsa, unda ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi iqtisodiy taraqqiyot sharoitida ishlab chiqarish natijalari ishlab chiqarish omillari o'sishiga qaraganda tezroq o'sib borishi sharoitida omillar va ishlab chiqarish natijalari o'rtasidagi munosabatni etarli darajada tavsiflaydi. Agar $(a + b) < 1$ bo'lsa, u holda ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi iqtisodiy regressiya sharoitida ishlab chiqarish natijalari ishlab chiqarish omillari o'sishiga qaraganda sekinroq o'sib borishi bilan omillar va ishlab chiqarish natijalari o'rtasidagi munosabatni etarli darajada tavsiflaydi.

O'sish sur'atlari - makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik

koeffitsiyentidir.

Kobb-Duglas ishlab chiqarish funksiyasining yana bir takomillashtirgan olim J.Tinbergen hisoblanadi, u ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyotning iqtisodiy o'zgarishga mustaqil o'zgaruvchiga ta'sirini hisobga olishni taklif qildi. Shu maqsadda u asl Kobb - Duglas formulasidagi omillar sonini g ning kuchiga e ning natural logarifmli asosini qo'shimcha omil bilan to'ldirdi. Shu asnodan biz KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatan miqdorni - Y deb olsak, investitsiyadagi miqdori(mlrd so'm)- X_3 ni K va KBXTda band bo'lganlar soni - X_4 ni L qilib olib J.Tinbergen tomonidan takomillashtirilgan modelni tuzib olamiz.

6 Muallif tomonidan topilgan regression tahlil hisob kitobi

7 Stata14 amaliy paketi erdamida muallif tomonidan topilgan regression tahlil hisob kitobi.

J.Tinbergen tomonidan Kobb-Duglas ishlab chiqarish funksiyasini takomillashgan shaklidan foydalandik. Unga g darajasidagi ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyotning iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'sir kuchiga t - davrlarni ta'sirini oldik va quyidagi shakilda ifodaladik.

$$Y = A \times K^m \times L^{(1-m)} \times e^{g \cdot t}$$

Bu tenglamadan ko'rinib turibdiki, ishlab chiqarish, ikki xarajat va ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot orasidagi munosabat nochiqli. Biroq bu modelni natural logarifmlash orqali chiziqli ko'rinishda o'zgartirib hisoblanadi:

$$\ln Y = \ln A + \alpha \cdot \ln K + \beta \cdot \ln L + g \cdot t \cdot \ln e$$

$$= B + \alpha \ln K + \beta \ln L + \omega \cdot t, \quad \text{bunda } B = \ln A \text{ va } g = \omega$$

Shunday qilib, yozilgan model B, α , β va ω parametrlari chiziqli ko'rinishda va shuning

6-rasm. KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatan miqdori va tuzilgan modelning hisoblangan Y qiymati⁸

uchun u chiziqli regressiya modelidir. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, Y va K, L o'zgaruvchilarda chiziqsiz edi, ammo natural logarifmlanganidan so'ng bu o'zgaruvchilar chiziqli bo'ldi. Qisqacha aytganda (7) tenglama - bu log-log, ikki tomonli log yoki log chiziqli model hisoblanadi. Biroq 4-rasm natijasiga qaraydigan bo'lsak, investitsiyadagi

. reg LK L.LK

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	21
Model	87.0552478	1	87.0552478	F(1, 19)	=	2047.83
Residual	.807707113	19	.042510901	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	87.8629549	20	4.39314775	R-squared	=	0.9908
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9903
				Root MSE	=	.20618

	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
LK					
LK					
LL	1.008556	.0222871	45.25	0.000	.9619085 1.055203
_cons	.2944899	.1891825	1.56	0.136	-.1014736 .6904534

7-rasm. AR(1) modelning ryegression tahlil natijasi⁹

8 Stata14 amaliy paketi ёрдамида муаллиф томонидан топилган регрессион тахлил ҳисоб китоби.
9 Stata14 амалий пакети ёрдамида муаллиф томонидан топилган регрессион тахлил ҳисоб китоби.

miqdori(mlrd so'm) K t-student mezoniga asosan ishonchsiz koeffitsiyentga ega bo'ldi. Shuni inobatga olgan holda R.Solou tomonidan takomillashtirilgan Kobb-Duglas funksiyasini qo'llaymiz.

Yuqoridagi Regression Tahlil Natijasida Quyidagi Shakilda Modelimiz Hosil Bo'ldi:

$$LY = B + \alpha * \ln K + \beta * \ln L$$

Shunda

$$Y = (1,79461e-07) * K^{0,5713078} * L^{2,351587}$$

Agarda Tuzilgan Modelni Tahlil Qiladigan Bo'lsak, Determinatsiya Koeffitsiyenti 0,99 Ga Teng, Fisher Mezoni Qiymati 1245,9 Ga Ya'ni Tanlangan Model Shakli To'g'ri Va Ahamiyatli Ekanligini Ifodalydi, Shuningdek, Topilgan Barcha Koeffitsiyentlar T-Styudent Mezonida Bo'yicha Ishonchli.

Grafikka Asosan Solishtiriladigan Bo'lsak, Tuzilgan Modelning Hisoblangan Y Qiymati Ehtimollik Asosida 99 Foiz Reallikka Yaqinligini Ifodalamoqda. Shuningdek, Ekonometrik Modellashtirishni Davom Etirgan Holda, Modelda Qatnashgan K Va L O'zgaruvchilarning Kelgusidagi Prognoz Qiymatlarini Topib Olamiz. Bunda N - Tartibli Avtoregression Modellar(Ar)Dan Foydalanamiz.

Tahlil Natijasiga Asosan Ar(1) Modelning Barcha Qiymatlari Ijobiydir. Shunga Asosan Modelning Shakli Quyidagicha Bo'ldi:

$$Ar(1) = 0,2944899 + 1,008556 * L1.Lk$$

Yuqoridagi Regression Tahlil Natijasiga E'tibor Beradigan Bo'lsak, Bu Modelning Natijalari Ham Ijobiy Qiymatlardan Tashkil Topgan. Lag Li Modelni Hosil Qilganda Quyidagi Shakilga Ega Bo'ldi.

$$Ar(1) = 0,9391927 + 0,8996358 * L1.Ll$$

Shuningdek, Yuqoridagi 9-Modelga Asosan Kbxt Umumiy Hajmi, Yaimga Nisbatan Miqdorni Prognoz Qiymatini Topib Olishdan Oldin, Modelning Prognozning Standart Xatoligi Va T-Critical=1,7291328 Qiymatini Topib

. reg LL L.LL

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	21
Model	1.29803765	1	1.29803765	F(1, 19)	=	2021.55
Residual	.012199806	19	.000642099	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	1.31023754	20	.065511877	R-squared	=	0.9907
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9902
				Root MSE	=	.02534

	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
LL					
LL					
LL	.8996358	.0200089	44.96	0.000	.8577566 .941515
_cons	.9391927	.1796086	5.23	0.000	.5632677 1.315118

8-rasm. AR(1) modelning regression tahlil natijasi¹⁰

years	K	L	lb0	yhat2	ub0
2021	244962.7	10070.67	308510.8	557630.6	800368.7
2022	365681.8	10213.64	498271.5	724691.8	1054000
2023	547766.8	10344.01	637102	940515.8	1388428
2024	823359.4	10462.71	812452.6	1219373	1830101
2025	1241931	10570.65	1033696	1579802	2414419
2026	1879892	10668.72	1312644	2045921	3188826

9-rasm. O'rta muddatli prgnoz qiymatlar¹¹

Olamiz. So'ngra Prognoz Qiymatining O'zgarish Intervalini Topib Olamiz.

Tadqiqot natijasi

Topilgan tahlil natijalariga asosan KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatan miqdori o'rtaacha katta ehtimollikda 2022 yilda 724 691,8 mlrd.so'mni tashkil etadigan bo'lsa, u ko'rsatkich 2026 yilga borib 2 045 921 mlrd. so'mga etadi. Agarda KBXT umumiy hajmining investitsiyadagi miqdori(mlrd so'm) 2022 yilda 365 681,8 mlrd.so'mni tashkil etasa va u ko'rsatkich 2026 yilga borib 1 879 892 mlrd. so'mni hamda KBXTda band bo'lganlar soni 2022 yilda 10 213 tani va 2026 yilda 10 668 taga tenglashsa KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatan miqdori yuqoridagi ta'kidlangan miqdorga o'sishi mumkin. Shu bilan birgalikda KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatani 2022 yilda 498 271,5 mlrd.so'mdan 1 054 000 mlrd. so'm miqdorgacha o'zgarib turish ehtimolligi mavjud. 2026 yildagi prognoz qiymati esa KBXT umumiy hajmi, YAIMga nisbatani 1 312 644 mlrd.so'mdan 3 188 826 mlrd.so'm oralig'ida tebranishi mumkin.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

1. Milliy iqtisodiyotda kichik biznesning barqaror rivojlanishi asoslarini, bozor mexanizmi, jumladan, firmalarning normal foyda olish uchun raqobatchilik muhiti sharoitida kichik biznes subyektlari ko'satkichlarini tahlil qilish, tadbirkorlik subyektlarining YAIMdagi ulushini o'rganib borish hamda prognoz ma'lumotlar olish kelgusidagi soha istiqbolini rivojlantiradi.

2. Respublikada kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning vujudga kelish zaminini, shakllanishi bosqichlari va rivojlanish jarayonlarini aniqlash hamda barqarorlik ko'rsatkichlarini o'rganish kelgusida tadbirkorlik subyektlarining barqarorlik omili sifatida xizmat qilishi va kutilmagan tashqi ta'sirlarga chidamli bo'lish imkonini beradi.

3. Mamlakatimizda kichik biznesni ko'llab-quvvatlashda amalga oshirilgan tarkibiy o'zgarishlar, tadbirkorlikning barqaror rivojlanishini rag'batlantirishning zamonaviy usullarini takomillashtirib borish, bu borada o'zgaruvchan bozor muhitiga tez moslashish, xizmat turlari va mahsulot turlarini iste'mol talabidan kelib chiqib o'zgartirish imkoniyatini hisobga olish.

10 Muallif tomonidan topilgan regression tahlil hisob kitobi.
11 Muallif tomonidan topilgan regression tahlil hisob kitobi.

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Intilganga
tole yor!

